

**A Precarious Task:
Science Indicators, Research Assessment, and Science Policy in the United States**

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University of Pittsburgh, 2026

This dissertation examines the evolution of science indicators in the United States from the 1970s to the present. It traces how indicators have been constructed, interpreted, and adopted across three historical periods and considers how they have been used to make claims about research quality and value. The analysis is based on inductive thematic analysis of approximately 200 documents, including federal reports, congressional hearings, policy memoranda, and scholarly literature.

The dissertation makes three primary contributions. First, it identifies the operationalization of evaluative concepts into indicators as a key site where governance is enacted. Second, it documents a growing distance between indicators and the phenomena they indicate. While this distance is acknowledged early in the development of science indicators, it becomes more difficult to track as indicators become embedded in infrastructures and begin to travel across contexts. Third, it distinguishes between research quality and research value as analytically distinct but historically conflated concepts, demonstrating the extent to which their persistent conflation has complicated research assessment and science policy for over fifty years.

The findings of this dissertation support several recommendations. First, evaluative terms should be explicitly identified and defined prior to their operationalization. Second, evaluators should remain attentive to the distinction between research quality and research value, recognizing that they often speak to different audiences. Third, the space between an indicator and the

phenomenon it should be acknowledged and actively protected. Finally, the use of indicators as evaluative tools should be approached with humility, recognizing their capacity to shape behavior and reorganize complex sociotechnical systems in ways that extend beyond their original intent.

These contributions take on particular significance in the current moment. Recent policy developments - notably the Executive Order on “Gold Standard Science” - signal a more explicit intervention into the terms of evaluation themselves. Understood within the longer history traced in this dissertation, such developments can be understood as intensifications of prior dynamics, in which control is exercised through the definition, operationalization, and enforcement of evaluative terms.

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1.0 Introduction

This dissertation explores the evolution of science indicators as tools of research assessment and science policy in the U.S. between 1972 and 2025. More specifically, it explores the priorities and concerns of those engaged in debates about their development and use. Since their formal introduction into the science policy and research assessment landscape in the early 70s, indicator use has proliferated across research assessment interventions at every level of the research ecosystem, informing funding decisions at the federal and foundation level, informing national rankings, and influencing decisions about which faculty to hire, promote, and grant tenure. Simultaneous with their introduction has been a rising chorus of criticism about their validity and unintended consequences, with researchers across varied disciplines taking a lead in first documenting the many concerns about evaluative indicators and ultimately serving as active advocates for research assessment reform. Primary among the critiques raised about indicator-driven research assessment (IDRA) is that it fails to account for the values and priorities of researchers themselves – that indicator-driven interventions prioritize quantity over quality, exacerbate entrenched biases, “reward” only certain outputs common to certain disciplines, and are easily gamed – a manifestation of the “perverse incentives” many argue they have become.¹

¹ Diana Hicks et al., “The Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics,” *Nature* 520, no. 7548 (2015): 7548, <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>; Aisha Al-Janabi, “Publish in English or Perish,” *Chemistry World*, April 2022, <https://www.chemistryworld.com/careers/publish-in-english-or-perish/4014820.article>; Basma Albanna et al., “Publication Outperformance among Global South Researchers: An Analysis of Individual-Level and Publication-Level Predictors of Positive Deviance,” *Scientometrics* 126, no. 10 (2021): 8375–431, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04128-1>; Mario Biagioli and Alexandra Lippman, “Introduction: Metrics and the New Ecologies of Academic Misconduct,” in *Gaming the Metrics: Misconduct and Manipulation in Academic Research*, ed. Mario Biagioli and Alexandra Lippman (The MIT Press, 2020), <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11087.001.0001>.

Science indicators were formally introduced in the United States in 1972 as a means of assessing “the health of science” as a national enterprise.² Common examples of science indicators are patent counts, numbers of Nobel prizes awarded and, as are particularly relevant to this dissertation, various forms of citation analysis – often referred to in the aggregate as “bibliometrics”. The actual development of such measures long predates the term, as scholars have, for centuries, tracked citations, awards, and other markers of peer esteem.³ What sets these measures apart as indicators is, among other factors, the purposeful nature of their use. It is this shift toward evaluative utility that began to change in the latter part of the 20th century, as formal efforts to track indicators of “the health” of the scientific enterprise in the United States were officially mandated by way of a change in legislation tasking the National Science Foundation (NSF) with the biannual requirement of reporting on the state of science across the country, and as previously informal citation analyses were developed into stabilized methodologies adopted for evaluative practices.⁴ The report series that was born from this initiative was called *Science Indicators* – the inaugural edition was produced in 1972.⁵

Scholars’ inclination to calculate and compare rates of citation has a long and well-documented history. In a chapter contributed to Cassidy Sugimoto and Blaise’s *Beyond Bibliometrics: Harnessing Multidimensional Indicators of Scholarly Impact*, Nicola de Bellis

² An Act to Amend the National Science Foundation Act of 1950 to Make Changes and Improvements in the Organization and Operation of the Foundation, and for Other Purposes, H.R. 5404, 90th Congress 2nd Session, 1968, 82 Stat. 360 (1968), <https://www.govinfo.gov/app/details/STATUTE-82>.

³ Nicola De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” in *Beyond Bibliometrics: Harnessing Multidimensional Indicators of Scholarly Impact*, ed. Blaise Cronin and Cassidy R. Sugimoto (The MIT Press, 2014), <http://direct.mit.edu/books/book/4039/chapter/167946/Science-Metrics-and-Science-Policy>.

⁴ An Act to Amend the National Science Foundation Act of 1950 to Make Changes and Improvements in the Organization and Operation of the Foundation, and for Other Purposes.

⁵ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, Science Indicators (National Science Foundation, 1973), <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED084150>.

provides a particularly engaging account of this history, tracing the interest in citation as a reflection of peer esteem to the 1920s, via an early study by F.J. Cole and N.B Eales.⁶ Francis Narin, contracted by NSF to draft a report detailing the history of bibliometrics, distinguishes between evaluative and more curatorial interests in citation analysis, where the latter supports more informed decision making on the part of librarians seeking to select the most relevant journals to support a particular discipline or department, and where the former supports judgement or the measurement of some aspect of a scientific activity or output.⁷

Information scientist Eugene Garfield is credited with the developing the methodology and related indices that have contributed to the efflorescence of citation-driven metrics that are now inescapably familiar to scholars, librarians, and science policy makers. Eugene Garfield first articulated the idea of citation indexing in a 1955 *Science* article “Citation Indexes for Science,” in which he posited that tracking references between papers could function as a retrieval tool as well as a means to map relationships among scientific works.⁸ In 1960, he founded the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI), through which he later launched the Science Citation Index (SCI) and, later, the journal impact factor – a measure of “impact” as calculated by the rate at which articles in specific journals accrue citations.⁹ The JIF was initially conceived as a tool to help librarians compare journals and guide collection decisions, however it was quickly picked up –

⁶ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 28.

⁷ Francis Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics: The Use of Publication and Citation Analysis in the Evaluation of Scientific Activity*, in *Computer Horizons* (Computer Horizons, 1976), 1, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269992229_Evaluative_Bibliometrics_The_Use_of_Publication_and_Citation_Analysis_in_the_Evaluation_of_Scientific_Activity.

⁸ Eugene Garfield, “Citation Indexes for Science,” *Science* 122, no. 3159 (1955): 108–11, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1749965>.

⁹ Eugene Garfield, “Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation,” *Science* 178, no. 4060 (1972): 471–79, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1735096>.

and in increasingly formal, administrative fashion – as a means of evaluating not only journals but also, ultimately, the impact and quality of individual scholars’ contributions themselves.

Garfield’s SCI data was included as a data source in the initial editions of NSF’s *Science Indicators* reports, selected by virtue of an observed correlation between the number of citations accrued by a given publication and the purported quality or impact of that work. Citation data was used in these reports as one of the few identifiable indicators of the quality of U.S.-funded research.¹⁰ However, from the very introduction of these methodologies and the publication of the *Science Indicators* reports, they were met with active and sometimes emotional debate over both the validity of using quantitative measures to capture qualitative characteristics of research, and the consequences of their increasingly institutionalized use. Such critiques arose from the scholarly community in quick response to the publication of the first *Science Indicators* report and have continued to this day, as the use of impact factors and other quantitative metrics has proliferated across what has become an increasingly digital and networked research infrastructure.

This dissertation tracks these developments, focusing on three periods identified as particularly consequential in the evolution of science indicators. These periods were identified by virtue of their accordance with three primary qualifiers, the first of which being their specific relevance within a U.S. context. While indicator-driven solutions are in some respects now agnostic of borders, different countries do maintain different national policies regarding research assessment across their public institutions.¹¹ This study focuses specifically on IDRA within the context of the United States. The second qualifier used in identifying the periods included in this

¹⁰ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 7.

¹¹ “REF 2029,” Research Excellence Framework, REF, accessed February 23, 2026, <https://2029.ref.ac.uk/>.

study pertains to the negotiation of specifically indicator-driven solutions to research assessment, while the third pertains to the extent to which both policymakers and researchers were engaged in those negotiations. In identifying the three periods ultimately selected for inclusion, I looked for moments in which efforts to direct indicator-driven research assessment were accompanied by sustained discourse across policy and scholarly venues.

The first period so identified encompasses the period in which the NSF's *Science Indicators* reports were first published and debated. The second captures a period in the late 1990s and early 2000s, by which point quantitative performance measurement had taken hold across a variety of environments, emerging in the policy sphere in an initiative to leverage indicators in effort to “make science policy more scientific,” while across academia, frustration with their increased use – combined with an increased sensitivity to their limitations and consequences – was rising. The third period is the most recent and is closely tied to the open science movement, seeking to “open” science across the various stages of its lifecycle by ensuring that protocols, instrumentation, and outputs are readily accessible and extensively documented, thereby enabling reuse, reproduction, and, ideally, more equitable entry into the culture and practice of science.

This third period is referred to as that of “Values-Driven Research Assessment,” owing to the heavily value-inflected language of this period. Indeed, the curiosity that motivated this research was in part sparked by the rhetoric of this period. In early 2022, a call for reform issued from the Paris Open Science European Conference, centering a “need to align what we assess with what we value” and recognizing “that openness improves the quality, efficiency and impact of

research.”¹² The same year saw multiple advances in the development of open science indicators – quantitative measures that had been developed by open science publishers and others to track instances of open science behavior across the research ecosystem.¹³ These indicators seemed to meet a need widely expressed by many open science and research assessment reform advocates to incentivize and reward open science practices in the same manner that citation analysis had served over the years to incentivize publication in high impact journals.

This dissertation was inspired by a series of questions arising from these developments. First, how have values become encoded in indicator-driven research assessment? Whose are represented where, and what are the consequences of these arrangements? Second, if incentive-aligned research assessment is suspected of leading to unintended and potentially negative consequences, how has it come to pass that new incentive-aligned research assessment mechanisms have also been strategically aligned with the asserted values of a particular group? Inspired by the observation that research assessment reformers may be in the process of recreating the very construct they are seeking to change, I designed this research as an exploration of the evolution of science indicators as tools of research assessment and science policy, focusing specifically on the priorities, assumptions, and agendas embedded in the efforts of multiple parties to take control over the mechanisms through which science is measured and thereby governed in the United States. I chose to do so by centering my analysis on the documentary record, performing inductive thematic analysis over roughly 200 documents capturing the trajectory of this evolution.

¹² Paris Open Science European Conference, *Paris Call – OSEC 2022*, 2022, <https://osec2022.eu/paris-call/>.

¹³ Iain Hrynaszkiewicz, “PLOS Partners with DataSeer to Develop Open Science Indicators,” *The Official PLOS Blog*, September 14, 2022, <https://theplosblog.plos.org/2022/09/plos-partners-with-dataseer-to-develop-open-science-indicators/>.

1.1 Key Terms

Definition of terms is a critical concern of this research, as a pervasive theme surfaced by this analysis concerns the extent to which terms that are foundational to the discourse are used in ways that are incommensurate one another. This dissertation does not set out to litigate definitions broadly, however it is necessary to define the ways some key terms have been interpreted for the purposes of this analysis alone. Guiding definitions of key terms will be set forth below, while a more fulsome discussion of the extent and application of the study's three themes is provided in Section 1.4: Themes of Study.

An *indicator* is a type of proxy measure that is common to social statistics. In order to quantitatively track socially understood but ontologically evasive concepts it is first necessary to identify what might serve as an appropriate indicator of the concept in question. Crime is often used as an exemplar: if one were to outline the phenomena that might meaningfully indicate a crime had taken place, how might they do so? A broken window might suggest a crime had taken place, as would a discrete instance of theft, the report of that theft, and any resulting conviction. Each, however, has its own constraints and affordances as an indicator of crime.

In providing a history of science indicators as tools of science policy, Benoît Godin draws on baselines provided by the Department of Health, Education, and Welfare's 1970s report *Towards a Social Report*, to establish that an indicator must first and foremost be "a statistics of direct normative interest," adding to this baseline that an indicator must also occur as part of a longitudinal series such that it might track change over time, that it must be one among many ("a lone statistic can rarely be a reliable indicator") and, finally, drawing from Gerald Holton that it

must be based on a model “that explicitly tests some assumption, hypothesis, or theory.”¹⁴ Each of these criterion are vital in distinguishing an indicator from other measures, however Godin’s care to include discussion of their intentional purpose is of particular relevance to this study.

Various scientometric and bibliometric measures have been leveraged as *science indicators* – those used to measure and/or assess characteristics of a given scientific enterprise or actor – particularly since their introduction in the early 1970s. This dissertation draws on the definition adapted by Nicola de Bellis to understand *scientometrics* as “the quantitative methods of the research on the development of science as an informational process.”¹⁵ *Bibliometrics* is often categorized as a type of scientometrics that is specifically concerned with applying such quantitative methods to the textual, published outputs of scientific research, of which citation analysis is recognized as a common exemplar.¹⁶ It is important to note that citation measures and other biblio- and scientometrics are not always indicators – whether they meet the criteria depends on their intended function.

In the context of this dissertation, *science* is understood as a social process that is normatively and collectively governed, bound by the shared commitment to exercising rigor in the systematic pursuit of new knowledge, and informed through public processes of information sharing and consensus building. This frame emerges as a bricolage of others’ reflections, strongly

¹⁴ Department of Health, Education and Welfare, *Towards a Social Report* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 1970), 97, quoted in Benoit Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, Routledge Studies in the History of Science, Technology and Medicine (Routledge, 2005), 107; Gerald Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” in *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, ed. Yehuda Elkana et al. (John Wiley & Sons, 1978), 53.

¹⁵ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 23.

¹⁶ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 23; Robin Chin Roemer and Rachel Borchardt, *Meaningful Metrics: A 21st Century Librarian’s Guide to Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, and Research Impact* (Association of College and Research Libraries, 2015), 3, <https://www.alastore.ala.org/content/meaningful-metrics-21st-century-librarians-guide-bibliometrics-altmetrics-and-research>.

informed by Robert Merton and Harriet Zuckerman's canonical work in establishing science as a social system maintained through normative feedback and incentives, and mutually informed through the broad dissemination of information.¹⁷ This is extended and given critical nuance by John Ziman, who opens *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science* by first exploring what science is not: it is not, according to Ziman, solely mastery of a given pursuit or discipline, although under the best of circumstances science might nurture these outcomes. Science is also not merely "the study of the material world," although that is frequently a subject. Science is also not sufficiently defined by the scientific method, although such method is a critical support.¹⁸ What distinguishes science, according to Ziman, is the pursuit of public knowledge made possible through the process of arriving at consensus. Here, public knowledge can be achieved through communication of various forms, with publication serving as the final ratification and "public" debut of a given contribution.¹⁹

Ziman commits much of his essay to a demonstration of the folly inherent in trying to define science too precisely. He focuses much of his observation here on efforts to distinguish between "pure" or basic science – described by Vannevar Bush as arising from "the free play of free intellects, working on subjects of their own choice, in the manner dictated by their curiosity for exploration of the unknown" – and technology, or applied science, offering a hypothetical to

¹⁷ Robert K. Merton, "The Normative Structure of Science," in *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, ed. Norman W. Storer (The University of Chicago Press, 1973); Robert K. Merton and Harriet Zuckermann, "Institutionalized Patterns of Evaluation in Science," in *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, ed. Norman W. Storer (The University of Chicago Press, 1973).

¹⁸ John Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science* (Cambridge University Press, 1968), 2–4.

¹⁹ Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science*, 109.

illustrate the practical challenges of trying to define one in a way that surgically distinguishes it from the other:

Suppose, for example, that we are researching on the phenomenon of ‘fatigue’ in metals. We are almost forced into the position of saying that on Monday, Wednesday and Friday we are just honest seekers after truth... whilst on Tuesday, Thursday and Saturday we are... trying to stop aeroplanes from falling to pieces.²⁰

What this dissertation borrows from Ziman is, primarily, that seeking to precisely define science is an effort that may have diminishing returns. Rather than seeking to identify or endorse any specific definition of science, this dissertation takes that science can be understood a social system in which new knowledge claims are verified, dismissed, adapted, and cultivated through the pursuit of consensus as is supported and often communicated through public forms of information exchange.

1.2 Significance of the Study

As this dissertation documents, debates over the measurement and evaluation of scientific activity are both long-running and wide-ranging. Spanning science policy, information science, and the sociology and philosophy of science, related discourse has now extended through several decades, spilling over occasionally from scholarly and policy venues into the mainstream. Since their formal introduction in the early 1970s, science indicators have evolved into familiar performance metrics deployed on ad hoc, individual, and systemic bases, taken to be – and now regularly packaged and sold as – practical tools for informing decision-making, supporting impartial comparison, and advancing accountability and transparency. Concurrently, voluminous

²⁰ Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science*, 23.

and at times passionate critiques have accompanied the rise of indicators, raising persistent and often difficult questions about what indicators indicate, how any meaning they impart is stabilized, what their implications are, and whose agendas they advance.

This study contributes to the now decades-old debates about indicator-driven research assessment by helping to clarify how indicators shape, and are shaped by, the systems and outputs they were designed to measure. First, it centers definition as a consequential political act, imbued with the priorities, assumptions, and agendas of those who have either claimed or been endowed with the authority to say what science is, under what circumstances it is deemed legitimate, what it is worth, and to whom. This study is not the first and likely will not be the last to center definition as a political act. Rather, it draws on the canonical work of Lucy Suchman, Geoffrey Bowker, and Susan Leigh Star to assert that the categories into which research and its outputs are placed do have politics, and that the tools developed to create and maintain these categories have become tools of governance.²¹ By focusing on the priorities, assumptions, and agendas underlying IDRA, this study trains attention away from indicators themselves and onto those developing and debating them. At interest here is the social motivation – the “why” rather than the “how” or the “if”.

By focusing on the meaning that is embedded in indicators, this study assumes the explicit position that indicators are neither neutral nor objective measures, instead adopting Steve Woolgar’s position that measurements are representative technologies – proxies for embedded assumptions. In “Beyond the Citation Debate,” Woolgar asks his audience a clear and difficult question: why are those concerned with research assessment so intractably committed to citation

²¹ Lucy Suchman, “Do Categories Have Politics? The Language/Action Perspective Reconsidered,” *Computer Supported Cooperative Work* 2, no. 3 (1994): 177–90, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00749015>; Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star, *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences* (The MIT Press, 2000).

analysis as an indicator of research quality in the face of significant evidence that citation analysis is, in fact, a poor measure of quality? Observing, effectively, that quality is in the eye of the beholder, he argues that it therefore cannot reliably serve as a stable object of measurement.²² Rather than continuing to try, he suggests that those concerned with research assessment might instead turn their attentions to examining their motivations, calling specifically for a “sociology of measurement technologies” that might illuminate “what happens to the nature and conduct of scientific... research as its practitioners are increasingly asked to become more responsive to criteria of utility and policy relevance.”²³ This dissertation takes up that invitation by tracing the priorities, assumptions, and agendas encoded within science indicators. It therefore contributes to a sociology of measurement technologies by reorienting focus from whether indicators “work” to what it means for them to work – and what it means when they fail to.

A third contribution of this study can be found in its urgent contemporary relevance. Indicator-driven research assessment and the governance of science in the United States remain actively contested, with actors across the research ecosystem openly advancing normative agendas through the redesign and reinterpretation of the sociotechnical systems that have structured the research ecosystem for more than fifty years. Indicators are now being mobilized to direct scientific activity – to define what counts as a valued output, what products and processes are rewarded, and to whom science is accountable. As will be discussed in this dissertation’s conclusion, explicit control over research evaluation at the federal level has recently been claimed by fiat in an Executive Order issued by President Donald J. Trump that relocates evaluative

²² Steve Woolgar, “Beyond the Citation Debate: Towards a Sociology of Measurement Technologies and Their Use in Science Policy,” *Science and Public Policy* 18, no. 5 (1991): 321, <https://doi.org/10.1093/spp/18.5.319>.

²³ Woolgar, “Beyond the Citation Debate,” 319.

authority from its traditional home in the scientific community to deputized appointees installed across federal funding agencies.²⁴ In offering an historical analysis of how priorities, assumptions, and agendas have become encoded in the representational tools and infrastructures that support research assessment, this study equips scholars and practitioners with conceptual tools for recognizing how governance operates through definition, measurement, and infrastructure.

1.3 Research Questions

This dissertation addresses two primary research questions.

Question 1

How have science indicators evolved as instruments of research assessment in policy and academic contexts over time?

Question 2

How have debates over science indicators reflected changing priorities and assumptions in research assessment?

²⁴ Donald J. Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science,” The White House, May 23, 2025, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/05/restoring-gold-standard-science/>.

1.4 Themes of Study

This dissertation contextualizes the history of science indicators within the broader evolution of research assessment and science policy in the United States. This research is inspired by questions about how normative motivations become embedded in tools developed to both evaluate and govern scientific activity, drawing on an inductive thematic analysis of the documentary record to identify recurrent concerns surfacing in the long-running debates over indicator development and use. I approach this analysis by considering the relationship between three interconnected themes: control, quality, and value. The proceeding section will describe these themes and their function within this research.

1.4.1 Control

The understanding of control that has been leveraged throughout this study has been informed by the scholarship of historian and sociologist James R. Beniger. In his 1986 treatise on what he noted as a “control revolution,” Beniger writes that most common definitions of control tend to suggest a “purposive influence towards a predetermined goal,” continuing on to emphasize these dual components: “*influence* of one agent over another, meaning that the former causes changes in the behavior of the latter; and *purpose*, in the sense that influence is directed toward some prior goal of the controlling agent.”²⁵ This provides two nuanced but critical qualifications – first, that influence can cause but must not inevitably produce change and, second, that influence

²⁵ James R. Beniger, *The Control Revolution: Technological and Economic Origins of the Information Society* (Harvard University Press, 1986), 7.

must be trained on a prior goal, whatever that goal may be. He continues by positioning information processing as being “inseparable from the concept of control”:

Information processing is essential to all purposive activity, which is by definition goal directed and must therefore involve the continual comparison of current states to future goals.... So integral to control is this comparison of inputs to stored programs that the word control itself derives from the medieval Latin verb *contrarotulare*, to compare something ‘against the rolls’, the cylinders of paper that served as official records in ancient times.²⁶

Comparisons, of course, require standardization. Before one can compare one measurement or classification to another, one must first be certain that they are operating with shared definitions and assumptions. Identifying, operationalizing, and then deploying units of measure is no easy task, as complicating nuances and context are necessarily stripped away so that described units might fit within the confines of their classifications. In *Sorting Things Out: Classification and its Consequences*, Geoffrey Bowker and Susan Leigh Star reflect upon historical tables documenting causes of death over various jurisdictions and across many centuries, illustrating the extent to which categories can define both interpretation and outcomes. “Death by wolf alone becomes impossible by 1948,” they report, referring to the fact “death by wolf” dropped from that year’s edition of the World Health Organization’s *International Classification of Diseases*.²⁷ Several pages later, a reprinted table of casualties that they share dating to 1662 declares it possible to die of either “worms” or, “teeth and worms”.²⁸

Categories such as these are certainly unsettling, and also move the reader to wonder what, precisely, they mean. Quite a bit of information can be lost in pursuit of quantification and comparison, as Beniger takes care to point out. Drawing connections between information

²⁶ Beniger, *The Control Revolution: Technological and Economic Origins of the Information Society*, 8.

²⁷ Bowker and Star, *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences*, 19.

²⁸ Bowker and Star, *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences*, 22–23.

processing and control, he calls in Max Weber's conception of rationalization to explain that while the term might have "a variety of meanings... most definitions are subsumed by one essential idea: control can be increased not only by increasing the capability to process information but also by decreasing the amount of information to be processed." One might think of this process as a denuding of context – a stripping away of the contingent, qualitative, or contextual details to distill an object to a classifiable manifestation. This process is necessarily guided by priorities: there must have been some useful reason to distinguish between worms and teeth and worms in 1662, and to stop tracking deaths by wolf in 1948. These reasons were guided by someone's priorities, and themselves guide how one might calculate nearby mortal risks – how one might make decisions.²⁹ Such purposeful influence is recognized throughout this study as control.

1.4.2 Quality

Quality, as it pertains to science or research, is a highly variable concept, long debated and heavily premised on definitions. The deeply contested nature of "good science" thus stands as a natural impediment to any effort made to measure scientific quality through quantifiable measures: first task in doing so would be to identify a reliable proxy for quality – an indicator that might remain meaningful and measurable over time. As has been documented by many scholars over many years, citations, citation counts, and more sophisticated citation analyses have long been a popular choice of proxies for scientific quality, premised on the assumption that citations are

²⁹ Beniger, *The Control Revolution: Technological and Economic Origins of the Information Society*, 15.

tokens of peer esteem, small votes of confidence cast by disciplinary and other scholarly peers as they cite sources valuable in the production of new contributions to the record.

The proliferation of citation-based indicators is one of the stories most relevant to this research, as is the proliferation of protest against them. This study joins many others in documenting the energetic push-back against citation-based indicators since their emergence as evaluative tools during the last half of the 20th century. Most studies critique their validity, accuracy, and consequences. Steve Woolgar's critique frames the problem much differently, calling into question the underlying assumption that quality is or can be a stable object of measure. Describing the potential that "there may be no such thing as quality out there" to measure as "an absolute last-ditch option" for the advocates and defenders of citation analysis, he makes the following observation: "citation analysis persists for reasons other than the fact that citations reliably measure something. Thus, when we ask about the value of citation analysis, we are not simply asking about technical reliability. We are... asking about the social basis for an institutionalized measurement practice."³⁰

In this dissertation, I also ask about the social basis for institutionalized measurement practices and, as such practices relate to the pursuit of or interest in scientific quality, I follow Woolgar's lead in understanding these as representational technologies. The goal of this research is not to define or arbitrate the meaning of scientific or research quality, but rather to trace how these concepts are understood, debated, defined, and proxied such that the result might illuminate the priorities, values, and agendas that animate them. As a general rule, the only restriction placed around the understanding of quality that guides this research is that it must be expressed in

³⁰ Woolgar, "Beyond the Citation Debate," 321.

qualitative terms. While elementary, this basic bounding is challenged throughout the literature, as quality is regularly conflated with those manifestations of research that can be counted.

A firmly held premise of this study is that the two must remain distinct, for the reasons outlined by Wendy Nelson Espeland and Michael Sauder in their article “Rankings and Reactivity: How Public Measures Recreate Social Worlds.” Espeland and Sauder situate the efforts to quantify qualities in the history of social statistics, referring to the tendency as “commensuration... the transformation of qualities into quantities that share a metric,” nothing that this is “a process that is fundamental to measurement.”³¹ Evoking Beniger, they cite among the dangers of commensuration its reliance on the reduction and simplification of otherwise meaningfully rich information, also citing integration as another unassuming but risky outcome: qualities quantified as metrics can become integrated and repurposed into systems outside of or adjacent to their original “habitat” – ultimately becoming detached from the objects they once described and repurposed as their own message, sent without necessary context. The dangers of this are laid bare by Espeland and Sauder:

The radical simplification of commensuration produces decontextualized, depersonalized numbers that are highly portable and easily made public.... The capacity of numbers to circulate widely is enhanced by their abstractness, which appears to eliminate the need for particularistic knowledge in interpreting them. We assume that the meaning of numbers is universal and stable. The erasure of context and the people who make numbers is crucial for their authority. We trust that the methods that accomplished this erasure were rigorous enough to constrain the discretion, politics, and biases of those who create them.³²

Throughout the course of this study, I have taken great care to neither rigidly define quality nor allow it to become commensurate with quantity. The former allows quality to emerge from the

³¹ Wendy Nelson Espeland and Michael Sauder, “Rankings and Reactivity: How Public Measures Recreate Social Worlds.,” *American Journal of Sociology* 113, no. 1 (2007): 16, 25729857, <https://doi.org/10.1086/517897>.

³² Espeland and Sauder, “Rankings and Reactivity,” 18.

literature as an artifact unearthed from discourse. The latter avoids replicating the very problem I am studying.

1.4.3 Value

Inspired by the framing offered by academic librarian R.H. Orr, the value of science is understood for the purposes of this dissertation as the good that science does.³³ Such value can refer to worth, benefit, or return on investment as articulated through evaluative and, often, quantitative claims. Analytically, it is identifiable in moments where actors seek to demonstrate what research produces, to what effect, and for whom. As with quality, this study does not advance a normative definition of value, but rather attends to how value is discussed and operationalized within research assessment discourse. Analytic focus is limited to those contexts in which value is made explicit through quantifiable expressions, including claims about impact, return on investment, productivity, benefit to beneficiaries, and the feasibility of measuring such outcomes in the first place.

It is important to note when framing the orientation to value leveraged throughout this study that axiological values – including ethical and moral commitments – are kept intentionally distinct from the econometric values that typify this theme. However, axiological values do play a central role in both the history and the analysis guiding this research. Indeed, morally inflected values play a critical role in what has been identified through this analysis as the Values-Driven Research Assessment period – one in which assertions about ethical values affect shared understandings of what good science is and what good it can, and should, do.

³³ R. H. Orr, “Measuring the Goodness of Library Services: A General Framework for Considering Quantitative Measures,” *Journal of Documentation* 29, no. 3 (1973): 317, <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb026561>.

1.5 Conclusion

In their book *Data Feminism*, Catherine D’Ignazio and Lauren Klein argue that “what gets counted counts”.³⁴ This dissertation proceeds from the perspective that how things get counted also counts, and that counting, particularly when it is done via proxy measures, is itself an act imbued with assumptions, priorities, and assumed authority – one that can matter very much indeed. This research positions indicator-driven research assessment as a political act, drawing on the above understandings of control, quality, and value to assert that in the act of negotiating, defining, and capturing proposed indicators of research quality and value, those involved in IDRA debates are, more broadly, engaged in a contest over the control of research.

The prior pages offer an introduction to the research questions and the methodological and epistemological orientation guiding this study. In the subsequent chapter, I detail the research design, methods, and commitments that informed my analysis. In the third chapter, I offer a review of existing literature on the subjects that are both referenced by and central to the questions of this dissertation, focusing on prior discussion of research assessment – including peer review and the use of evaluative bibliometrics – and the role, understanding, and negotiation of control, quality, and value across the research ecosystem over time. The chapters that follow this review of the literature share the study’s findings, organized chronologically and analytically around the three historical periods identified in this chapter, each of which is treated as an analytic case. The Science Indicators period is analyzed the fourth chapter, focusing on the development of science indicators as tools of science policy and on their early negotiation as measures of scientific quality and value.

³⁴ Catherine D’Ignazio and Lauren Klein, “4. ‘What Gets Counted Counts,’” *Data Feminism*, March 16, 2020, <https://data-feminism.mitpress.mit.edu/pub/h1w0nbqp/release/3>.

The Science of Science period is analyzed in the fifth chapter, tracing the expansion and contestation of evaluative metrics and the growing emphasis on indicator-driven governance. The Values-Driven Research Assessment period is analyzed in the sixth chapter, highlighting a notable shift toward normative strategy, advocacy, and infrastructural intervention. The final chapter synthesizes findings across these three chapters, reflecting on the ways in which quality and value have been defined and redefined over the years, the relationship between this contest and broader control over the research ecosystem, and what recommendations might be made in light of this history. Suggestions for future research are offered as well.

2.0 Research Design

This study employs a qualitative, interpretive research design to examine how science indicators and related research assessment initiatives have been negotiated across three defining periods in the history of U.S. science policy and research assessment. The purpose of the study is to identify and describe the priorities, assumptions, and agendas embedded within these initiatives, with a broader goal of understanding how indicator-driven research assessment has evolved as a mechanism of governance across the U.S. science and research apparatus.

The research design employed in this study has been influenced by the scholarship of sociologist Susan Leigh Star. In the opening pages of *Ecologies of Knowledge: Work and Politics in Science and Technology*, Star introduces the concept of ecologies of knowledge, observing a natural, mutually informing connection between the great complexities of the sociotechnical interplay cooperating in the production and process of science and suggesting that researchers in science and technology studies strive to cultivate an understanding of “the systemic properties of science by analogy with an ecosystem, and equally important, all the components that constitute the system.”³⁵ This study seeks to better understand the evolutionary role of measurement in research assessment and governance, proceeding from the perspective that the broad system of actors, institutions, technologies, and attendant norms and behaviors that support and inform such measurement can be understood as “the research ecosystem.”

³⁵ Susan Leigh Star, “Introduction,” in *Ecologies of Knowledge: Work and Politics in Science and Technology*, ed. Susan Leigh Star (State University of New York Press, 1995), 2.

As a study fundamentally concerned with the negotiation of meaning and inspired by observations regarding the effects of what Espeland and Sauder refer to as commensuration – a quantification of quality, ultimately resulting in a loss of meaning – an interpretive approach is critically important to its design. While this study is, in some respects, “about” measurement, it is not itself structured to measure anything. It also does not seek causal explanation, nor does it seek to test a specific hypothesis. Rather, this study was undertaken with the goal of developing analytically transferrable insights elicited through sustained engagement with a large and heterogeneous corpus of documentary material. The thematic patterns identified through this analysis are intended to serve as interpretive lenses through which control over the research enterprise, particularly as it is manifested in formal evaluation regimes, might be explored.

This research is situated in the complex tradition of STS, described by Edward J. Hackett and his coeditors of the 2007 *Handbook of Science and Technology Studies* as a fundamentally “interdisciplinary field that is creating an integrative understanding of the origins, dynamics, and consequences of science and technology.”³⁶ Susan Leigh Star has a bit more fun characterizing the field, referring to its contributors as “an omnivorous bunch.”³⁷ This study draws from the already interdisciplinary tradition of STS to pursue connections between information science, the history and sociology of science, and policy studies. In the same *Handbook of Science and Technology Studies*, Alan Irwin takes the position that, thanks to the contributions of STS scholars, “science policy” can be perhaps more accurately understood as “science governance,” and, further, that the study of this governance is “at the core” of STS, offering a reorientation that broadens the possible

³⁶ Edward J. Hackett et al., “Introduction,” in *The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies*, ed. Edward J. Hackett et al. (MIT Press, 2007), 1, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3338749>.

³⁷ Star, “Introduction,” 4.

conceptions of how governance works and at whose hands.³⁸ This study extends this tradition to undertake an examination of how governance – top-down and bottom-up – has evolved and become operationalized through the use of indicators. It thus explores not simply the fact of this evolution but, by virtue of the study’s interpretivist orientation, the priorities, assumptions, and agendas encoded into the systems that have emerged as political interventions into the process, progress, and governance of science.

2.1 Infrastructure Studies

A second concept introduced by Susan Leigh Star that has been incorporated into this study’s design is that of the ethnography of infrastructure, characterized as a practice of studying infrastructure with some of the tools and perspectives of ethnography.”³⁹ Generally associated with a researcher’s extended immersion into “the real world of the selected phenomenon or topic”, ethnographic approaches are often adopted by those interested in understanding how actors make sense of their worlds and how those understandings are shaped by social, material, and institutional contexts.⁴⁰ Ethnographic approaches have been used in the study of various cultures and cultural practices, as well as in the study of artifacts including technologies and institutions. Star extends this application to the study of infrastructure, noting the potential for such methods to surface

³⁸ Alan Irwin, “STS Perspectives on Science Governance,” in *The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies*, ed. Edward J. Hackett et al. (MIT Press, 2007), <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3338749>.

³⁹ Susan Leigh Star, “The Ethnography of Infrastructure,” *American Behavioral Scientist* 43, no. 3 (1999): 377, <https://journals-sagepub-com.pitt.idm.oclc.org/doi/abs/10.1177/00027649921955326>.

⁴⁰ Sylvain K. Cibangu, “A Memo of Qualitative Research for Information Science: Toward Theory Construction,” *Journal of Documentation* 69, no. 2 (2013): 202, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220411311300048>.

priorities, preferences, values, and assumptions that are built into the systems that shape, direct, and describe our lives.

This study is premised on the understanding that indicator-driven research assessment is an infrastructural technology supporting the broader practices of research and scholarly communication. Indeed, indicator-driven research assessment meets many of the criteria of an infrastructure as they are described Star. These include its embeddedness and transparency – the extents to which IDRA has been integrated into the larger infrastructures of research and scholarly communication, becoming “invisible” within them.⁴¹ They also include “[l]inks with conventions of practice” and an “embodiment of standards” that supports its ability to be “[plugged] into other standards and tools in systematized fashion”.⁴² A final and crucial set of observations made by Star about infrastructure that bears relevance to this study is that infrastructure generally “becomes visible on breakdown” and that it is modified incrementally over time. Towards this latter characteristic, she observes “no one is really in charge of infrastructure”.⁴³ That no one is really in charge of indicator-driven research assessment, that it has been modified by constituent social forces over time and that it has become quite visible upon breakdown are not only key characteristics of indicator-driven research assessment – they are also some of the key factors motivating this research.

Applying ethnographic methods to information infrastructure can seem straightforward when studying related practices in situ – for example, observing academic librarians’ implementation of a new cataloging platform. However, it becomes more challenging when

⁴¹ Star, “The Ethnography of Infrastructure,” 381.

⁴² Star, “The Ethnography of Infrastructure,” 381–82.

⁴³ Star, “The Ethnography of Infrastructure,” 382.

seeking to do so retrospectively – when seeking to understand how infrastructures evolved over time. In approaching this challenge, I sought to center attention on those artifacts that were well positioned to communicate negotiations between involved and affected parties – essentially, to seek out and examine a reliable documentary record of the discourse surrounding the development and use of science indicators in the U.S. I selected documents as my source, owing to their centrality to the discourse of both research and science policy. I chose thematic analysis as the study’s primary method, owing it its long-recognized utility in surfacing nuanced meaning from text. Each of these approaches is discussed in the following section.

2.2 Methodology

Thematic analysis is the primary analytic method employed in this study. Identified by Virginia Brown and Victoria Clarke as “a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data,” thematic analysis is a highly flexible method that can be applied across a wide variety of qualitative datasets and within studies framed by a similarly wide variety of theoretical and epistemological commitments.⁴⁴ It is so ubiquitous across qualitative research that Braun and Clarke commit their article to making a case for thematic analysis to be recognized not simply as qualitative analysis but as a foundational form of it. In its practical application, thematic analysis features rounds of interpretive analysis in pursuit of analytic themes in a manner that “minimally organizes and describes... data in (rich) detail,” and often offers an additional

⁴⁴ Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke, “Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology,” *Qualitative Research in Psychology* (London, United Kingdom) 3, no. 2 (2006): 79, <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.

interpretation of “various aspects of the research topic.”⁴⁵ Braun and Clarke identify six critical steps, including the necessity of acquainting one’s self with selected data, identifying initial codes, synthesizing these codes in search of broader themes, reviewing these themes, describing and naming them, and ultimately synthesizing resultant findings into a report.⁴⁶ It is important to note that while this study did follow the six steps outlined above, the actual process of doing so was highly iterative. The data corpus supporting this research comprised nearly 200 textual documents, offering a rich and heterogeneous set of primary sources documenting each period analyzed. The number and variety of these sources required multiple rounds of iterative review and analysis, the broad strokes of which are detailed in the sections that follow.

2.2.1 Document Analysis

While not performed in the style of a traditional historical analysis, this study does have an historical orientation, given that it is interested in the evaluation of science indicators of science policy and research assessment over the course of several decades. Written and otherwise textual documents generally comprise the majority of artifacts illustrating historical events and, in the case of research into the history of policy and scholarly debates, can be understood as the “natural habitat” for related discourse. Policy scholars Dvora Yanow and Frank Fischer each argue the value of an interpretive approach to policy studies and, in so doing, each also center documents and texts as critical resources to a fulsome interpretation of how arguments and meaning are both

⁴⁵ Braun and Clarke, “Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology,” 79.

⁴⁶ Braun and Clarke, “Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology,” 87.

formed and communicated in policy settings.⁴⁷ In the academic space, documents – largely in the form of peer-reviewed scholarly articles – are widely recognized as not only a primary but in fact a constitutive mechanism of communication. Sociologists of science Robert Merton and Harriet Zuckerman each center publications as foundational components of the social structure of science; John Ziman extends the argument further by suggesting that the very process of research is not complete until it is communicated made available for “public” debate via publication – “public” here referring to the internal community of researchers.⁴⁸

This study likewise understands documents to be central sites of argumentation, debate, and discourse across the policy and research communities. They are approached as artifacts, understood, as Glenn Bowen argues, to be partial and biased by both the authors’ perspective and goals as well as by the larger context – political, historical, discursive – in which they were drafted.⁴⁹ To mitigate against the potential limitations of document analysis, Bowen advises two broad safeguards – one regarding analytic approach and the other regarding selection. Toward the former, he advocates for an iterative approach, identifying thematic analysis as a primary means of surfacing patterns and meaning across documentary corpora, particularly when research aims to develop interpretive understanding rather than to verify factual claims.⁵⁰ Toward the latter, he

⁴⁷ Dvora Yanow, *How Does A Policy Mean?: Interpreting Policy and Organizational Actions* (Georgetown University Press, 1996), 21694, <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=64cc46c6-d231-3354-983b-f90766161051>; Frank Fischer, *Reframing Public Policy: Discursive Politics and Deliberative Practices* (Oxford University Press, Incorporated, 2003), <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3052456>.

⁴⁸ Robert K. Merton, *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, ed. Norman W. Storer (The University of Chicago Press, 1973); Robert K. Merton and Harriet Zuckerman, “‘Recognition’ and ‘Excellence’: Instructive Ambiguities,” in *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, ed. Norman W. Storer (The University of Chicago Press, 1973); Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science*, 111.

⁴⁹ Glenn A. Bowen, “Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method,” *Qualitative Research Journal* 9, no. 2 (2009): 33, <https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027>.

⁵⁰ Bowen, “Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method,” 32.

recommends that researchers select documents with a “critical eye and be cautious in using documents in their studies,” considering documents’ origin, author, and purpose, and including not only enough but sufficiently diverse documents as to adequately represent the discourse that is captured and communicated across the selected corpus.⁵¹ The subsequent section attends to the sources selected for this study, including relevant inclusion and exclusion criteria considered in light of shifting political, academic, and technological landscapes.

2.3 Data Sources

This study draws on a corpus of 189 documents, including scholarly publications, policy documents, advisory reports, congressional testimony, and opinion and other reform- and advocacy-oriented materials, each representing distinct arenas in which science indicators and research assessment practices were discussed and debated over time. Broadly, these documents can be classified into four broad categories: policy and governance records; reports and white papers; scholarly and technical literature; and journalistic and opinion pieces. With the exception of selected National Science Board meeting minutes, which required in-person review, all materials are publicly accessible either electronically or as bound monographs. All documents analyzed were produced contemporaneously with the periods under study.

⁵¹ Bowen, “Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method,” 33.

2.3.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed iteratively and refined over the course of the study, adapted as needed to reflect the changing nature of the ecosystem, the actors, and the discourse surrounding science indicators and research assessment over the period studied. While some criteria did shift across periods, a primary and central criterion remained firm: all documents selected for inclusion directly engaged with science indicators as tools of science policy and research assessment. The proceeding paragraphs detail the specific inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to each period.

Science Indicators Period

Inclusion decisions related to the Science Indicators period were relatively well bounded. On the policy side, the core corpus comprised the first five editions of *Science Indicators*, related National Science Board and Government Accountability Office materials, and transcripts of Congressional Hearings. These documents constitute a coherent policy discourse explicitly concerned with defining, measuring, and comparing scientific activity at the national level. Identifying scholarly resources for inclusion was similarly straightforward, as the scholarly discourse was still relatively contained to a few key scholars, events, and outlets. The corpus includes foundational contributions by Eugene Garfield, proceedings from two major conferences devoted to science indicators, the associated monograph *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, and a dedicated issue of *Scientometrics* published in 1980. A complete accounting of the documents included in this study's analysis of the Science Indicators period is provided in Appendix A.1.

Science of Science Policy Period

In selecting documents for this study's analysis of the Science of Science period, inclusion and exclusion decisions became more complex due to the proliferation of performance measurement initiatives and the expansion of bibliometric research during this period. Policy documents were included if they addressed science indicators as measures of research performance rather than administrative efficiency alone. Broader performance management initiatives such as GPRA and PART are referenced selectively as contextual precursors, but the analytic focus remains on Marburger's Science of Science Policy initiative and related efforts.

On the scholarly side, the rapid growth of bibliometric and informetric research during the SOS period necessitated selective inclusion. Rather than attempting comprehensive coverage, the analysis focused on contributions that addressed evaluative metrics as objects of debate and critique. Here, the focus was trained on documents offering an examination of how science indicators were evolving, how they were understood to function, and what their implications were for the research enterprise as a whole. There was, in general, a proliferation of bibliometric research during this period, with many studies seeking to apply bibliometric and other techniques to specific disciplinary or analytic problems for exploratory rather than evaluative purposes. These were generally excluded, as the focus of this study remains on science indicators as evaluative tools. An itemization of the documents included in this study's analysis of the Science Indicators period is provided in Appendix A.2.

Values-Driven Research Assessment Period

Inclusion criteria applied to the Values-Driven Research Assessment period expanded to reflect changes in the structure and context of the discourse. As was true across the preceding two periods, policy documents were easily identifiable – here limited to the two Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) Public Access Memos that marked the period. Outside of the policy

sphere, the landscape shifted somewhat dramatically, making way for new voices and newly aligned voices across the scholarly, infrastructure, and advocacy spheres. Indeed, it is the turn towards a marked values-driven advocacy that defines the period – a turn that is evidenced in part by the emergence of new document types and sources available for analysis. As a result, the corpus of included materials broadens in this period to include the standard policy and scholarly materials as well as reform-oriented reports, blogs, manifestos, and opinion pieces. Simultaneously, the geographic reach of the corpus also expanded. As networked and other digital technologies continued to transform the landscape of scholarly and other communications, and as international initiatives such as the Leiden Manifesto and the Paris Call on Research Assessment entered and affected the discourse, strict national delimitation was no longer analytically defensible. A full list of the documents included in this study’s analysis of the Science Indicators period is provided in Appendix A.3.

2.4 Analytic Process

The analytic process employed in this study combined qualitative coding, memoing, and interpretive writing to identify and refine thematic patterns across the corpus of selected documentary materials. Coding functioned as a heuristic device for directing attention and tracing recurring themes; interpretation, meanwhile, emerged iteratively through reflexive cycles of reading, coding, comparison, and writing. Per the design of the study, each historical period is treated as an analytic case, bounded historically but not necessarily temporally. Rather, periods – cases – are bookended either by moments or shifts in the discourse that are understood to define

them. As such shifts can be emergent in nature, so too are the advent and conclusion of some periods.

The Science Indicators period is anchored at its start by the initiation of the NSB's *Science Indicators* project and concludes around 1982 – as Reagan's first administration marked a broader shift in political priorities and policy discourse concerning federal support for science. The Science of Science period is more diffuse, emerging in the late 1990s through a rising chorus of discontent across the scholarly literature, citing multiple concerns and complains about – and observed weaknesses of – the citation-based impact metrics that were increasingly being used to assess research performance. The most defining single moment of the period comes in 2005, when John Marburger delivered the keynote address at the American Association for the Advancement of Science's annual Science and Technology Policy Forum, in which he explicitly called for a systematic, indicator-based understanding of science to inform policy – a “science of science policy”.⁵² Defined for many more years by the continued debate over the proper measurement of science, the consequences of that measurement, and the development of social and technical infrastructures to support it, the period extends until the discourse transformed into a series of explicitly normative critiques that reframed research assessment in terms of values and alignment. This transformation and related emergence of values-driven reform initiatives begins in the early 2010s. This study takes the 2012 San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment as itself an indicator of the start of the Values-Driven Research Assessment period – one that in many respects may extend through the present moment. However, as considered in the concluding chapter of this

⁵² John H. Marburger, III, “2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum Keynote Address,” 2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum, April 21, 2005, https://scisip.weebly.com/uploads/1/6/8/5/1685925/marburger_2005_aaas_keynote.pdf.

dissertation, a new period may also be emerging – one defined by explicit and punitive top-down control.

2.4.1 Coding as an Analytic Tool

Thematic coding served as a primary analytic tool leveraged in this study’s design, facilitated by NVivo qualitative data analysis software supporting the organization, retrieval, and management of documents and codes. In their writing about thematic analysis, Victoria Clark and Virginia Braun observe that, often, qualitative analysis is conflated with thematic analysis. The same appears to be true for qualitative analysis and thematic coding, as Earl Babbie observes that a “key process in the analysis of qualitative social research is coding,” a process that he defines as facilitating not only the discovery and organization of themes in one’s data but also the analysis of those themes and relevant emergent meaning surfaced throughout the act of coding.⁵³ Johnny Saldaña, author of *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Research*, extends Babbie’s argument to assert that “coding *is* analysis,” a position that he premises on the understanding that coding is an inherently an iterative process, ideally drawing upon “heuristic fluidity... to prioritize insightful qualitative analytic discovery over mere mechanistic validation.”⁵⁴

Saldaña defines a code as “word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language-based or visual data.”⁵⁵ Through iterative reading, interrogating, synthesizing, and revising, codes can help to

⁵³ Earl Babbie, *The Practice of Social Research*, 14th ed. (Cengage Learning, 2016), 387–88.

⁵⁴ Johnny Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 4th ed. (Sage, 2021), 12–13.

⁵⁵ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 5.

highlight patterns and, later, to identify broader, meaningful categories – or themes – evident in data, as identified through prolonged engagement with a qualitative data set and necessarily informed by both the researcher’s perspective and their guiding research questions.⁵⁶ The process of coding is often described as being comprised of phases or stages – Babbie frames these as proceeding from open coding, in which researchers seek to identify the highest-level and yet still central concepts, events, and sentiments across data sources; to axial coding, which seeks to surface “core” concepts that are more relevant to the unique constraints of a given project.”⁵⁷ Saldaña frames coding differently, conceiving of it as an iterative process that can include two broad cycles, the first of which attends more to code identification and the second of which offers an opportunity to synthesize codes and the insight they generate into synthesized classifications, abstractions, and – where supported by one’s research design – emergent theory.⁵⁸ In this study, the coding process was indeed iterative, relying on a sustained reflexivity that ensured emerging codes and themes were continually defined and redefined, actively engaged, and held in ongoing conversation with others across the corpus. In line with Saldaña’s framework, two broad cycles of coding were conducted, described in detail in the forthcoming section.

2.4.2 Coding Process

The computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS) NVivo was used to support the majority of the coding and classification undertaken in this dissertation. It was not

⁵⁶ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 8–13.

⁵⁷ Babbie, *The Practice of Social Research*, 388–89.

⁵⁸ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 88–89.

possible to electronically code all sources used, as some were physically bound and others were not in a format conducive to the successful application of optical character recognition. All others, however, were uploaded into NVivo and organized into “cases,” with each case corresponding to one of the three periods analyzed in this study. The study’s codes were managed in NVivo as well, as were the memos that supported and documented my analysis.

Throughout the course of this study, coding was conducted through several iterative phases rather than through a strictly linear sequence. These phases are described here procedurally, although in practice they often overlapped and informed one another.

Initial Coding

The first phase of coding involved open, exploratory engagement with the documents. This stage focused on identifying descriptive categories such as: key actors and institutions; discursive contexts; stated purposes, of both publications and events; and any other explicit claims. This phase supported familiarization with the corpus and helped establish a working map of the terrain within and across periods. Coding was broadly inductive, however familiarity with the corpus and general concerns related to the research questions did help train attention. While initial coding was intentionally inclusive, I was attuned to normative assertions, explicit critiques, and other declarations relevant to science indicators, research assessment, and the various initiatives introduced and advocated throughout the periods included in this study’s design.

Per Saldaña’s typology, the process employed during the initial phase of coding could be described as that of eclectic coding, or an application of open coding that leverages a complementary set of first-cycle coding methods undertaken “with the understanding that analytic memo writing and second cycles of recoding will synthesize the variety and number of codes into

a more unified scheme.”⁵⁹ The primary first-cycle coding methods that were used in combination during this first cycle included general initial coding – highlighting the stated purpose of documents and events, their primary contributors, and subjects – and values coding, focusing on passages communicating judgement about what *should* “count” as a valuable research output; what *ought* to be measured; what is *important, valuable, or problematic*; and whose perspectives or interests are foregrounded.⁶⁰

Axial Coding

In later stages, coding became more integrative, leveraging axial coding to synthesize first-round coding into higher-level categories capturing the normative concerns and priorities surface across the documents analyzed in this study. Saldaña categorizes axial coding as one of the common methods used in second-phase coding, however in his description of the process, he also suggests that axial coding functions as much as an effort in synthesis as it does an act of classification. Quoting his mentor Kathy Charmaz, he describes the work of axial coding as that of linking and finding connections between and across initial codes, reassembling data such that new meaning can be derived from it.⁶¹

Per Saldaña’s introduction, axial coding gets its name from the synthetic categories that form axes comprised of relevant and related codes. The axes that form the backbone of this analysis are control, quality, and value – categories that were derived through sustained inductive and reflexive analysis, and honed through multiple cycles of comparison, memoing, and analytic writing. Many of the first round of codes surfaced in the preliminary cycles of initial coding were

⁵⁹ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 223.

⁶⁰ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 152; Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 167.

⁶¹ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 308.

grouped into the three encompassing axial codes. Others were retained for context and framing but ultimately deemed less central to the study’s findings. See **Figure 1** for a schematic of the grouping and organization of axial and supporting codes developed through the course of this study's analysis. A supporting codebook is shared in Appendix B.

Figure 1: Diagram of this study’s axial categories and codes

2.4.3 Writing as Analysis

In describing coding as an iterative process, I join the tradition of many other qualitative researchers who understand that iteration to necessarily involve mutable and “rhizomatic” rounds of coding, analysis, writing, and revision.⁶² Laurel Richardson and Elizabeth Adams St. Pierre observe that “language is a constitutive force,” evoking Bowker and Star’s recognition of definition as an act of control in arguing that “[p]roducing ‘things’ always involves value – what

⁶² Laurel Richardson and Elizabeth Adams St. Pierre, “Writing: A Method of Inquiry,” in *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*, 3rd ed., ed. Norman K. Denzin and Yvonna S. Lincoln (2005), 970.

to produce, what to name the productions, and what the relationship between the producers the named things will be.”⁶³ In making decisions about what to produce, how to define the results, and how to characterize the relationships between them, I relied on a cyclical process of coding, memoing, and analytic writing to both document and generate interpretation. These cycles can be recognized as involving the creation of, specifically, code notes, theoretical memos, analytic outlines and, finally, synthetic drafts. However, in reality these cycles emerged iteratively, each informing and leading to one another in the same manner as lacing a shoe – tightening in one area requires adjusting another.

Memoing was thus critical to this study’s analytic process. Often most directly associated with grounded theory, memoing – characterized by Johnny Saldaña as “a place to ‘dump your brain’ about the participants, phenomenon, or process under investigation by thinking and thus writing and thus thinking even more about them” – is a practice that is associated with a variety of qualitative methodologies, ensuring that the evolution of meaning, definition, and analysis are captured in real time as they progress.⁶⁴ Throughout the course of this study, memoing supported and was supported by code notes that captured the meaning and scope of codes as they too evolved. An example of the interplay between the two is included in Figure 2, demonstrating the manner in which code notes tracked the scope of codes while memos served to document the decision-making and analysis that helped shape this scope.

⁶³ Richardson and St. Pierre, “Writing: A Method of Inquiry,” 960.

⁶⁴ Saldaña, *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*, 58.

Figure 2: A representation of the relationship between code notes and analytic memos
 In her contribution to a co-authored chapter with Laurel Richardson, Elizabeth Adams St.

Pierre reflects on the role that writing played in her analysis of a particular study (her original emphases retained):

I used writing as a method of data analysis by using writing to think; that is, I wrote my way into particular spaces I could not have occupied by sorting data with a computer program or by analytic induction.... I did not limit data analysis to conventional practices of coding data and then sorting it into categories that I then grouped into themes that became section headings in an outline that organized and governed my writing in advance of writing. *Thought happened in the writing.*⁶⁵

Writing served much the same analytic function in this study as St. Pierre describes of hers. Emerging reflexively from the process of coding; writing code notes; tracking insights, connections, and synthesis in memos; drafting analytic outlines; and ultimately iterating through multiple narrative drafts, I also wrote my way into the thinking that led to the surfacing of meaning and connections that became the output of my analysis.⁶⁶ While writing as analysis is a method

⁶⁵ Richardson and St. Pierre, "Writing: A Method of Inquiry," 970.

⁶⁶ Many thanks are owed to my co-advisor Dr. Alison Langmead for continually – over the course of years – training me to understand and practice writing as an analytic aid.

recognized by many qualitative scholars, it also requires diligent documentation and self-reflection, for as Laurel Richardson and Elizabeth Adams St. Pierre observe, “[n]o textual staging is ever innocent”.⁶⁷ In the course of this study, documentation was created and tracked largely via code notes and analytic memos. The meaning made must also be contextualized in light of the perspective that I, as a researcher, bring to it. This critical context is provided in the following section.

2.5 The Researcher’s Perspective

In interpretive, qualitative research, the researcher functions as the primary analytic instrument.⁶⁸ As such, a researcher’s personal and professional background, as well as their epistemological commitments, invariably informs their orientation, decision-making, and analysis throughout the research process. In this section, I will take the opportunity to document the experiences and perspectives that I carried with me into this research, and that informed my decision making as I proceeded through its various stages.

This study is grounded in an interpretive research orientation informed by scholarship in science and technology studies. Within this tradition, knowledge practices are understood as being historically situated, institutionally mediated, and shaped by social, political, and infrastructural

⁶⁷ Richardson and St. Pierre, “Writing: A Method of Inquiry,” 960.

⁶⁸ John W. Creswell and J. David Creswell, *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, 5th ed. (Sage Publications, 2018), 181.

arrangements. Insights drawn from feminist epistemology – specifically, from the work of such scholars as Susan Leigh Star and Donna Haraway – help to frame and interrogate these arrangements as inescapably reflective of certain values, assumptions, and priorities. Inspired by Donna Haraway’s position that there can be “no view from nowhere,” I approach my research and my professional work with a dedicated sensitivity to whose values are encoded where, who is affected, and in what ways.⁶⁹ In short, I am interested in how values are embedded in infrastructures, and particularly in what might be lost as this encoding is subsumed in the natural “disappearance” of infrastructure into the backgrounds of our lives.⁷⁰

The design of this study identifies documents as central conveyances across the broader infrastructures of scholarly communication and research governance. Documents serve as the primary artifacts informing this historical interpretation, and are understood as cultural artifacts as well, bearing record of the values, assumptions, and normative priorities of the various communities contributing to and affected by the negotiation of research governance that is documented by this research. My professional experience in science policy informs this perspective, providing intimate familiarity with the social and institutional contexts within which these documents circulate. My background in the field serves as both a resource and a responsibility, informing a unique sensitivity while also requiring rigorous, reflexive attention to how my position informs my interpretation.

Accordingly, this research design is premised on a foundational rejection of both positivism and relativism, setting forth from an understanding that while there are and can be discrete,

⁶⁹ Donna Haraway, “Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective,” *Feminist Studies* 14, no. 3 (1988): 581, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3178066>.

⁷⁰ Star, “The Ethnography of Infrastructure.”

knowable facts, one's access to and experience of them is necessarily partial, mediated by their experiences, worldview, and – critically for this study – prior assumptions. This research is therefore aligned with traditions of critical interpretivism, which hold that social phenomena must be understood through situated interpretation simultaneously rejecting the claim that such interpretations are arbitrary or unconstrained.⁷¹

With due deference to the central role of definition both in the history detailed herein and the recommendations that follow, this study is framed by a respect for the value of transparently defining one's terms and identifying one's positions. This is reflected in the documentation shared throughout this chapter as well as in supporting appendices. It is likewise grounded in a practice of sustained engagement with documentary evidence, historical context, and analytic coherence. The aim has been to offer historically situated interpretations that illuminate how control, quality, and value have been negotiated across the ecosystem of U.S. research and science policy over time.

⁷¹ Jason Blakely, "Returning to the Interpretive Turn: Charles Taylor and His Critics," *The Review of Politics* 75, no. 3 (2013): 383–406, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0034670513000326>; Charles Taylor, "Interpretation and the Sciences of Man," *The Review of Metaphysics* 25, no. 1 (1971): 3–51, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20125928>.

3.0 Review of the Literature

3.1 Research Assessment

Research assessment, like the practice of science itself, is intimately intertwined with the scholarly communication lifecycle. Robert K. Merton wrote on this pairing extensively, collaborating with fellow sociologist Harriet Zuckerman in an essay that explores what they observe as “Institutional Patterns of Evaluation in Science”.⁷² Their primary focus is peer review, and specifically the formal peer review that is familiar within scholarly publishing. Christine Borgman, a professor of Information Studies at UCLA, is one of many scholars who recognizes peer review’s broader scope, noting its role in citation practice and grant proposal reviews. Scientometrician Paul Wouters also notes the centrality of judgement by one’s peers throughout the literature on research assessment, arguing more directly that distinct types of research assessment cannot be so easily differentiated from one another precisely because the same communities of researchers are often the ones who are citing, peer reviewing and awarding funding to one another’s research and research proposals.⁷³ Therefore, while this section will consider peer review and evaluative bibliometrics as being distinct from one another, it is recognized that when considered at a certain level of analysis, research assessment may well be traditionally understood as “peer review all the way down”.

⁷² Merton and Zuckermann, “Institutionalized Patterns of Evaluation in Science.”

⁷³ Paul Wouters, “The Citation: From Culture to Infrastructure,” in *Beyond Bibliometrics: Harnessing Multidimensional Indicators of Scholarly Impact*, ed. Blaise Cronin and Cassidy R. Sugimoto (The MIT Press, 2014), <http://direct.mit.edu/books/book/4039/chapter/167946/Science-Metrics-and-Science-Policy>.

3.1.1 Peer Review

Throughout many discussions of scholarly communication, peer review (defined loosely here as the formal referee system that engages a body of subject experts in selecting articles for publication) is referenced as the “gold standard” of research assessment. Information scientist Christine Borgman refers to peer review as an “imprimatur” of quality, providing the stamp of legitimacy and marker of formal approval that rest at the heart of both scholarly communication and the assessment of scholarly outputs.⁷⁴ Others have referred to it as the “alpha and omega of scientific production” and the “linchpin” securing the integrity and function of the scholarly communication enterprise.⁷⁵

Consonant with its integral role in scholarly communication and research assessment, peer review is also often assigned deep historical roots, traced as far back as the mid-1700s by scholars including Nicola de Bellis. In his telling of this history, de Bellis advances a lineage that was validated by Robert K. Merton and Harriet Zuckerman in their 1971 essay “‘Recognition’ and ‘Excellence’: Instructive Ambiguities”. Per Merton and Zuckerman’s telling, that history began with Henry Oldenburg, one of two Secretaries of the Royal Society of London. Drawing on the research of historian Charles R. Weld, Merton and Zuckerman highlight a passage in the Society’s records establishing that the publication *Philosophical Transactions* was “to be composed by Mr.

⁷⁴ Christine L. Borgman, “The Discontinuity of Scholarly Publishing,” in *Scholarship in the Digital Age: Information, Infrastructure, and the Internet* (Cambridge: MIT Press, 2007), 84, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3338751>.

⁷⁵ David Pontille and Didier Torny, “From Manuscript Evaluation to Article Valuation: The Changing Technologies of Journal Peer Review,” *Human Studies* 38, no. 1 (March 2015): 3, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10746-014-9335-z>; John Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science* (Cambridge University Press, 1968), quoted in Alex Csiszar, “Peer Review: Troubled from the Start,” *Nature* 532, no. 7599 (April 2016): 308, <https://doi.org/10.1038/532306a>.

Oldenburg, be printed on the first Monday of every month... [and] licensed under the charter by the council of the Society, being first reviewed by some of the members of the same.”⁷⁶ It is instructive to note, however, that throughout their chapter Merton and Zuckerman refer to this history of institutionalized review as a “referee system” rather than as peer review. Indeed, they describe it much more capaciously than the modern concept of peer review might be understood, placing “the systematic use of judges to assess the acceptability of manuscripts submitted for publication” amid a broader tradition of reliance upon “status judges who are charged with evaluating the quality of role-performance in a social system.”⁷⁷

In recent decades, contributions to the literature have added context – if not, in some cases, direct challenges – to the previously prevailing notion of peer review’s historical roots. Science historian Alex Csiszar is among this cohort of scholars, writing in a 2016 paper that what might be understood as peer review today should not be confused with the significantly less formal referee system that was adopted by, among others, the Royal Society of London in the 1700s. “These referees,” he cautions, “were never intended to play the part of supreme scientific gatekeepers.”⁷⁸ Rather, and until about the 1930s, Csiszar explains that “editors of scientific journals made publishing decisions by personal fiat.” A larger point of his piece is that peer review has a history of transformation during active periods of change.

In a 2018 article in *Isis*, the journal supporting the History of Science Society, physicist Melinda Baldwin joins Csiszar in his challenge of peer review as a centuries-old quality control mechanism resting at the heart of the practice of science. She also attributes its rise to a moment

⁷⁶ Charles R. Weld, *A History of the Royal Society*, (London, 1848), Merton and Zuckerman, “‘Recognition’ and ‘Excellence’: Instructive Ambiguities,” 463.

⁷⁷ Merton and Zuckerman, 460.

⁷⁸ Csiszar, “Peer Review,” 306.

of great change.⁷⁹ However, she cites its rise in the United States specifically to a discrete moment in time during which the National Science Foundation faced a public challenge of its research funding decisions. She explicitly positions the defense – and indeed use – of peer review by federal grantmaking institutions as a means of protecting the autonomy of science from increasingly critical lawmakers and citizens. Her research additionally demonstrates that many of the most widely-respected scientific journals – including *Nature*, *Lancet* and the *New England Journal of Medicine* – did not adopt what would today be recognized as a formal peer-review system until well into the latter half of the 20th century.⁸⁰ Likewise, her research also underscores the distinction that it was not until at least the 1970s that the term and concept of “peer review” were widely understood to represent a mechanism safeguarding by the scientific community. “Calling external refereeing at journals or funding bodies ‘peer review’,” she explains, “established that the evaluation of a paper or grant proposal could only be done by experts—the peers of the person who submitted the work. The new term established a narrow range of acceptable reviewers and implicitly deemed those without a scientific background unqualified to evaluate the work in question.”⁸¹

This definition of peer review is consonant with contemporary understandings and usage of it, illustrating Alex Csiszar’s earlier observation that the transformation from “referee systems” to “peer review” secured the latter as “a mighty public symbol of the claim that these powerful and expensive investigators of the natural world had procedures for regulating themselves and for

⁷⁹ “Isis: About,” Isis, accessed November 7, 2022, <http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/journals/isis/about?doi=10.1086%2Fisis&publicationCode=isis>. “Isis: About,”

⁸⁰ Melinda Baldwin, “Scientific Autonomy, Public Accountability, and the Rise of ‘Peer Review’ in the Cold War United States,” *Isis* 109, no. 3 (2018): 543, <https://doi.org/10.1086/700070>.

⁸¹ Baldwin, 548.

producing consensus”.⁸² Such symbolism and power have, like many other traditional indicators of quality, trustworthiness and authority, faced a more recent sociotechnical change through the introduction of the internet and otherwise digital technologies. Indeed, just a few years into the broadening public use of and access to the internet, Craig Bingham asked explicitly in a 1998 *Lancet* article, “what is peer review on the Internet?”.⁸³ His incredulity owed to the deep ties that remained at the time between journals, peer review and, as Csiszar suggests, the semiotics of quality and veracity across scientific communities.

As has been suggested by Christine Borgman and others, peer review is understood as a signal of quality control, taken to denote that a given publication has been determined by the scholarly community to make a meaningful contribution to its discourse. Peer review is thus an intentional, strategic system of gatekeeping by peers – an effort towards establishing the consensus that John Ziman argues to be a defining characteristic of science.⁸⁴ Citation is another central means of indicating either peer approval or, at the very least, the relevance of a contribution to the scholarly discourse. Citations themselves have been referred to as “pellets of peer recognition,” and have survived decades of debate to remain recognized as among the most socially meaningful indicators of peer approval available across the scholarly ecosystem.⁸⁵ The following section on evaluative bibliometrics tracks the history of and discourse surrounding citation analysis as a mechanism of research assessment.

⁸² Csiszar, “Peer Review,” 308.

⁸³ Craig Bingham, “Peer Review on the Internet: A Better Class of Conversation,” *Lancet* 351, no. 9106 (1998): 10, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(98\)90307-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(98)90307-5).

⁸⁴ Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science*.

⁸⁵ Robert K. Merton, “The Matthew Effect in Science, II: Cumulative Advantage and the Symbolism of Intellectual Property,” *Isis* 79, no. 4 (1988): 620, <https://doi.org/10.1086/354848>.

3.1.2 Evaluative Bibliometrics

If bibliometrics is, as Nicola de Bellis has identified, “the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication”, evaluative bibliometrics can be understood as the application of such methods and tools for the purposes of assessing some entrant into the scholarly discourse.⁸⁶ The practice of applying them to citations rests at the heart of evaluative bibliometrics, having developed slowly across a variety of disciplines throughout the 1800s, and emerging as a strictly evaluative practice around the late 1970s.⁸⁷ De Bellis opens “The History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics” by outlining how philosophy and sociology laid the groundwork for treating a research paper as a proxy for the quality of the science – and the scientist – behind it. Calling into consideration contributions by Francis Bacon, Emile Durkheim and Talcott Parsons, he observes that “[b]y the turn of the 20th century, the idea that one of the highest forms of mental activity (i.e., engaging in scientific research) [might be] conveniently addressed through the tangible traces of its existence was taken for granted by scholars of diverse origins.” To connect this tracing to the practice of citation specifically, he examines the fundamental importance of a scientist’s reputation to their ability to participate in related social and (increasingly) professional circles. De Bellis credits Sir Francis Galton with helping to make explicit the presumed connection between reputation and ability, observing that insofar as “the most reliable way to identify a ‘man of science’ was ‘to take the verdict of the scientific world as expressed in definite language’, [r]eputation among peers” was a “key indicator”.⁸⁸

⁸⁶ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 23.

⁸⁷ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*.

⁸⁸ Francis Galton, *English Men of Science: Their Nature and Nurture* (Macmillan 1874), quoted in De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 28.

As late as the 1870s, the scope of the western scientific community remained small enough that it could be reasonably ascertained and quantified. It was during that time that Alphonse de Candolle and James McKeen Cattell produced indexes of scholars' peer-based reputations, but such efforts became increasingly unmanageable as the size of the scientific enterprise continued to grow.⁸⁹ The late 19th century was a period in which scientific research was becoming more professionalized and more specialized. As distinct disciplines began to crystallize, some curious scholars set forth to leverage citation analysis as a means of assessing the scope of their growing fields. A study by zoologists F.J. Cole and Nellie Eales is often credited as being among the first such analyses. Their effort was one undertaken with the goal of “apply[ing] graphic methods to an historical study... of the literature of comparative anatomy.”⁹⁰ As assessed by research analyst Francis Narin roughly six decades later, Cole and Eales' work near the turn of the 20th century represented perhaps the first “evaluative” bibliometric study, in that it was conducted to conceive of the size of a body of scientific literature.⁹¹

Francis Narin contrasts Cole and Eales' “evaluative path” with “the bibliometric path of publication and citation counts as tools for the librarian,” among the first of which is credited by both Narin and de Bellis to librarians P.L.K. and E.M. Gross.⁹² In an article published in *Science* in 1927, Gross and Gross cite the advancing professionalization of scientific disciplines as making more critical the need for academic libraries to develop collections strategically tailored to the needs of their increasingly sophisticated and specialized clientele. Asking specifically, “[w]hat

⁸⁹ De Bellis, 28.

⁹⁰ F. J. Cole and Nellie B. Eales, “The History of Comparative Anatomy: Part I.—a Statistical Analysis of the Literature,” *Science Progress (1916-1919)* 11, no. 44 (1917): 578, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43426882>.

⁹¹ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, 1.

⁹² Narin, 1; De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 28.

files of scientific periodicals are needed in a college library successfully to prepare the student for advanced work, taking into consideration also those materials necessary for the stimulation and intellectual development of the faculty,” they set out to “seek an arbitrary standard of some kind by which to measure the desirability of purchasing a particular journal.”⁹³ Citation analysis was presented as their methodology of choice, laying the groundwork for Eugene Garfield to begin working towards similar ends nearly a quarter of a century later.

Eugene Garfield was an information scientist who developed the Science Citation Index (SCI) – the first citation index to be used broadly across scientific disciplines.⁹⁴ Inspired by a citation index that had served the legal community for seventy years prior, Garfield first conceived of the Science Citation Index in the 1950s.⁹⁵ Building on work originally supported by the National Institutes of Health, Garfield and his colleagues at the Institute for Scientific Information (now Thompson Reuters) developed a method of citation analysis that enabled users to narrow the increasing number of published scientific articles to those that were most relevant to their present needs. In a 1955 article introducing the methodology, he referred to this means of analysis as “an association-of-ideas index... [dealing] in the submicro or molecular unit of thought.”⁹⁶

Following its original introduction, Garfield and his colleague Irving H. Sher continued to publish the SCI and corresponding *Journal Citation Reports* for decades, providing the broader scientific community with information intended to guide literature reviews and simultaneously nourishing the bibliometric community with the large-scale, interdisciplinary data necessary to

⁹³ P. L. K. Gross and E. M. Gross, “College Libraries and Chemical Education,” *Science* 66, no. 1713 (1927): 386, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1651803>.

⁹⁴ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 30.

⁹⁵ Garfield, “Citation Indexes for Science,” 108.

⁹⁶ Garfield, 108.

inspire and advance the nascent field.⁹⁷ Nicola de Bellis stresses the importance of this particular resource – the systematized bibliometric data provided by SCI – as being among Garfield’s most significant contributions. The growing bibliometric and broader scientific communities now had access to a methodology and a data source that they could use to generate targeted citation analyses. While these analyses were originally intended to measure the output and purported impact of journals, the proxy measurements were themselves taken to serve as indicators of the impact of a variety of units of analyses – most controversially, individual researchers.⁹⁸ Nevertheless, and as noted by de Bellis, “[t]he SCI citation data officially entered the evaluation game by inclusion in the National Science Foundation’s Science Indicators Report 1972.”⁹⁹ What had originally been designed as a bibliographic measure had thus become an evaluative tool.

Throughout its history, the use of citation analysis in research assessment has been subject to ongoing and heavy criticism, often regarding its statistical reliability. An early such critique resulted from a study conducted by MacRoberts and MacRoberts in 1989, resulting in their assessment that the “signal” of meaning derived from citation analysis can be “repetitive... weak, distorted, fragmented, incoherent, filtered, and noisy”.¹⁰⁰ Per O. Seglen further demonstrated that citation distributions tend to be field-dependent, undermining the use of aggregated indicators as valid proxies for research quality.¹⁰¹ In addition to these more methodological concerns, a second line of critique concerns the behavioral and social dynamics that citation metrics both reflect and

⁹⁷ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 30.

⁹⁸ Henk F. Moed, *Appropriate Use of Metrics in Research Assessment of Autonomous Academic Institutions*, no. 1, 2, no. 1 (2020): 4, 1, <https://doi.org/10.29024/sar.8>.

⁹⁹ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 32.

¹⁰⁰ Michael H. MacRoberts and Barbara R. MacRoberts, “Problems of Citation Analysis: A Critical Review,” *Journal of the American Society for Information Science* 40, no. 5 (1989): 347, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4571\(198909\)40:5%253C342::AID-ASI7%253E3.0.CO;2-U](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(198909)40:5%253C342::AID-ASI7%253E3.0.CO;2-U).

¹⁰¹ Per O. Seglen, “Why the Impact Factor of Journals Should Not Be Used for Evaluating Research,” *BMJ: British Medical Journal* 314, no. 7079 (1997): 499, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25173791>.

induce. Sue Cozzens' scholarship, for instance, has demonstrated that citations often arise from social networks, visibility effects, and reward structures rather than from intellectual lineage alone, complicating popular understanding about what citation might indicate.¹⁰²

A third line of critique thus focuses on the loss of interpretive nuance that can occur when citation counts are treated as simplified, context-free indicators. Cronin's early work on the rhetorical functions of citations demonstrated that a single citation can serve multiple purposes – from acknowledgment, to persuasion, framing, and even criticism – none of which can be inferred from the count alone.¹⁰³ Building on this perspective, Leydesdorff and his co-authors argue in a 2016 article that what citations “mean” depends not only on how they are framed but also – and importantly – on who is “reading” them.¹⁰⁴ Paul Wouters, a contributor to that article and contemporary of Leydesdorff's, later likened scholar's contextualized readings of citation analysis to folk theory, making a 1987 quote by George Lakoff all the more compelling: “It is easier to show what is wrong with a scientific theory than with a folk theory. A folk theory defines common sense itself. When the folk theory and the technical theory converge, it gets even tougher to see where that theory gets in the way – or even that it is a theory at all.”¹⁰⁵ Indeed, what these critiques together afford is the central insight that the more such analyses are removed from their originating context, the less meaningfully they can indicate anything.

¹⁰² Susan E. Cozzens, “What Do Citations Count? The Rhetoric-First Model,” *Scientometrics* 15, no. 5 (1989): 437–47, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02017064>; Susan E. Cozzens, “The Knowledge Pool: Measurement Challenges in Evaluating Fundamental Research Programs,” *Evaluation and Program Planning* 20, no. 1 (1997): 77–89, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-7189\(96\)00038-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-7189(96)00038-9).

¹⁰³ Blaise Cronin, *The Citation Process: The Role and Significance of Citations in Scientific Communication* (Taylor Graham, 1984), 46–47, <http://garfield.library.upenn.edu/cronin/citationprocess.pdf>.

¹⁰⁴ Loet Leydesdorff et al., “Professional and Citizen Bibliometrics: Complementarities and Ambivalences in the Development and Use of Indicators—a State-of-the-Art Report,” *Scientometrics* 109, no. 3 (2016): 2129–50, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2150-8>.

¹⁰⁵ Wouters, “The Citation: From Culture to Infrastructure,” 56; George Lakoff, *Women, Fire, and Dangerous Things: What Categories Reveal about the Mind* (University of Chicago Press, 1987), 121.

3.2 Control

Control is a critical and dominant theme across the literature on both research assessment and science indicators – one that is equally integral to efforts to describe the relationship between science and the state. In the United States, the early twentieth century was a period in which science was presented as an essential contributor to social progress. During the late 19th century, and prior to its U.S. institutionalization, science was becoming increasingly standardized, maturing from a distributed network of tinkerers into a more coherent community of professional practitioners. Simultaneously, its outputs were becoming more (and more immediately) relevant to the concerns of the general populace.¹⁰⁶ Sociologist Michael J. Mulkey highlights the co-incidence of this more general trend with the start of the first World War, noting that while during the war, many scientists lent their skills and time to the wartime as an act of patriotism, an additional motivating force was at work: some saw it as an opportunity to advance the argument for federally funded research.¹⁰⁷ Drawing on the work of historian Ronald C. Tobey, Mulkey illustrates a moment in history when a group of scientists “banded together to sell science, not only to government but also to the American public.”¹⁰⁸

This sales pitch was premised on a number of soaring ideals, including the purported self-evident nature of the fact of science as, first, a social good and, second, a social good that is intrinsically to American values and progress. Mulkey describes this relationship in helpful detail:

In trying to show the importance of science to American culture, great emphasis was placed on what were claimed to be the values of science. These values were

¹⁰⁶ Michael J. Mulkey, “Norms and Ideology in Science,” *Social Science Information* 15, no. 4–5 (August 1, 1976): 640, <https://doi.org/10.1177/053901847601500406>.

¹⁰⁷ Mulkey, 650.

¹⁰⁸ Mulkey, 651.

said to be derived from the nature of scientific knowledge and, although they were realised most fully in the scientific community, they were portrayed as being the fundamental values of American society. The main objective in explaining science to the lay public was to establish that science was the source of national progress. This required the concept of inevitable progress in science.¹⁰⁹

It also required a shared social understanding of the “man of science” as also being a “man of conscience”. In a book exploring the ideological roots of American “national science,” historian Ronald C. Tobey positions Robert Millikan – a physicist working in the early decades of the 20th century – as an energetic advocate who intentionally pitched the image of science as a pursuit towards the social good.¹¹⁰ Specifically, Tobey recounts that “[a]ccording to Millikan, [scientists’] fundamental virtues sprang out of the manner in which a scientist approached nature to obtain knowledge. The successful use of the scientific method required true humility: the scientist who was arrogant would miss the discovery.” A supporting observation by Mulkay holds that this valorization was in line with a broader ideology emerging from the same point in history – one in which it was argued and increasingly accepted to be the case that “society should support, but not govern, science; that... scientists must have complete independence... and that the internal value system of science guarantees an ethical standard which requires no outside surveillance.”¹¹¹

Mulkay draws on the historical research of Daniels and Greenberg to make the argument that a depiction of science and scientists was intentionally crafted by a group of dedicated activists, one that emerged from a scientific community that was fast-growing, increasingly professionalized, taking on larger and more complex challenges and, as a result, becoming more dependent on federal funding. Scientists at the time, he observes, “were determined to resist

¹⁰⁹ Mulkay, 651.

¹¹⁰ Robert C. Tobey, “Ideology: Social Values,” in *The American Ideology of National Science 1919 -1930* (Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press, 1971), 179.

¹¹¹ Mulkay, “Norms and Ideology in Science,” 649.

government control of academic or ‘pure’ science... [and] strove vigorously” to secure that support while protecting their autonomy.¹¹² To do this, he argues, they worked as carefully as they did purposefully in crafting a vision of science as a pursuit towards a unique type of “knowledge [that] is established in accordance with impersonal and universal criteria of adequacy.”¹¹³ The argument then followed naturally that only trained scientists understood the criteria required to ensure empirical adequacy – those who were untrained in such arts were therefore obviously unfit to judge the practice, process and results of science.

If efforts to secure long term mechanisms for the governmental support of science were advanced by U.S. involvement in World War I, they were effectively guaranteed by its subsequent involvement in World War II. Through the sequential establishment of the National Defense Research Committee in 1940 and the Office of Scientific Research and Development in 1941, the federal government recruited scientists to collaborate on the broad-scale efforts needed to advance the medical, military and other research that would ensure the country’s ultimate dominance in the war. Eminent engineer Vannevar Bush was selected to head both of these entities and after the war was invited by President Franklin Delano Roosevelt to propose an ongoing model for federal support of scientific research.¹¹⁴ Bush’s response came in the form of a report entitled *Science – The Endless Frontier*, in which he called upon prior decades’ valorization of science and “men of science” to establish a case for federal investment in basic research.¹¹⁵ It is from this report that

¹¹² Mulkay, 649.

¹¹³ Mulkay, 649.

¹¹⁴ Emily K. Gibson, “Overseeing Innovation,” *Science* 369, no. 6501 (July 17, 2020): 258, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb4913>.

¹¹⁵ Vannevar Bush, “Science - The Endless Frontier” (Washington, D.C.: United States Government Printing Office, 1945), <https://www.nsf.gov/od/lpa/nsf50/vbush1945.htm#ch5>.

the National Science Foundation (NSF) emerged, formally established by Congress with the National Science Foundation Act of 1950.¹¹⁶

A guiding premise of *Science – The Endless Frontier* is Bush’s staunch prioritization of basic research. In the third annual report of the National Science Foundation, issued in 1953, its authors illustrate basic research in heroic terms:

A worker in basic scientific research is motivated by a driving curiosity about the unknown. When his explorations yield new knowledge, he experiences the satisfaction of those who first attain the summit of a mountain.... Discovery of truth and understanding of nature are his objectives. His professional standing among his fellows depends upon the originality and soundness of his work.¹¹⁷

Discovery, achieved through a pursuit characterized by unbounded – and unfettered – curiosity indeed rested at the heart of the basic research advanced and similarly illustrated by Bush in *Science – the Endless Frontier*. Crucially for present purposes, Bush advanced basic research as a national imperative founded on shared national values, undertaken “without thought of practical ends” and advanced by a “freedom of inquiry” enjoyed by professionals of unique and specialized training that was necessarily beyond the purview of the federal government. As such, Bush exhorted the federal government to “proceed with caution” and respect as it made the transition from funding immediately necessary wartime research to establishing a system of federal patronage of basic research.¹¹⁸

Federal research investments increased dramatically throughout the late 1940s and early 1950s, as – particularly in the 1950s – Cold War concerns including the “space race” and Sputnik

¹¹⁶ National Science Foundation, “A Timeline of NSF History - 1940s and 1950s,” National Science Foundation, accessed November 5, 2022, <https://www.nsf.gov/about/history/overview-50.jsp>.

¹¹⁷ National Science Foundation, “The Third Annual Report of the National Science Foundation” (Washington DC: National Science Foundation, 1953), 38, <https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/1953/annualreports/start.htm>.

¹¹⁸ Bush, “Science - The Endless Frontier.”

affair helped to justify research expenditures.¹¹⁹ This period of expansion came to a relatively quick end, however. Melinda Baldwin cites the early 1960s and subsequent Department of Defense Hindsight Report as perhaps the first high-level inquiry into federal research spending, explaining “that while applied research had yielded massive benefits in the form of new military technologies... [t]he report led many policy makers to question military and government expenditures on basic research.”¹²⁰ Baldwin and other chroniclers of midcentury federal funding initiatives center the 1970s as a period of intensifying scrutiny and budget cuts, as Cold War anxieties subsided, the economy began to sour and increased criticisms of the Vietnam War and related research investments tempered the optimism and expansion of decades prior.¹²¹

It was in this environment that the effort to assess the “health” of science via institutionalized indicators arose.¹²² Historian Benoît Godin explores the history of state-funded S&T measurement in *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, attributing its midcentury rise to two factors: first, the increasing investment of state funds into research and development efforts, particularly following the second world war; and, second, the simultaneous and enabling rise of scientometric and bibliometric indicators being developed and discussed by the likes of economist Joseph Schmookler and physicist-turned-historian-of-science Derek de Solla Price.¹²³ Godin takes the position that such indicators do not qualify as traditional

¹¹⁹ Baldwin, “Scientific Autonomy, Public Accountability, and the Rise of ‘Peer Review’ in the Cold War United States,” 548; De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 31.

¹²⁰ Baldwin, “Scientific Autonomy, Public Accountability, and the Rise of ‘Peer Review’ in the Cold War United States,” 548–49.

¹²¹ Baldwin, 550–51; Irwin Feller, “This Time It Really May Be Different,” in *The University Under Pressure*, ed. Michael Lounsbury, Elizabeth Popp Berman, and Catherine Paradeise (Bingley, UK: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2016), 453, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=4509354>.

¹²² An Act to Amend the National Science Foundation Act of 1950 to Make Changes and Improvements in the Organization and Operation of the Foundation, and for Other Purposes, 362.

¹²³ Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, 2.

social statistics because the original intent of their implementation was not one of control. Michel Foucault and Ian Hacking have each contributed to the now widely held understanding of social statistics as means of social control, the former by introducing the concept of biopower and illustrating its expression through technologies of control and accounting, and the latter by applying Foucault's analysis to a history of public health interventions in 1800s Europe.¹²⁴ Godin draws on Hacking's work in particular to establish science indicators as a foil to such efforts, arguing that the "purpose of the first science policies and their statistics was to fund, without much intervention, ever more research hoping that this served the economy."¹²⁵ He attributes the creation of these statistics to the demand of economists for "perfect information – generally quantitative – to assist in rational decision making."¹²⁶

Interestingly, while Godin holds firm in his assessment that at least the initial attempts at gathering indicators of the health of science were not efforts at control, he does acknowledge quickly and readily that the statistics collected by state offices, both in the U.S. and in Europe, were by design reflective of the purposes they were gathered to advance. "This book suggests that official statistics reflect already-held views, rather than offering information for choosing among alternatives.... This is why statistics are used and 'useful,' despite considerable limitations: they help construct discourses on how we want things to be. Between statistics and action, then, there

¹²⁴ Michel Foucault, *Security, Territory, Population: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1977-78*, with Michel Senellart et al. (Palgrave Macmillan, 2007); Ian Hacking, "Biopower and the Avalance of Numbers," in *Biopower: Foucault and Beyond*, ed. Vernon W. Cisney and Nicolae Morar (University of Chicago Press, 2015), <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/pitt-ebooks/detail.action?docID=5892735>.

¹²⁵ Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, 3.

¹²⁶ Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, 5.

is discourse: statistics are a rhetorical resource used to convince for a course of action already selected.”¹²⁷

In Godin’s view, the purpose of science indicators was not to control the conduct or output of science, but instead to justify federal investments by the most defensible and scientific means possible – by using what were seen as “perfect” numbers that could be deployed in rendering policy decisions “rational”. Per his position, science indicators were intended to offer purportedly objective justification for the research expenditures made across Europe and the United States in the second half of the 20th century. His research traces the history of the development of science indicators across these two regions, beginning in a formal sense with the publication of *The Measurement of Scientific and Technical Activities: Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys of Research and Development*, a report known more succinctly as “the Frascati Manual”. Published by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 1963 and colloquially named after the Italian town where it was first drafted, the Frascati Manual has been recognized as a foundational international standard for establishing comparable, policy-relevant statistics on state-supported research and development (R&D) activities.¹²⁸ The stated goals were to make a case for the standardized collection of state-sponsored R&D statistics – particularly those that would advance international comparisons – and to encourage those countries that had not yet begun regimes of R&D assessment to do so (“Most countries still devote far more attention to the measurement of the number of chickens they possess, their rate of lay and the price of eggs,

¹²⁷ Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, 6.

¹²⁸ OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys of Research and Development* (OECD Publishing, 1963), https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/frascati-manual-1963_a9f6ca4b-en.html; Benoît Godin, “The Numbers Makers: Fifty Years of Science and Technology Official Statistics,” *Minerva* 40, no. 4 (2002): 376, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41821220>.

than they do to the measurement of the number of research scientists and technicians, their output and their cost.”).¹²⁹

Notably, and as Godin points out, OECD originally failed to define research or development, characterizing “R&D” largely by what, they argued, it was not: “The guiding line to distinguish R&D activity from non-research activity is the presence or absence of an element of novelty or innovation. Insofar as the activity follows an established routine pattern it is not R&D. Insofar as it departs from routine and breaks new ground, it qualifies as R&D.”¹³⁰ Activities that were research-adjacent but that failed to fit OECD’s qualifying criteria for R&D were classified as “research support activities,” or RSA.¹³¹ This classification itself contained four further categories – those of “scientific information,” training and education, data collection, and testing and standardization.¹³² Into the first of these was lumped publication and various other forms of “communication among scientists, including such activities as the publication, dissemination, and translation of information resulting from research and development.”¹³³

In *Sorting Things Out*, Susan Leigh Star and Geoffrey Bowker argue that the act of categorizing carries with it some risk. “Each standard and each category valorizes some point of view and silences another. This is not inherently a bad thing.... [but] it *is* an ethical choice, and as such it is dangerous – not bad, but dangerous.”¹³⁴ The exclusion of publications from the OECD’s categorization of “research” illustrates this danger. Nearly every consequential, large-scale research assessment regime – including that of the National Science Foundation’s *Science*

¹²⁹ OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys*, 5.

¹³⁰ OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys*, 16.

¹³¹ OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys*, 16.

¹³² OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys*, 15.

¹³³ OECD, *Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys*, 15.

¹³⁴ Bowker and Star, *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences*, 5–6.

Indicators effort, which Benoît Godin argued was at least in part inspired by the Frascati Manual – is premised to some degree on a recognition of the central role that scholarly communication plays in demonstrating research “quality” or “value”, but also in circulating and upholding the values that might be used to assess the health of a given scientific enterprise.¹³⁵

John Ziman argues that science is in fact typified – indicated – by the generation and public dissemination of findings.¹³⁶ The relationship between scholarly communication and what Robert Merton and Harriet Zuckerman referred to as “the Normative Structure of Science” is discussed in greater detail in the “Quality” section of this chapter. Here, the matter is raised as an example of what Geoffrey Bowker, Susan Leigh Star, and Lucy Suchman might describe as control via categorization. Suchman argues in a now-canonical article published before the turn of the century that the “inscription of formal representations of action in technical systems” can shed instructive light onto “how our relations to each other are ordered and by whom.”¹³⁷ The intertwined histories of science indicators and research assessment that are traced in this dissertation will demonstrate that excluding broad swaths of research outputs from the pool of materials “rewarded” through mechanisms of research assessment is indeed a political issue, at the heart of which rests the question about who has the authority – who has the control – to define what science is and which of its products are markers of quality or value.

¹³⁵ Godin, “The Numbers Makers: Fifty Years of Science and Technology Official Statistics.”

¹³⁶ Ziman, *Public Knowledge: An Essay Concerning the Social Dimension of Science*, 111.

¹³⁷ Suchman, “Do Categories Have Politics? The Language/Action Perspective Reconsidered,” 188.

3.3 Quality

To assess the correspondence between evaluative bibliometrics and what might be recognized as “scientific values,” it is necessary to first identify the framework from which one might identify the values of science. “Science,” as an effort towards the discovery of facts, truth and the communication thereof has traditionally and is still regularly idealized as a pursuit towards objectivity, premised on an assumption or expectation that there might be one objectively knowable truth that can be revealed and understood incrementally. Throughout the late 20th and early decades of the current century, this notion has been vigorously challenged – particularly so by feminist philosophers who argue that there can be no “view from nowhere.” Often attributed to philosopher Thomas Nagel, this phrase refers to the expectation that objective truths can be, first, identified and, second, communicated without any residual value inflection accumulated from or deposited by contextual circumstances.¹³⁸ Donna Haraway is a feminist philosopher widely recognized for her dismantling of the notion of a “view from nowhere”. In a 1988 contribution to the discourse, she comments sharply that “[v]ision can be good for avoiding binary oppositions,” and suggests that it is the precisely the range of vision provided to those who exist outside of power structures that affords the vantage necessary to see the fallacy of objectivity.¹³⁹

¹³⁸ Steven Shapin, “Placing the View from Nowhere: Historical and Sociological Problems in the Location of Science,” *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers* 23, no. 1 (1998): 9, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/623153>.

¹³⁹ Donna Haraway, “Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective,” *Feminist Studies* 14, no. 3 (1988): 581, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3178066>.

Janet Kourany helps to advance and operationalize Haraway's critique by naming the issue – that of the “value-free ideal” of science.¹⁴⁰ She leverages the work of feminist scholars to dispatch with the notion of value-free science by using their work to, first, reveal the heavy value inflection of traditional misogynist perspectives operating in the pursuit of science and, second, demonstrate on their own merits the ways that values inform and direct the work of feminist philosophers.¹⁴¹ One such philosopher is Helen Longino, who in a contribution to the 1990 book *Science As Social Knowledge: Values and Objectivity in Scientific Inquiry*, Longino declares the “value-freedom” of science to be “nonsense”.¹⁴² To the contrary of such supposed objectivity, Longino argues that the pursuit of science is in fact affected by values and value systems both implicitly and explicitly, distinguishing between the two as the “constitutive” and “contextual” values of science.¹⁴³ The constitutive values of science, per her classification, are those that are “generated from an understanding of the goals of science,” and those that “are the source of the rules determining what constitutes acceptable scientific practice or... method.”

The contextual values of science, on the other hand, are according to Longino those that define what is appropriate within and to the environment in which science is conducted. This environment can be defined by individuals as well as by, for instance, disciplines and broader cultural determinants and are those that prescribe what “ought” to be. They are therefore normative structures of the type commonly attributed to Robert K. Merton. Merton was a mid-century

¹⁴⁰ Janet A. Kourany, “Replacing the Ideal of Value-Free Science,” in *The Challenge of the Social and the Pressure of Practice: Science and Values Revisited*, ed. Martin Carrier et al. (University of Pittsburgh Press, 2008), 87, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt9qh7nh>.

¹⁴¹ Kourany, “Replacing the Ideal of Value-Free Science,” 88–89.

¹⁴² Helen E. Longino, “Introduction: Good Science, Bad Science,” in *Science as Social Knowledge: Values and Objectivity in Scientific Inquiry* (Princeton University Press, 1990), 4, <https://web-p-ebsochost-com.pitt.idm.oclc.org/ehost/ebookviewer/ebook?sid=f0d22150-8f05-43c1-85fe-24ffed1c9a06%40redis&vid=0&format=EB>.

¹⁴³ Longino, “Introduction: Good Science, Bad Science,” 4.

sociologist who wrote extensively on the sociology of science. His most well-known contribution to related scholarship is his itemization and definition of what have since become known eponymously as “the Mertonian norms”. Merton situated these norms within what he observed to be “the ethos of science,” or “that affectively toned complex of values and norms which is held to be binding on the [person] of science.” They are, he continued, “legitimized in terms of institutional values” that are communicated by entities across the practice of science and coalesce, ultimately, in a “scientific conscience”.¹⁴⁴

The Mertonian norms are sometimes referenced by their acronym – CUDOS – and are comprised of communism, universalism, disinterestedness and organized skepticism. “Communism”, in the parlance of the mid-1930s, is used in reference to the ideal that all scientific output – the discoveries, knowledge and the formal communication thereof – might be freely accessed and shared by all members of the scientific community, towards the ends of verification, replicability and continued exploration. It is helpfully referred to by many modern scholars as “communalism,” and has been observed by John Ziman to be typified by the scholarly communication system.¹⁴⁵ Universalism suggests not necessarily that the output of scientific activity be universally true but more specifically that, first, “truth-claims” must be “subjected to *preestablished impersonal criteria*” and, second, that demographic qualities such as “race, nationality, religion [and] class... are irrelevant” in the pursuit of such efforts towards truth. “The chauvinist may expunge the names of alien scientists from historical textbooks,” Merton explains

¹⁴⁴ Merton, *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, 268–69.

¹⁴⁵ John Ziman, “‘Post-Academic Science’: Constructing Knowledge with Networks and Norms,” *Science & Technology Studies* 9, no. 1 (1996): 68, <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.55095>.

in language indicative of the time, “but their formulations remain indispensable to science and technology.”¹⁴⁶

Of a piece with the norm of universalism is that of disinterestedness, which stipulates that a person of science must pursue research without personal investment – of any sort – in the outcome. The Mertonian norms have fallen into disfavor in recent decades; of the lot, the prescription of disinterestedness is arguably the one that fared the worst no matter the era. In contrast here is the final norm of organized skepticism, which Merton describes as extending throughout the institution of science, edifying the pursuit with “the temporary suspension of judgement and... detached scrutiny of beliefs” that enable “truth” to emerge from a social system acknowledged to house numerous “empirical and logical criteria.”¹⁴⁷ Many scholars and researchers have acknowledged this final norm as describing – at the very least – an ideal that is reflected throughout much of the practice of science. In reflecting on organized skepticism, Ziman identifies it as the “normative basis for many academic practices,” not the least of which includes peer review and which, in sum, have the effect of “stress[ing] the constructive role of refutation as the natural partner of conjecture in the production of reliable knowledge.”¹⁴⁸

As mentioned, Merton’s norms have met with considerable criticism over time. Resulting from this criticism has been the occasional contribution of counter-norms to the literature, including the 1974 offering of Ian K. Mitroff’s norm/counter-norm proposal. Following the Apollo lunar missions of the late 1960s and early 1970s, Mitroff engaged a group of Apollo scientists in a longitudinal study of the values that inspired their work. Mitroff described his sample of

¹⁴⁶ Merton, *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, 270.

¹⁴⁷ Merton, *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, 277.

¹⁴⁸ Ziman, “Post-Academic Science,” 68.

participants as “forty-two of the most eminent” scientists involved in the missions, having intentionally selected them on the presumption that their eminence was an indicator of not only their expertise but also of their knowledge – perhaps even mastery – of the mores of their field. Through a series of interviews spanning years, Mitroff amassed the body of evidence that he then analyzed in effort to determine the scientists’ values.

The results were not wholly kind to Merton’s proposed norms, coming down predictably hard on the norm of disinterestedness. One participant was quoted as reporting that no scientist he knew “believed in that simple-minded nonsense.”¹⁴⁹ Another provided an indelible illustration of the same: “X is so committed to the idea that the moon is Q that you could literally take the moon apart piece by piece, ship it back to Earth, reassemble it in X's backyard and shove the whole thing... and X would still continue to believe that the moon is Q.”¹⁵⁰ Debunking the myth of the disinterested scientist is not so much Mitroff’s goal as is, first, adding to the conversation necessary nuance about how truths are agreed upon by admittedly invested researchers and, second, using this nuance to recommend acknowledgement of the counter-norms he argues to be already extant and indeed essential to maintaining balance across the system. The point of a norm/counter-norm allowance, Mitroff argues, is that each should be “restrained... [I]f any were unrestrained, science would probably collapse.”¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁹ Apollo Mission scientist quoted in Ian I. Mitroff, “Norms and Counter-Norms in a Select Group of the Apollo Moon Scientists: A Case Study of the Ambivalence of Scientists,” *American Sociological Review* 39, no. 4 (1974): 88, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2094423>.

¹⁵⁰ Scientist quoted in Mitroff, “Norms and Counter-Norms in a Select Group of the Apollo Moon Scientists,” 586.

¹⁵¹ Mitroff, “Norms and Counter-Norms in a Select Group of the Apollo Moon Scientists,” 593.

Mitroff's recommended counter-norms included – in an order respective of their obverse in Merton's accounting – solitariness, particularism, interestedness and organized dogmatism.¹⁵² These accord well with similar recommended counter-norms suggested by researchers Bruce Macfarlane and Ming Cheng, who in 2008 published the results of a survey completed in effort to understand the relevance of three Mertonian norms – communalism, universalism and disinterestedness – to the work of contemporary scholars. Their analysis also demonstrated significant ambivalence with respect to disinterestedness and, overall, revealed that the relevance of the norms depended on the perspective of the person making the assessment. As might be expected, Macfarlane and Cheng's findings found that adherence to Merton's norms depended specifically on how much risk was involved and who was doing the risk-taking. Full professors, for instance, emerged as the group most likely to openly demonstrate interestedness and take ideological positions based on personal opinion. Meanwhile, female academics were observed as being more likely to align their research agendas with the priorities of their funders.¹⁵³

John Ziman also recommends a set of counter-norms but does so from a different perspective as Mitroff or Macfarlane and Cheng. He takes the position that, given transformative change that swept across higher education and the research landscape throughout the 1970s, 80s and 90s, Merton's norms can simply not be universally applied. He premises his work on that of Michael Gibbons, Camille Limoges, Helga Nowotny, Simon Schwartzman, Peter Scott, and Martin Trow and their proposition that science as a whole has experienced a break between “Mode 1”, or the traditional “academic science” idealized by Merton's writing, and “Mode 2”, a new

¹⁵² Mitroff, “Norms and Counter-Norms in a Select Group of the Apollo Moon Scientists,” 592.

¹⁵³ Bruce Macfarlane and Ming Cheng, “Communism, Universalism and Disinterestedness: Re-Examining Contemporary Support among Academics for Merton's Scientific Norms,” *Journal of Academic Ethics* 6, no. 1 (2008): 74–75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-008-9055-y>.

manifestation typified by decentralization (of research efforts as well as communication) and postindustrial, postmodern means of knowledge production.¹⁵⁴ Observing the centrality of reputation and prestige to academic science, Ziman remarks that the Mertonian acronym of “CUDOS” (or, “kudos”) is nicely fitting. His proposed counter-norms – proprietary, local, authoritarian, commissioned and expert – form a similarly appropriate acronym (“PLACE”), given the heavily context-dependent nature of their relevance: one of Ziman’s guiding arguments is that in Mode 2 science, normative structures are less institutionalized and instead are embodied momentarily by decentralized groups of researchers and technicians working together not to advance knowledge so much as to solve specific problems more commonly defined by their funders, employers and sponsors.¹⁵⁵

3.4 Value

In a 1973 study, R.H. Orr set forth to “measure the goodness” of academic library services. With this rather winsome turn of phrase, he aimed to reference something quite complicated – that which might generate from a contribution to the research process. In an attempt to distill the conceptual challenge into more concrete terms, he discerns that, in such a context, the notion of “goodness’... seems to have two basic aspects, which are reflected in the simple questions—'How good is the service?' and 'How much good does it do? For want of better labels, the first aspect

¹⁵⁴ Ziman, “Post-Academic Science,” 70.

¹⁵⁵ Ziman, “Post-Academic Science,” 76.

may be called quality, and the second, value.”¹⁵⁶ What “good” science does and how it might be identified are two questions that rest at the heart of historical efforts to determine the “value” of science.

An econometric tradition of scholars seeking to understand the value of science via estimations of its economic contribution is typified by the work of economist Zvi Griliches, whose work provided much of the supportive methodological framework underlying this type of inquiry. One of Griliches’ most critical contributions was the notion of – and methodologies to support – measuring for productivity as a means of quantifying returns on investment. Pioneered early on via a study highlighting the importance of modeling for incentives and other often overlooked managerial influences, his scholarship over many decades continued to stress the importance of accounting for the intangibility of many inputs into research and development lifecycles.¹⁵⁷

Edwin Mansfield, an economist and contemporary of Griliches, extended this econometric inquiry by testing whether basic research, as distinct from applied R&D, contributed to productivity growth in U.S. manufacturing. By comparing industries’ basic research expenditures with gains in their long-term productivity, Mansfield identified a statistically significant – although admittedly “tentative” – relationship between the two, offering a model for estimating the value of research in terms of productivity.¹⁵⁸ He was careful, however, to note that the distinction between basic and applied research is often “nebulous” and that “[i]n other words, basic research may be a proxy for long-term R&D,” highlighting the difficulty of isolating the mechanisms by which

¹⁵⁶ Orr, “Measuring the Goodness,” 317.

¹⁵⁷ Barry Bozeman and Daniel Sarewitz, “Public Value Mapping and Science Policy Evaluation,” *Minerva* 49, no. 1 (2011): 5, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-011-9161-7>.

¹⁵⁸ Edwin Mansfield, “Basic Research and Productivity Increase in Manufacturing.,” *American Economic Review* 70, no. 5 (1980): 872, 4503746, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1805767>.

research investments translate into economic outcomes.¹⁵⁹ Mansfield’s caution that measurable relationships may mask more cumulative and institutionally embedded processes anticipates the concerns raised by Nathan Rosenberg, another scholar working during the same period, whose historical analysis of technological change argues that innovation cannot be reduced to discrete inputs and outputs but instead must be more thoroughly understood as interdependent, path-dependent, and contingent upon complementary developments across time.

As a historian of technology in particular, Nathan Rosenberg focused on the processes underlying and embedded within innovation. In the late 70s and early 80s, Rosenberg argued specifically against simplistic understandings of inputs into and outputs emerging from technological production. His scholarship emphasizes instead the cumulative, iterative, and path-dependent nature of innovation as one that is additionally dependent on expertise, the vicissitudes of institutional structure, and the constraints of historical contingencies. “Inventions hardly ever function in isolation. Time and again in the history of American technology, it has happened that the productivity of a given invention has turned on the question of the availability of complementary technologies. Often these technologies did not initially exist, so that the benefits potentially flowing from invention A had to await the achievement of inventions B, C, or D.”¹⁶⁰ Referring to these as “relationships of complementarity,” Rosenberg situates the benefits emerging from these clusters of technology as a question of social value. “A serious difficulty in tracing out the social payoff to invention,” he warns “is that these linkages are both numerous and of varying degrees of importance and therefore difficult to measure with any pretense of precision.”¹⁶¹

¹⁵⁹ Mansfield, “Basic Research and Productivity Increase in Manufacturing.,” 866.

¹⁶⁰ Nathan Rosenberg, *Inside the Black Box* (Cambridge University Press, 1982), 56–57, 53623, <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=48bca32c-7265-3913-b393-9a3cb1840d04>.

¹⁶¹ Rosenberg, *Inside the Black Box*, 57.

Returning to Orr’s distinction between “the goodness” of a product and how much good it does, one can situate the literature reviewed here as representing cyclical and still quite active conversations about how quality and value might be identified by different audiences and for different purposes. Across academic circles, quality is most often operationalized through peer judgement, whether that judgement is formalized through peer review, normalized through disciplinary standards, or stabilized by the multiple processes that can result in consensus. Evaluative bibliometrics extends and gives shape to that logic by packaging traces of recognition – via citation – into portable measures that enable some means of standardization and comparison, however potentially sacrificing context and interpretive nuance along the way.

The literature on value further complicates this picture by foregrounding what Orr frames as the second question: not whether science is “good” in disciplinary terms, but what good it does in the world. The econometric tradition explored by Griliches and Mansfield reflects a long-running desire to treat science as an input into productivity and growth, even as its central problem remains the intangibility and non-market character of many research outputs. As a whole, the body of scholarship considered in this review of the literature on science indicators and research assessment helps contextualize the decades-long debates surrounding each. Research assessment, whether qualitative or quantitative in nature, is itself constitutive, defining what counts, what is rewarded, what is recognized as valuable, and who has the authority to decide.

4.0 Science Indicators

4.1 Introduction

In 1968, Congress amended the National Science Foundation Act to include a new directive requiring the National Science Board (NSB) to provide annual reports to the President detailing the “status and health of science” in the United States.¹⁶² While the mandate itself was clear, its path to realization was not. Indeed, among the primary questions guiding an NSB committee convened to inform the development of these new mandates reports was one asking directly, “How do we define and measure the state of health of U.S. science?”¹⁶³ At the time, no consensus existed as to what constituted a healthy research enterprise, nor how such an ideal might be evaluated (another question asked by the committee asked “is identification of U.S. science priorities possible?”).¹⁶⁴ The NSF and NSB were thus faced with a conceptual challenge: to transform the abstract notion of “scientific health” into a set of measurable indicators suitable for federal reporting and policy planning. The solution they developed – first published in 1972 under the title *Science Indicators* – arrived in the form of a biannual series that inaugurated a new era in research assessment.

The first few editions of these reports were designed via closed-door Executive Sessions of the National Science Board, as part of an internal deliberative process that excluded external

¹⁶² An Act to Amend the National Science Foundation Act of 1950 to Make Changes and Improvements in the Organization and Operation of the Foundation, and for Other Purposes, 362.

¹⁶³ National Science Board, *Approved Minutes of the 136th Meeting of the National Science Board*, NSB-71-84 (National Science Foundation, 1970), 56.

¹⁶⁴ National Science Board, *Approved Minutes of the 136th Meeting of the National Science Board*, 56.

scholars and public input. Constrained by time and resources, NSB was also unable to collect data intentionally curated to answer their research questions. Rather, the reports' authors assembled a patchwork of existing datasets drawn largely from internal and external sources, including previously conducted federal surveys. Owing first to a dearth of output measures available in the data NSB had on hand and, second, to the subsequently limited methods that could be used to analyze the data, the resulting indicators heavily privileged inputs into the scientific enterprise, in the form of R&D expenditures, numbers of employed scientists and engineers and degrees granted in scientific fields. This omission was widely recognized by all involved parties, including NSF itself and President Nixon, who, in his Letter of Transmittal introducing *Science Indicators 1972* to Congress, observed that “present indicators principally reflect the application of resources to science and technology and not the return that the Nation receives from its considerable investment in research and development.”¹⁶⁵ Nixon closed this letter with the firm recommendation that the NSB “develop better measures of the outputs from our Nation’s scientific and technical enterprise in contributing to the progress and welfare of the United States and its citizens”.¹⁶⁶

Among the few output indicators that were included in the early *Science Indicator* reports were citation counts and analysis. These were also among the few measures in the series drawn from an external source – in this case, the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI), the proprietary citation indexing service developed and maintained by Eugene Garfield.¹⁶⁷ Citation counts were

¹⁶⁵ National Science Foundation, Washington, DC. National Science Board, “Science Indicators 1972,” *Science Indicators* (Washington, D.C.: National Science Foundation, 1973), viii, <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED084150>; Richard M. Nixon, “President’s Letter of Transmittal to Congress”, Washington DC, 1973. Quoted in National Science Board, “158th Meeting of the National Science Board - Executive Session” (Washington, DC: National Science Foundation, September 20, 1973), ES:158:14.

¹⁶⁶ “President’s Letter of Transmittal to Congress”, Washington DC, 1973. Quoted in National Science Board, *158th Meeting of the National Science Board - Executive Session*, ES:158:14.

¹⁶⁷ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 7.

used in the *Science Indicators* reports to quantify scientific output as well as to approximate research quality, or, by NSB's equation, the degree to which a publication or body of work had been recognized by peer authors.¹⁶⁸ The intellectual foundations for using citation data in this manner had been laid by Garfield decades earlier, beginning with his 1955 article "Citation Indexes for Science". In this piece, Garfield introduced and proposed a system for tracing the flow of ideas and influence through citations across the published literature.¹⁶⁹ His 1972 article, "Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation," formalized this method as an assessment tool, arguing that citation patterns could be used to map the reputational structure of science and, by extension, to approximate research performance.¹⁷⁰

NSB's decision to include ISI data and methodology as a means of assessing research output and estimated quality was influenced by a report that it commissioned to inform its indicator selection efforts.¹⁷¹ Published in 1976 by Francis Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics* provided critical support for the use of citation analysis as a measure of research influence broadly and as a policy instrument more specifically, demonstrating through various analyses and applications the potential for bibliometric techniques to, first, correlate to other estimations of peer recognition and, second, trace the return on federal investment in science, creating pivotal linkages between funding inputs and the research outputs they ultimately supported.¹⁷²

The same year Narin's report was published, *Science Indicators* also drew the attention of external oversight bodies, prompting formal review by both Congress and the U.S. General

¹⁶⁸ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 7.

¹⁶⁹ Garfield, "Citation Indexes for Science."

¹⁷⁰ Garfield, "Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation."

¹⁷¹ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, ii.

¹⁷² Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, 141.

Accounting Office. In March 1976, the House Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis convened a hearing titled *Measuring and Evaluating the Results of Federally Funded Research*, bringing together NSF officials, policy experts, and academic researchers in a two day-long discussion of the extent to which the indicators then in use might capture the outcomes of federal R&D expenditures. Testimony revealed a shared unease with the program’s overreliance on input measures, its limited treatment of outputs, and its failure to reflect the public benefit of science. This concern was echoed in a report from the U.S. General Accounting Office (GAO), which reviewed the design and construction of the Science Indicators series, focusing specifically on *SI-76*. The GAO acknowledged the program’s overall significance and nodded to the indicators’ potential value but ultimately concluded that the indicators were of limited value unless interpreted cautiously and contextualized appropriately.¹⁷³ The report also faulted NSF for offering insufficient guidance on the appropriate uses and limitations of its data, warning that without scrutiny, the indicators risked being misused or over-interpreted in policy contexts for which they were not originally designed.¹⁷⁴

Simultaneously, critiques were beginning to emerge from within the scientific and scholarly communities themselves, some via conferences dedicated to the review and discussion of the *Science Indicators* reports. The first of these was initiated in 1974 by Dr. Eleanor Bernert Sheldon, then President of the Social Science Research Council (SSRC). Recognizing the importance of the newly released *Science Indicators 1972* report, Sheldon convened a small conference at the Stanford Center for Advanced Study in the Behavioral Sciences, bringing

¹⁷³ United States Government Accountability Office, “Science Indicators: Improvements Needed in Design, Construction, and Interpretation,” 51, accessed April 25, 2024, <https://www.gao.gov/products/pad-79-35>.

¹⁷⁴ United States Government Accountability Office, “Science Indicators,” 39.

together a group of leading scholars to examine the concept of science indicators from the perspectives of history, sociology, political science, and economics. The outcome of this conference was *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, published in 1978 and now a canonical resource in the fields of bibliometrics and metascience, featuring Robert K. Merton, Derek de Solla Price, Zvi Griliches, Eugene Garfield, John Ziman, and Harriet Zuckerman – many of the fields’ most prominent mid-century scholars.

Reflections by Price, Garfield, and Zuckerman were later included in a special issue of *Scientometrics* that was at once dedicated to a critique of *SI-76* and self-styled as an informal follow-on to *Toward a Metric of Science*. Papers published in this volume also originated from an event organized by the SSRC’s Subcommittee on *Science Indicators*, this one held in 1978 with a specific focus on the recently released *Science Indicators 1976* report. Written by Harriet Zuckerman, the introduction to this issue details its specific intent to feature papers that “concentrate far more often on specific problems in devising adequate indicators of the state of the scientific and technological enterprise... than those in *Toward a Metric of Science*,” highlighting what the editors observed as the “institutionalization of research on science indicators” and acknowledging that “there is now less ‘getting ready’ and more work actually being done.”¹⁷⁵

The following year, Eugene Garfield’s Institute for Scientific Information (ISI) hosted a conference titled *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature*. Partially funded by NSF and explicitly designed to bring together information scientists, science studies researchers, and analytical methods specialists, the event

¹⁷⁵ Harriet Zuckerman and Roberta Balstad Miller, “Introduction,” *Scientometrics* 2, no. 5 (1980): 328, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02095074>.

featured six papers on bibliometric data sources, indicator construction methods, and policy applications. In addition to paper sessions, the conference included workshops designed to surface use cases across research management, science policy, and the study of science itself. This discourse – extending from the *Science Indicators* reports themselves to the deliberations of the National Science Board that shaped them, and the critical responses that followed – documents the emergence of what will become a decades-long power struggle over the control and normative shaping of the U.S. scientific enterprise.

4.2 Control

The emergence of *Science Indicators* as a federal reporting instrument marked a shift in how the U.S. research enterprise was both assessed and managed. Prior to this shift, the assessment of research largely took place within the scientific community itself, through the mechanisms of peer review, disciplinary reputation, and long-standing, field-specific expressions of judgment and consensus. These forms of evaluation constituted a kind of distributed control in which scientists determined the merits of research primarily by reference to internal norms. The *Science Indicators* initiative presented a landmark reconfiguration of this arrangement. By translating the abstract notion of “scientific health” into standardized data for federal reporting, NSF and NSB were positioned as central actors in the articulation of evaluative priorities. The stated aim was to furnish Congress and the public with a periodic snapshot of the nation’s scientific condition, however this technical apparatus also carried epistemic and political implications, formalizing decisions about which dimensions of science should be rendered visible and how and by whom they should be

measured. As mentioned, indicators were chosen for their availability, stability, and policy relevance, not for their capacity to reflect the complexity of scientific practice. As such, the system privileged what could be consistently measured across time with available data, even when those measures were acknowledged as incomplete or conceptually underdeveloped.

The authors of the series recognized this limitation and emphasized in the introduction to each of the first five issues that the reports were intended to be understood as experimental, approached with caution, and remain responsive to critique from the scholarly community. In the opening pages of *SI-72*, the effort was introduced as “a long-term experiment to determine if a useful system of indices can be devised in the years ahead”.¹⁷⁶ The provisional nature of the opening disclosures changed over the years, shifting focus from a question of whether it was possible to how it might be achieved. Nevertheless, caution was continuously advised. “Quantitative indicators, no matter how useful, are not a substitute for the experience and judgment of the scientific community,” warn the authors of *SI-72*. “Indeed, the interpretation of indicators – what they mean for the present and future health of the enterprise – requires the judgment of this community.”¹⁷⁷ This sentiment was repeated across the introductions to *SI-74*, *-76*, *-78*, and *-80*, with the focus shifting over time to ultimately come to rest, with the publication of *SI-76*, on the judgement of policymakers rather than that of the scientific community.¹⁷⁸

While this evolution suggests a certain maturation of the reports from evaluative experiment to actionable policy instrument, they were continuously treated as living documents designed to be responsive to community critique and input. The first explicit invitation of such

¹⁷⁶ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, vii.

¹⁷⁷ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, vii.

¹⁷⁸ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1976*, Science Indicators (National Science Board, 1977), viii, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA387209.pdf>.

input came with *SI-74*, in which the hope is shared that “that all those interested in science indicators will participate in the search” for measures.¹⁷⁹ The 1974 report is also the first to acknowledge influence from outside the NSB itself, noting the work of the Social Science Research Council and the then timely seminar they held, ultimately resulting in the publication of *Toward a Metric of Science*.¹⁸⁰ SSRC was again referenced in the 1978 report, then as a direct and intentionally engaged contributor.¹⁸¹ Two years later, in *Science Indicators 1980*, NSF took a further step by including a reader response card designed to elicit suggestions from the broader research and policy communities (see Figure 3).¹⁸²

¹⁷⁹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1974*, Science Indicators (National Science Board, 1975), viii, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA387126.pdf>.

¹⁸⁰ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1974*, viii.

¹⁸¹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1978*, Science Indicators (National Science Board, 1979), viii, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA387151>.

¹⁸² National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1980*, Science Indicators (National Science Board, 1981), 369, <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/101876576>.

USER SURVEY

The judgments and inputs of users of this report are valuable elements for the planning of *Science Indicators—1982*. In addition to providing responses to the following questions, users are encouraged to communicate further with the Science Indicators Unit of the National Science Foundation.

1. How do you think you will use this report?
(check all that apply)

Monitoring trends
 Instructional material
 Developing legislation
 General information source
 Projecting or forecasting
 Developing material for budgets, planning or administration
 Preparing position papers or speeches
 Other: _____

2. What do you see as the strengths and weaknesses of this report, compared to similar reports?
(check all that apply)

Strengths	Item	Weaknesses
<input type="checkbox"/>	Breadth of content	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Interpretation and explanation	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Summaries and overviews	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Topical/author index	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Index of data for selected policy issues	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Organization and format	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Figures and graphs	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Style of text	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Documentation of sources	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Statistical tables	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Frequency of issuance	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trend data	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	_____	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	_____	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Please elaborate on the weaknesses checked in Item 2 and other areas of improvement.

4. Which indicators or interpretations are the best overall indicators of science and technology?

5. Which indicators or interpretations:
a. are or will be of most use to you in your work?
b. should be omitted from future reports, and why?
c. could feasibly be included in the next report but are not here?

6. What is your employment sector?
(check one)

Federal Government
 Business or industry
 College or university
 The Press
 Other: _____

7. What is your major responsibility?
(check one)

Administrative, management or planning
 Teaching
 Student
 R&D activities (incl. R&D mgt.)
 Staff analysis
 Other: _____

8. How did you receive this report?
(check one)

Purchased it
 By request from NSF
 By direct mail from NSF
 From library
 Routed from someone else

9. Which of the previous reports have you used?

Science Indicators—1972
 Science Indicators—1974
 Science Indicators—1976
 Science Indicators—1978

Figure 3: A reader feedback survey included in *Science Indicators 1980*¹⁸³

For their part, however, the research community did not wait for an invitation to weigh in. As was highlighted in the introduction to this chapter, it was in fact Eleanor Bernert Sheldon, then president of the SSRC, who in response to the introduction of the Science Indicator effort summoned a group of experts – social scientists, sociologists and historians of science, information scientists, and others – to join a workshop dedicated to the discussion and critique of *SI-72*. In the introduction of the volume that resulted from this gathering, editors Yehuda Elkana, Joshua

¹⁸³ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators, 1980*, 369.

Lederberg, Robert K. Merton, Arnold Thackray, and Harriet Zuckerman noted that science indicators are, at root, social indicators, placing them within the political realities inherent to any social system:

Whether pursued with scientific rigor or deliberately cast in the modes of humanistic understanding, any indicator of the state, character, or direction of change in science will necessarily reflect not only the *Ding an sich* it seeks to capture... but also the historical experience, fundamental assumptions, and present visions of the group or groups that gave it birth.... That is, indicators in general and science indicators in particular may serve as modes in which to shape knowledge, to mediate perceptions, to order values, and to handle ambition.¹⁸⁴

The editors' framing centers an argument that the development of science indicators was, from the start and by virtue of its very genesis, embedded in the political and institutional realities of its time. Several contributors to the volume traced this entanglement further, examining how science indicators were shaped by the imperatives of federal governance and, in turn reshaped how science itself is understood and evaluated. Physicist and historian of science Gerald Holton, for instance, makes the argument explicit by placing the Science Indicators effort in the political context of the 1970s – most immediately, in the infamy of the Nixon White House.¹⁸⁵ Observing more generally of the broader context in which *SI-72* arose, he surfaces an inherent tension underlying its production:

The scientific community, and to some extent the Congress, see the NSB as an independent board of scientific statesmen, in a position to speak out forthrightly to the President and the Congress on the state of science and the interests of the scientific community and whose scholarly and scientific training and credentials should certify the independence and quality of any report they issue. In contrast, the Administration sees the NSB as a part of the Administration, subject to its political discipline.... The result is evidently an uneasy accommodation in a constant tug-of-war between the NSB and the OMB.¹⁸⁶

¹⁸⁴ Yehuda Elkana et al., eds., *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators* (John Wiley & Sons, 1978), 2–5.

¹⁸⁵ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 51.

¹⁸⁶ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 51–52.

That the emergence of the *Science Indicators* reports instigated a power struggle is certainly among the clearest findings of this analysis of control across the Science Indicators period. Indeed, control, power, and the managerial implications of a state-sponsored assessment enterprise were directly and repeatedly discussed by scientists during the time. Some of the most forceful emerged from the proceedings of the 1979 ISI conference, bound in a volume that was prefaced by ISI's H. Roberts Coward. In his remarks, Coward situates the matter of science indicators squarely within a political context, observing that "the quest for science indicators reflects the fact that science has become a major concern of national governments." He continues:

The result has been a highly ambivalent relationship. While most participants agreed that the National Science Board's Science Indicators series must be viewed as a policy document to one degree or another, it was also recognized that decision-makers, the scientific community, and social researchers or indicator constructors had different needs and objectives. The more decision-oriented the indicator, the greater the skepticism it meets from scientists and university-based researchers. Policymakers seek criteria for decisions, but dislike the loss of flexibility that having visible criteria entails and resist the number crunching techniques developed by social scientists.¹⁸⁷

This tension between the desire for informed governance and the limits of what science indicators could meaningfully convey was further articulated by William D. Carey, then Executive Officer of the American Association for the Advancement of Science, in his opening address at the conference. Carey – a career scientist working at the boundary between research and policy – spoke candidly about the fraught relationship between decision-making and the evidentiary frameworks that claim to support it. "All of us who have struggled with decision-making," he reflects, "know all too well that the decision rules are very shaky. We itch for evidence on which

¹⁸⁷ Institute for Scientific Information, Inc., *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature: Proceedings* (National Science Foundation, 1980), iii, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27521048>.

to act. It turns out, on the whole, that we fall back on proxies for the evidence that isn't there.”¹⁸⁸ In these remarks, Carey gives voice to a widespread concern that in the absence of clear or sufficient evidence, indicators might be embraced for this convenience rather than for their accuracy.

What seemed to trouble Carey most, however, was not the existence of indicators per se, but the pressures that might lead them to become determinative.

Even as we thrash around for quantifiers and measures,” he muses, “we are implicitly skeptical of the signals they appear to emit, and we resist grounding our decisions to them.... I live with the small nightmare that as policy dilemmas become more acute... the tendency to embrace shortcuts and pretentious indicator systems will prove nearly irresistible and ultimately regrettable.”¹⁸⁹

Carey articulates here what might be read as the central paradox of the Science Indicators period: that tools designed to support judgment under uncertainty might become substitutes for judgment itself. “My point,” he concludes, “is that science indicators can take us only so far in informing policy management.... I do not wish to see them controlling outcomes.”¹⁹⁰

This sense of foreboding extends throughout the literature written by members of the research community in response to the introduction of the *Science Indicators* efforts. Despite the fact that the introductions to each of the earliest reports underscore their exploratory nature and design as dynamic efforts intended to be responsive to critique, they were instantly operationalized as policy instruments – a fact that did not escape attention by the scholarly community. Gerald Holton noted this, observing that ‘even while they are being shaped, they are unlikely to remain

¹⁸⁸ Institute for Scientific Information, Inc., *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature: Proceedings*, 2.

¹⁸⁹ Institute for Scientific Information, Inc., *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature: Proceedings*, 2.

¹⁹⁰ Institute for Scientific Information, Inc., *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature: Proceedings*, 3.

unused in science-policy decisions.”¹⁹¹ He undermines his own equivocation in the paragraph that follows, however, noting the NSB’s own acknowledgement that *Science Indicators* were known to have influenced Presidential budgetary decisions as early as 1977.¹⁹² In her introduction to the issue of *Scientometrics* that was dedicated to a review of *SI-76*, Harriet Zuckerman noted much the same, observing that while

[i]ntended to be objective accounts of "the strengths and weaknesses of science and technology", these reports are inevitably perceived as having been prepared by proponents of scientific and technological research for an audience which is ultimately responsible for setting United States science and technology policy. Regardless of the intent of those who produce them, the Science Indicators volumes have come to be political as well as descriptive technical documents.¹⁹³

This reconfiguration of evaluative authority – from a peer community to top-down, managerial systems – marked a fundamental shift in how research was assessed. Whereas disciplinary norms had long guided judgments of quality through peer review, professional recognition, and field-specific standards, the *Science Indicators* initiative introduced a parallel system based on standardized, policy-driven metrics. This shift raised immediate questions about what, exactly, was being measured and how those measures might stand in for the more complex judgments traditionally reserved for local experts. It is to related questions of quality, and the attempts made during the Science Indicators period to define and approximate it, that the next section turns.

¹⁹¹ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 40.

¹⁹² Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 41.

¹⁹³ Zuckerman and Miller, “Introduction,” 328.

4.3 Quality

To assess the quality of something, one must first define it and identify a proper unit of measure. These initial charges were among the most discussed – and hotly debated – throughout the Science Indicators period, as the input/output model of science implicit in the *Science Indicators* reports fell under immediate scrutiny across the research community. From their first issue, the reports and the indicators that were discussed within their pages were premised on input and output measures – counts and tabulations of the things that went into scientific production (including funding, education, work hours), and approximate measures and estimations of the things that were produced (such as patents, papers, and their citations). This model reflected several assumptions about science as a process and an industry – many of which were quickly taken up as points of contention across the scientific community.

One of the most pervasive arguments against the implicit *Science Indicators* model was that in focusing only on inputs and outputs, the complex space that exists between the two is collapsed, precluding any possible examination of what many scholars referred to as the “internalities” of science. William Carey gives shape to these phenomena in his opening address to the 1979 ISI conference, considering what is lost when research outputs and their spoils – what he refers to as “externalities” – are overly prized. “You see, I have a problem,” he confesses.

I am much less preoccupied with the externalities of science than with the elements that really bear on its advancement or decline. I want to know whether the external scale and grandeur masks a creeping conservatism in scientific research, an aversion to unorthodox research, induced by the rigors of funding routines, peer review, and rationing constraints.... I have some concern lest we build indicator frameworks which have the unintended but practical effect of so concentrating our

minds on the quantifiable externalities as to block out the noise arising from the vitals of the research system.¹⁹⁴

In their contribution to the 1980 science indicators-focused issue of *Scientometrics*, Harriet Zuckerman and Roberta Balstad Miller also speak in terms of these internalities by referencing their counterpoints as forwarded in *SI-76*. “Tables, charts and text are given over to how many people are engaged in research, how much is spent on it, where it takes place,” they observe, “but little attention is given to what research is being done, why the money is being spent, and whether what has been produced is scientifically consequential.”¹⁹⁵

The GAO report published in response to *SI-76* directly advances these criticisms, centering a pervasive critique that the report “does not sufficiently differentiate science from technology and views these activities only in terms of economic resources and tangible products..., [leaving] both the process of scientific work and the substance of scientific knowledge”.¹⁹⁶ Due to the fact that the reports continued to avoid interpretation – a decision justified in their introductions as a necessary result of both their scope and the limitations of the indicators themselves – the GAO ultimately finds that these challenges render the report to be “at odds with” its own purpose.¹⁹⁷

As if in direct response to these criticisms, *Science Indicators 1980* introduces a new chapter titled “Advances in Science,” heralded in the report’s introduction as an attempt to “convey the process and significance of research” in acknowledgement of the fact that “the substantive aspects of science and technology are not easily captured by quantitative indicators”.¹⁹⁸ The

¹⁹⁴ Institute for Scientific Information, Inc., *Research Needs and Applications for Indicators Based on the Scientific and Technical Literature: Proceedings*, 3–4.

¹⁹⁵ Harriet Zuckerman and Roberta Balstad Miller, “Indicators of Science: Notes and Queries,” *Scientometrics* 2, no. 5 (1980): 349, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02095077>.

¹⁹⁶ United States Government Accountability Office, “Science Indicators,” ii.

¹⁹⁷ United States Government Accountability Office, “Science Indicators,” ii.

¹⁹⁸ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators, 1980*, vii.

chapter offers a series of descriptive vignettes highlighting recent scientific and engineering achievements, selected to illustrate not only outcomes but the nature of the research process itself. It explicitly acknowledges the limitations of prior reports in capturing the “complexities and nuances” of science, noting that most indicators fail to reflect the ingenuity, interdisciplinarity, and serendipity that often characterize meaningful advances.¹⁹⁹ As stated in its introduction, the chapter aims to deepen appreciation of research as an evolving and contingent process, one in which significant contributions regularly emerge unpredictably, across disciplinary boundaries, and as a result of novel methods and instruments.

Consequence, significance, and influence are discussed much more regularly across the literature reviewed for this chapter than is quality explicitly. They are sought in the outputs of science, via the very indicators that so stymied the authors of the first five issues of *Science Indicators* and that are so often discussed as being interchangeable. Throughout those reports, the notion of the qualitative attributes of science is operationalized almost exclusively through the use of bibliometric indicators in the form of citation counts and analyses, alongside more occasional references to other standard bearers of prestige such as the Nobel Prize. While this limited approach was not directly acknowledged in any of the *Science Indicators* reports analyzed as part of this study, it was recognized behind the scenes, in early planning sessions of the NSB. Captured in the minutes from the Executive Session of the 151st Meeting of the National Science Board is a commitment on the part of the Ad Hoc Committee on Science Indicators to “continue to study,

¹⁹⁹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators*, 1980, 182.

develop, and refine the science indicators (especially to include more quality indicators for future reports)”.²⁰⁰

Nevertheless, from *SI-72* through *SI-80*, the most explicit discussions of quality appear in sections dedicated to the analysis of scientific and technical publications. Here, citation counts are used to quantify output and estimate what the reports often refer to as the “relative ‘quality’ or ‘significance’ of the literature”.²⁰¹ *SI-72* offers a clear statement of the logic underlying this correlation: “The basis for this indicator was the number of citations to the literature produced by each country in each scientific area. The general rationale for such an index is the expectation that the most significant literature will be most frequently cited, whereas relatively unimportant research articles will attract few, if any, citations.”²⁰² The same rationale appears later in *SI-80*, which states that “citations are used to measure influence and quality under the assumption that the most significant literature will be more frequently cited than routine literature.”²⁰³

The logic underpinning the use of citations as indicators of something approximating quality did not originate with NSF or the *Science Indicators* reports themselves. Rather, it was articulated earlier by Eugene Garfield. Garfield’s early publications, particularly his 1955 article “Citation Indexes for Science” and his 1972 follow-up “Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation,” argued that citation patterns could map the structure of scientific communication and identify work that had achieved the quality-adjacent status of disciplinary significance.²⁰⁴ However, as it relates to the assessment of quality itself, it is important to note that as early as

²⁰⁰ National Science Board, *151st Meeting of the National Science Board - Executive Session*, NSB-72-280 Limited Distribution) (National Science Foundation, 1972), ES:151:14.

²⁰¹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 7.

²⁰² National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 10.

²⁰³ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators, 1980*, 17.

²⁰⁴ Garfield, “Citation Indexes for Science”; Garfield, “Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation.”

1979, Garfield was explicit in distinguishing the measurement of significance from assessments of other qualitative value. “The only responsible claim made for citation counts,” he cautions, “is that they provide an objective measure of the utility or impact of scientific work. They say nothing about the nature of the work, nothing about the reason for its utility or impact.”²⁰⁵

Garfield’s cautionary parsing did little to prevent the institutional uptake of citation analysis as a surrogate for quality. Francis Narin’s *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, commissioned by NSF, reflects the evolving role of citation analysis in policy discourse, particularly as it pertained to the measurement of research quality. While Narin did not offer a definition of quality in his report, he referenced it regularly, often in tandem with productivity, treating it as an outcome that could be reasonably approximated through bibliometric measures. Rather than interrogate the conceptual assumptions underpinning this approach, Narin traced a body of literature comparing bibliometric indicators to non-bibliometric metrics such as departmental rankings, peer evaluations, and measures of professional “eminence”.²⁰⁶ He acknowledged that there was no absolute standard of quality or productivity but maintained that correlations between citation counts and these alternative indicators were “typical” and sufficient to justify a “rule of reason” approach.²⁰⁷ “The fundamental problem in any discussion of the validity of indicators of scientific productivity,” he writes,

is the fact that there is no absolute standard of measure of such productivity. The classic scientific approach would be to obtain the best possible set of indicators of quality or productivity from the literature, and validate these indicators through correlations and similar analyses with independent, objective and quantitative

²⁰⁵ E. Garfield, “Is Citation Analysis a Legitimate Evaluation Tool?,” *Scientometrics* 1, no. 4 (1979): 364, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02019306>.

²⁰⁶ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, 85.

²⁰⁷ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, 82.

measures of scientific productivity and quality. Unfortunately, no such set of independent, objective, quantitative indicators exists....²⁰⁸

In this framing, citation metrics were presented as viable because they mirrored the outcomes of other reputation-based systems. *Evaluative Bibliometrics* thus provided a pragmatic rationale for the continued use of citation analysis in federal assessment efforts, reinforcing the notion that research quality, while difficult to define, could nonetheless be inferred through patterns of citation and their alignment with more established markers of prestige.

The claim that citation counts meaningfully correlate with peer judgments of research importance and contribution was tested and cautiously supported in the work of Jonathan Cole, Stephen Cole, and Lorraine Dietrich, whose contribution to *Toward a Metric of Science* offers an empirical study exploring the relationship between research quality – as represented by, among other things, disciplinary reputation and rates of citation.²⁰⁹ Drawing on their own data comparing citation frequency to peer evaluations, the authors report a reasonably high degree of correlation, which they suggest as evidence that citation data could, in some cases, reflect the reputational consensus of a field.²¹⁰ However, even as they acknowledge this correlation, they stress that both citation behavior and peer review are socially structured phenomena, subject to disciplinary norms, reputational dynamics, and strategic behavior. As such, they warn against the uncritical substitution of citation metrics for qualitative judgment, cautioning that “the development of indicators... must be coupled with the identification and measurement of other conditions that attend the advance of scientific knowledge.”²¹¹

²⁰⁸ Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, 82.

²⁰⁹ Stephen Cole et al., “Measuring the Cognitive State of Scientific Disciplines,” in *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, ed. Yehuda Elkana et al. (John Wiley & Sons, 1978).

²¹⁰ Cole et al., “Measuring the Cognitive State of Scientific Disciplines,” 248.

²¹¹ Cole et al., “Measuring the Cognitive State of Scientific Disciplines,” 250.

Building on the implicit challenges raised by Cole, Cole, and Dietrich regarding the social structuring of citation behavior, Gerald Holton asks more fundamentally whether scientific quality can or should be quantified at all.²¹² Writing from a dual perspective as practitioner and historian, he acknowledges the administrative appeal of numerical indicators and yet cautions that scientific excellence often hinges on singular events such as a breakthrough paper or disciplinary shift that resist aggregation and may prove illegible to conventional indicators.²¹³ These moments, he argues, are rarely identifiable in real time, often only becoming visible through retrospective analysis.²¹⁴ His broader point regards the nature of science itself, suggesting that its epistemological leaps and risk-taking are ill-suited to capture through the logic of quantitative evaluation. Holton thus raises the stakes of quality assessment – “a precarious task” – urging readers to consider not just how science might be measured, but what gets lost along the way.²¹⁵

While the question of quality animated many of the methodological discussions surrounding the Science Indicators reports, a similar but distinct concern regarded how best to evidence the value of scientific research. If quality refers to internal judgments of significance, consequence, or influence within and across the scientific community, value is more often perceived in terms of science’s relationship to the broader public – its utility, impact, and justification as a matter of public investment. The following section examines how research value was framed and negotiated across the Science Indicators period, with particular attention to the ways in which science was rendered accountable to both political and economic concerns.

²¹² Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?”

²¹³ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 43.

²¹⁴ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 44.

²¹⁵ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 43.

4.4 Value

Throughout the Science Indicators period, discussions of research value were shaped by a sense of urgency across policy circles regarding the need to both demonstrate and affect the value of science and its supporting investments to the American public. Indeed, the very introduction of the *Science Indicators* reports marked a significant formalization of science as a matter of public concern, emerging from a post-World War landscape defined by increasing federal investment in scientific research, the establishment of dedicated funding agencies, and a mid-Vietnam War reality amid which public sentiment regarding research expenditures was heavily influenced by perceptions of the war effort more broadly. Thus, the reports, while initially engineered in response to the 1968 Congressional mandate, also served to position science as a public institution – one whose vitality, impact, and direction were understood to bear directly on national well-being.

The position that science has the potential to affect national well-being is one that is asserted throughout the reports but never explicitly established. It is taken as a given, in many respects serving as a point of departure for the reports themselves. In the inaugural Letter of Transmittal prefacing *SI-72*, H.E. Carter, Chairman of the National Science Board, frames the effort in terms of its “ultimate goal”: a set of measures that would “[guide] the Nation’s research and development along paths most rewarding for our society”.²¹⁶ The report’s introduction asserts similarly that, “[s]uch indicators, updated annually, should provide an early warning of events and trends which may reduce the capacity of science... to meet the needs of the Nation.” Ultimately, the authors observe, these indicators might illustrate “the consequent impacts [of science] on that

²¹⁶ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, iii.

elusive entity, the ‘quality of life.’”²¹⁷ Such sentiments carry through to the introduction of *SI-80*, introduced by then NSB Chairman Lewis M. Branscomb with a Letter of Transmittal in which he observes that “[s]cience and technology pervade every aspect of our daily lives and will continue to have an increasingly important role in the strength and welfare of the Nation.”²¹⁸

An important dimension of this effort to assert and evidence the value of science can be found in a recurring chapter included in four of the five *Science Indicators* reports analyzed for this study – a dedicated chapter in *SI-72*, *-74*, *-76* and *-80* presenting data from public opinion surveys gauging American attitudes toward science and technology. Framed as tools for capturing the public’s views, these surveys were used to support the underlying premise that federal investment in science should reflect and respond to citizen priorities. In the earliest iterations of the report series, the public is cast primarily as the intended beneficiary of scientific progress, on the receiving end of the many social and economic benefits science was presumed to produce. These chapters therefore reinforce the legitimacy of science and its public funding by demonstrating that Americans continued to view science as a positive and transformative force – and indeed they did. The high-level takeaways from each of the surveys illustrate a high level of faith in and support for science as a perceived net positive, with an average of 72% of respondents noting that science had changed life for the better, and investments in medical research consistently championed throughout the years (see Figure 4 and Figure 5).²¹⁹

²¹⁷ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, vii.

²¹⁸ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators, 1980*, iii.

²¹⁹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 96–97; National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1974*, 143–44; National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1976*, 173–74; National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators, 1980*, 161.

6-6. Have science and technology changed life for the <i>better</i> or for the <i>worse</i> ?			
Response	Percent		
	1972	1974	1976
Better	70	75	71
Worse	8	5	7
Both	11	11	12
Neither/no effect	2	3	3
No opinion	9	6	7

SOURCE: Opinion Research Corporation, *op. cit.*, p. 18.

Figure 4: Table from *SI-76* illustrating public perceptions of science²²⁰

6-9. Benefits from science and technology (Cited by those feeling they do more good than harm)		
Benefit	Percent citing ¹	
	1972	1976
Improvements in medicine	79	81
Space exploration	26	24
General improvements (products and living conditions in general)	12	14
Protecting environment, conservation	12	11
Electrical and electronic products	9	11
Improved methods of travel and transportation	9	9
Food and agriculture	9	7
Energy programs	2 ²	5
Improved communications	3	4
Other answers	16	9
Don't know	4	4

¹ Two responses were requested.
² Includes only atomic energy in 1972.

SOURCE: Opinion Research Corporation, *op. cit.*, pp. 23-33.

Figure 5: Table from *SI-76* illustrating specific perceived benefits of science²²¹

By the 1980 edition of *Science Indicators*, however, the public had become a more strategic object of the reports' analyses. The introduction to that year's chapter on public attitudes begins with a straightforward reflection on the realities of political life in a participatory democracy,

²²⁰ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1976*, 172.

²²¹ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1976*, 173.

observing that while most Americans may lack detailed knowledge or firm opinions about science and technology, the public nonetheless "retains a veto on all political questions if it becomes motivated to utilize that power."²²² Here, the public is no longer simply a beneficiary to be served, but rather a political force to be managed – a population whose views could be strategically tracked and cultivated. This logic is particularly evident in the report's introduction of the "attentive public" – a subgroup defined by their interest in, knowledge of, and information-seeking behaviors surrounding science and technology.²²³ This constituency is presented as politically consequential, likely to engage in science-relevant policy debates and to therefore influence broader public opinion. This shift in emphasis from the public as a monolithic constituency to the "attentive" public as a strategically significant bloc marks an important shift in how the value of science was imagined in political terms.

This emerging view of the public as both a beneficiary of science and a political force to be engaged highlights a broader question animating the Science Indicators effort: how can the value of science be demonstrated to those outside the research system? This tension runs throughout the testimony given at the 1976 Congressional hearing on the Science Indicators reports, where the effort to quantify science was publicly discussed by those whose careers depended on their ability to demonstrate and justify Congressional spending. These proceedings repeatedly expose the gap between methodological rigor and political utility, as despite the founding objective to focus "more on methodological questions," members of Congress continuously press the National Science Board on how the reports can be used.²²⁴ The transcripts

²²² National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators*, 1980, 159.

²²³ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators*, 1980, vii.

²²⁴ United States House of Representatives Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis, *Measuring and Evaluating the Results of Federally Supported Research and Development*

are rife with examples of this tension, which is perhaps best illustrated by an exchange between Representative Ray Thornton, Chairman of the Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis, and Dr. Norman Hackerman, Chairman of the National Science Board. Thornton interrupts Hackerman's lengthy narrative on the difficulties of devising indicators sophisticated enough to capture the complex relationship between research and development to return to the basics, posing a much more elementary question about how one might even conceive of the indicators in applied use:

Back on page 6 you mention that... [indicators] are not suitable for use alone.... [I]t occurs to me that what you might be saying is that these indicators are bits of information which can be put on a mosaic like a television screen or a picture made up of bits of information collected by a satellite that orbits another planet and that all of the bits accumulatively may be able to give you a picture or an idea or a reading of the health of science and technology so as to assist in policymaking....²²⁵

This urgency to identify and understand the utility of the *Science Indicators* reports stems from a related urgency to demonstrate the value of federally funded science to the taxpaying American public. While evident throughout the hearings, this point is first made by Chairman Thornton, who opens the hearings with an acknowledgement of the “sometimes shrill” voices of “skepticism... increasingly being heard about the Federal investment of \$23 billion annually in R.&D.”, and who frames the discussion around questions entirely focused on use, application, and audience.²²⁶ One of the hearing's first speakers, Dr. Roger Heynes, then Vice Chairman of the

Part 1 - Special Oversight Hearings Before the Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis of the Committee on Science and Technology, May 19, 1976, 1, <https://hdl.handle.net/2027/mdp.39015069664632>.

²²⁵ United States House of Representatives Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis, *Measuring and Evaluating the Results of Federally Supported Research and Development Part 1 - Special Oversight Hearings Before the Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis of the Committee on Science and Technology*, 17.

²²⁶ United States House of Representatives Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis, *Measuring and Evaluating the Results of Federally Supported Research and Development*

National Science Board, makes the connection between this application and the American public more explicit:

for the hard-pressed taxpayers of this country science must be more than a spectator sport for vicarious enjoyment. Its value has long been accepted as ‘self-evident,’ but serious questions are now arising and have been for more than the last few years. It is nice to know that the United States led the world in Nobel prizes from 1901 to 1974, but the average citizen is entitled to wonder whether he has any deeper stake in maintaining a strong scientific establishment.²²⁷

The question underlying much of this exchange – what, precisely, the nation is getting for its money – reveals an explicitly economic mode of reasoning. In seeking to link federal expenditures to identifiable benefits, policymakers adopted the tools and language of econometric assessment, treating scientific activity as an input whose value could be inferred from measurable social and economic outputs.

Within this emerging economic framework, value is understood throughout the hearings to be identifiable via the output indicators that dominate much of the discussion, not just at the 1976 hearings but across the reflection and criticism of the reports more broadly. However, the nascent effort to establish indicators as proxies for research value raised concerns across the research community about their capacity to meaningfully represent the long-term, diffuse, and often indirect contributions of scientific activity. In his chapter in *Toward a Metric of Science*, John Ziman argues that the benefits of science are often “long-term, generalized, and nonspecific,” making it “extremely difficult to attribute a particular quantifiable benefit to a limited body of science whose

Part 1 - Special Oversight Hearings Before the Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis of the Committee on Science and Technology, 1–2.

²²⁷ United States House of Representatives Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis, *Measuring and Evaluating the Results of Federally Supported Research and Development Part 1 - Special Oversight Hearings Before the Subcommittee on Domestic and International Scientific Planning and Analysis of the Committee on Science and Technology*, 65.

input cost can be estimated, or to assess all the economic benefits that have been gained over a long period from a particular piece of research.”²²⁸ He continues: “these material benefits flow from the generation by science of an intermediate product – knowledge – which becomes available for common use often at negligible cost to the user.... [C]learly knowledge is not an economic category that can be quantified.”²²⁹ Any attempt to do so, he observes, would require a theoretical model capable of representing knowledge creation, communication, and use through a symbolic logic that is incongruent with reality. A model failing in this regard, he warns, “can produce nothing but nonsense.”²³⁰

Zvi Griliches, an economist known for his contribution to the discourse surrounding the challenges of measuring the economic gains accrued from research, extends Ziman’s argument in another chapter in *Toward a Metric of Science* addressing the “Economic problems of Measuring Returns on Research”. His point is made clear as early as the chapter’s second paragraph: “[f]rom an economist’s point of view, the main problem with measuring the ‘output’ of science is that very little of it is sold on any market; from a statistician’s point of view, the problem is that very little of it emerges in units that are comparable. The two problems are not unrelated.”²³¹ To illustrate this point, he considers three primary units that mirror those tabulated within early editions of *Science Indicators*: “invention lists”, patents, and publication counts.²³² The quantification of inventions, he argues, is compromised by inconsistency and subjectivity, while the systemic

²²⁸ John Ziman, “From Parameters to Portents - and Back,” in *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, ed. Yehuda Elkana et al. (New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1978), 265.

²²⁹ Ziman, “From Parameters to Portents - and Back,” 265.

²³⁰ Ziman, “From Parameters to Portents - and Back,” 266.

²³¹ Zvi Griliches, “Economic Problems of Measuring Returns on Research,” in *Toward a Metric of Science: The Advent of Science Indicators*, ed. Yehuda Elkana et al. (John Wiley & Sons, 1978), 171–72.

²³² Griliches, “Economic Problems of Measuring Returns on Research,” 172.

analysis of patents is hampered by what he referred to as a lack of “computerization” and classification – a still nascent research infrastructure that was, at the time, not yet advanced enough to support broadscale metascience analysis.²³³ Of publication counts, he makes a critical point, observing that they had “been used primarily to analyze the internal working of different scientific disciplines rather than to establish a relationship between such measure of ‘science’ and some other measure of socially valuable product.” In other words, and according to Griliches, if the question regards the public value of science, publication counts cannot stand in as an answer, as they only measure what is of value to scientists themselves. “Further progress” in measuring what matters to the broader public, he cautions, “will depend on... devising a new set of measures that can capture better the contribution of science to our lives.”²³⁴

Between the work of Ziman and Griliches, a case is made against leveraging econometric tools in research assessment, their collective point being that knowledge can neither be measured nor compared. In his article *“Indicators of the Impact of R&D on the Economy,”* economist Richard B. Freeman extends this conversation in more applied terms, exploring the ways in which research and development might be linked to economic productivity. To properly set the stage for a discussion of Freeman’s positions, however, it is important to first note that his work – like that of many others during the Science Indicators period – is shaped by a repeated need to draw boundaries between basic and applied research, and between research and development. Across the literature of the period, these distinctions emerge repeatedly as both necessary – one cannot measure something without first identifying it – and problematic, given the increasing

²³³ Griliches, “Economic Problems of Measuring Returns on Research,” 172.

²³⁴ Griliches, “Economic Problems of Measuring Returns on Research,” 177.

interdependence of research domains and the complexity of tracing influence across scientific and development lifecycles.

Freeman's analysis focuses on what he refers to as "R&D," a term he confoundingly does not define. His argument begins on the premise that "[i]ncreases in the stock of useful knowledge due to research and development (R&D)... contribute to economic growth," and yet also acknowledges a problem: exactly how these contributions are made has yet to be identified.²³⁵ Here he turns to a discussion of a then recent study on the returns of basic research – an effort known as "Project Hindsight," designed to measure the contribution of research to the development of weapons systems. According to Freeman, the study found that "basic research has relatively little direct impact on advances," and further that, "[s]tudies of the "spillover" of aerospace R&D on the civilian economy have been hardpressed to find significant effects. Much of the science used in major innovations appears to be relatively 'old' rather than the result of recent research."²³⁶ Echoing the common observation that advances in science can take time to reveal themselves as such, Freeman ultimately makes the point that such advances often arise from the accumulation and diffusion of knowledge across sectors, institutions, and time, rather than from the direct application of research findings. Noting the inherent challenge in quantifying this process of diffusion, Freeman concludes that while it is both important and possible to analyze the influence of science on the economy, any such analysis must be guided by realistic expectations and framed within broader social and policy contexts that often require qualitative assessment to validate.

²³⁵ R. B. Freeman, "Indicators of the Impact of R&D on the Economy," *Scientometrics* 2, no. 5 (1980): 377, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02095080>.

²³⁶ Freeman, "Indicators of the Impact of R&D on the Economy," 377.

The question of research value within the *Science Indicators* period was defined by two commitments that emerged but never fully aligned. First, science was framed as a public institution whose benefits should accrue to – and be intelligible to – the American people. Second, in attempting to evidence those benefits, policymakers and analysts turned to the language and tools of econometrics: expenditures as inputs, publications and patents as outputs – “returns” as evidence of value. The hearings and surrounding commentary reveal the appeal and the limits of this approach, as well as the fact that rather than advancing an assessment framework, the NSB *Science Indicators* reports started a conversation about whether such a framework was possible. These questions that arose – about how value is constituted, to whom it is owed, and whether it can or should be quantified – would continue to animate the political and methodological debates that followed.

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter has traced the history of the U.S. Science Indicators initiative through its inaugural years – roughly 1968 through 1982 – exploring how a Congressional mandate to report annually on the “status and health of science” in the U.S. gave rise to a transformation in research assessment. Faced with the challenges of defining what science is, in what ways it might be recognized as good, and identifying not only its value but also the beneficiaries of that value, NSF cobbled together a system of indicators premised on available data. Although each of the first five *Science Indicators* reports bore caveats warning of their exploratory nature, the reports became quickly institutionalized across federal science policy and decision-making, seemingly confirming

repeated concerns on the part of scientists and researchers who, immediately upon publication of the reports' first edition, raised complex and pointed concerns about their validity, accuracy, and unintended consequences.

Viewed by way of the three analytic themes that frame this research – control, quality, and value – the Science Indicators period illustrates a clear but contentious transformation of authority within and across the scientific enterprise. There was indeed a distinct and energetic tug-of-war afoot, in which policymakers and researchers each made their case about how science might be best understood and evaluated. In their attempt to define the “health” of science, NSF and NSB staked a claim in the definition of science, sparking a debate about what precisely science is, and how it might be distinguished from technology in particular. These definitions became the very grounds on which their efforts were critiqued by the GAO and by researchers, the latter of whom had been engaged in similar debate for some time.

Defining science is a first and necessary step in assessing its quality – one that is directly related to a host of additional and related definitional challenges. In seeking to measure scientific quality, should one assess the process of science, its output, or the effect – the value – of that output? NSF and NSB chose to measure quality in the output of science, but were limited in their ability to do so due to “a paucity” of output indicators.²³⁷ They chose to adopt Eugene Garfield’s Science Citation Index data as the primary source of the output data they were to use, heeding guidance provided by Francis Narin to complete a landscape analysis of the “state of the art” in evaluative bibliometrics at the time. Their justification – that “the most significant literature will

²³⁷ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, iii.

be most frequently cited” – mirrors that of Narin and researchers such as Jonathan Cole and Stephen Cole, each of whom assume some relationship between “significance” and quality.²³⁸

That a research output might be significant is of course dependent on its audience. The presumed audience – and therefore the presumed arbiters – here were other researchers, rendering quality meaningful to an exclusive cohort. This limitation was noted and fretted over by lawmakers seeking to justify growing research expenditures to their constituencies. Such justification was noted in the opening pages of the inaugural editions of *Science Indicators* as among their primary mandates. However, again owing to constraints on available output indicators, their success was itself a matter of debate. Meanwhile, economists, sociologists and other researchers discussed the extensive challenge – perhaps even the impossibility – of an econometrics of science. If it is to be taken that a dollar “in” to the pipeline of science can or should be traced to dollars “out”, the scholars included in this study raised questions about the feasibility of tracing this lineage without interruption, distinguishing it from other comingling influences, and, indeed, defining its integrity and unique identity over long periods and amid the addition and comingling of multiple other streams.

This analysis supports Woolgar’s suggestion that research quality may not serve as a stable object of measurement. It further suggests that, at least as evidenced during the Science Indicators period, quality might at best be understood as an agreement. This agreement is rhetorical, critically dependent on the definitions that give it meaning. Given the stakes – not simply regarding the commitment of the now multibillion-dollar federal funding apparatus but indeed reaching further

²³⁸ National Science Foundation, *Science Indicators 1972*, 10; Narin, *Evaluative Bibliometrics*, ii; Cole et al., “Measuring the Cognitive State of Scientific Disciplines.”

to encompass and identify the very nature, quality, and value of science – this research also supports the assertions of Lucy Suchman, Geoffrey Bowker, and Susan Leigh Star, suggesting that the acts of categorization and definition are also acts of control, supplying the premise upon which assessment and reward might follow. The next chapter traces the history of the Science of Science period, in which definitions and their resulting categories evolve into infrastructure – social and technical – that support the technologies through which the control, quality, and value of the research enterprise continue to be negotiated.

5.0 The Science of Science

5.1 Introduction

The materials discussed in this chapter represent the second period in this history of science indicators as a means of research assessment. Specifically, they detail a period extending roughly from the late 1990s to 2012, and conceived of as the “Science of Science” (SOS) period, in which the use of quantifiable indicators and methods to assess the performance of research activities was the topic of active discussion and debate across a research ecosystem that was simultaneously being cultivated to produce a community of practice to support experts in the maturing field of scientometrics. Scientometrics, or the effort to leverage data in quantitative assessments of research activity is understood as “the science of science” within the context of this dissertation. Whereas the prior period was rather neatly contained by a discrete set of policy-level activities and academic discussions, this period is by contrast highly dynamic and wide ranging, evident across multiple federal initiatives while also dominating both high level and more topical academic conversations.

From a policy perspective, the cornerstone of this chapter is the Science of Science Policy (SoSP) initiative introduced by John Marburger in 2005. The stage was set for the advancement of SoSP throughout the years that intervened between the Science Indicators period of the 1970s and the early 2000s, during which time a Cold War era-influenced preoccupation with national competitiveness dominated the Reagan White House, and concerns about fiscal conservatism,

reducing government waste, and ensuring measurable returns from public spending took hold.²³⁹ This moment in history ultimately led to the development of a formalized performance assessment regime introduced in 1993 – the Government Performance and Results Act (GPRA). GPRA was launched in response to findings that “waste and inefficiency in Federal programs undermine[d] the confidence of the American people in the Government and reduce[d] the Federal Government’s ability to address adequately vital public needs” and established a mandate that all federal programs implement strategic and annual performance plans.

These performance plans were required to “establish performance indicators to be used in measuring or assessing the relevant outputs, service levels, and outcomes of each program activity.”²⁴⁰ To further support this effort to assess the performance of federal programs from a “results-oriented” perspective, the George W. Bush administration advanced the Program Assessment Rating Tool (PART) as part of the Fiscal Year 2004 Budget.²⁴¹ PART was introduced as “a new rating tool to hold agencies accountable for accomplishing results”, and was explicitly premised on the failure of efforts to comply with GPRA requirements, noting that resulting agency strategic plans were “plagued by performance measures that [were] meaningless, vague, too numerous, and often compiled by people who ha[d] no direct connection with budget decisions.”²⁴²

²³⁹ Executive Office of the President, “Reagan Administration Programs to Combat Waste, Fraud and Abuse in the Federal Government,” Ronald Reagan Presidential Library and Museum, n.d., Collection: Correspondence, Office of: Records Folder Title: Reagan Administration Programs to Combat Waste, Fraud and Abuse in the Federal Government Box: 61, Ronald Reagan Presidential Library Digital Library Collections, <https://www.reaganlibrary.gov/public/2021-12/40-108-7564766-061-002-2021.pdf>.

²⁴⁰ Government Performance and Results Act (GPRA), Pub. L. Nos. 103–62, 107 Statute (1993), <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/eta/performance/goals/gpra>.

²⁴¹ George W. Bush, “Rating the Performance of Federal Programs,” Executive Office of the President, April 2002, 47, <https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/news/usbudget/budget-fy2004/performance.html>; Executive Office of the President, “Budget of the United States Government,” The White House, February 3, 2003, <https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/news/usbudget/budget-fy2004/>.

²⁴² Bush, “Rating the Performance of Federal Programs,” 47–49.

The PART tool itself was a questionnaire, designed to assess the extent to which federal agencies could demonstrate program performance. Despite its emphasis on performance measures, it counted among its own weaknesses the challenge of “defining ‘adequate’ performance measures”.²⁴³ The Bush administration further reinforced these priorities through the American Competitiveness Initiative (ACI), announced in 2006. The ACI cast innovation as the linchpin of U.S. competitiveness and explicitly tied expanded federal R&D investment to economic growth and national leadership, providing a clear policy backdrop for Marburger’s call to develop a new science of science policy – one that could generate the benchmarks and models necessary to demonstrate the value of federal research expenditures.

John Marburger introduced the Science of Science Policy initiative in a keynote address to the AAAS Science and Technology Policy Forum in Washington, DC on April 21, 2005. He tied his remarks to the Fiscal Year 2006 Budget and expressed a deep frustration with an observed inability to rely upon existing data and models to inform science policy decisions. Marburger’s call centered a need for better data, better theoretical models and the establishment of a “new interdisciplinary field of quantitative science policy studies.”²⁴⁴ These were pursued by a variety of related initiatives, including an Interagency Task Group that was formed by the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) Subcommittee on Social and Behavioral Sciences and charged to “develop a roadmap of federal efforts directed towards the long-term development of a

²⁴³ Bush, “Rating the Performance of Federal Programs,” 52.

²⁴⁴ Marburger, III, “2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum Keynote Address,” 7.

science of science policy.”²⁴⁵ This roadmap was published in 2008, offering ten guiding questions synthesized from a landscape analysis of the current state of the art.

In 2007, NSF committed \$6.8 million towards the establishment of a new Science of Science and Innovation Policy (SciSIP) program within its Directorate for Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences (SBE).²⁴⁶ Its primary goals were to “understand the contexts, structures and processes of science and engineering research, to evaluate reliably the tangible and intangible returns from investments in research and development (R&D), and to predict the likely returns from future R&D investments”, which it planned to pursue by funding research and other initiatives that would help to “develop usable knowledge and theories of creative processes and their transformation into social and economic outcomes; improve and expand science metrics, datasets and analytical tools... and develop a community of experts across the Federal government, industry and universities focused on SciSIP”.²⁴⁷ A major goal of the SciSIP program was to develop the community of practice around the science of science policy that Marburger called for in 2005 and that the Interagency Taskforce further championed in 2008. The program was envisioned and described as a means through which to foster interdisciplinary research, building bridges and

²⁴⁵ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy: A Federal Research Roadmap* (National Science and Technology Council Office of Science and Technology Policy, 2008), 35, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA496840>.

²⁴⁶ *The Science of Science and Innovation Policy (111-109): Hearing before the Subcommittee on Research and Science Education*, House of Representatives, 111th Congress Second Session (2010), at 4, <https://www.loc.gov/item/2023695659/>; National Science Foundation, “Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Science of Science and Innovation Policy: A Prospectus,” September 2006, https://scisip.weebly.com/uploads/1/6/8/5/1685925/scisip_prospectus_9.2006.pdf.

²⁴⁷ National Science Foundation, “Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Science of Science and Innovation Policy: A Prospectus,” 1.

relationships between the communities traditionally involved in scientometrics and those that practiced in the natural and social sciences.²⁴⁸

Julia Lane, an economist, was program director of SciSIP in the mid-2000s and, as such, served as an active proponent of an initiative known as STAR METRICS (“Science and Technology for America’s Reinvestment: Measuring the Effect of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science”), a joint venture between NIH and NSF designed to capture data relevant to the inputs and outputs of federally funded science.²⁴⁹ The STAR METRICS program centered scientists as the core “unit of analysis” and set out to establish links between scientists, their federal funding received, and the social and economic outcomes of the federally funded work they pursued.²⁵⁰ It was also among the SoSP initiatives discussed by members of the Subcommittee on Research and Science Education, part of the House of Representatives’ Committee on Science and Technology. The Subcommittee convened a hearing into the science of science policy on September 23, 2010, inviting Julia Lane, two academics funded by the SciSIP program (Fiona Murray and Daniel Sarewitz), and Albert Teich, Director of Science & Policy Programs with the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), to speak to present efforts to develop a science of science policy that might inform the budgetary and other concerns of Congress.²⁵¹ In 2010, Julia Lane also published an editorial in *Nature* that served effectively as a

²⁴⁸ National Science Foundation, “Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Science of Science and Innovation Policy: A Prospectus,” 5.

²⁴⁹ Office of Science and Technology Policy, “STAR METRICS: New Way to Measure the Impact of Federally Funded Research,” Executive Office of the President, May 28, 2010, <https://web.archive.org/web/20100709102023/http://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/STAR%20METRICS%20FINAL.pdf>.

²⁵⁰ Julia I. Lane et al., “STAR METRICS: Science and Technology for America’s Reinvestment: Measuring the Effects of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science,” n.d., https://sites.nationalacademies.org/cs/groups/pgasite/documents/webpage/pga_059236.pdf; Office of Science and Technology Policy, “STAR METRICS: New Way to Measure the Impact of Federally Funded Research.”

²⁵¹ *The Science of Science and Innovation Policy (111-109)*.

promotional piece touting the benefits and importance of the SciSIP program to the scientific community. In it, she translates the concerns of the SoSP initiative (developing indicators, models and methodologies that would inform a “scientific” approach to science policy) into the research assessment language used more broadly by researchers to discuss and critique the bibliometric measures by which their work was being judged.²⁵²

While the policy arena was increasingly framing science in terms of measurable returns, the research landscape was undergoing a transformation of its own. The scientometrics community, which had begun to take shape during the Science Indicators era, matured during the 1990s into a recognized scholarly field. This evolution was supported on the one hand by increasingly available data upon which scientometricians could base their research. On the other hand, it also found an expanded publishing home in new journals such as *Research Evaluation* and the *Journal of Informetrics*.²⁵³ The Science Citation Index (SCI), originally published in analog form in the 1960s and 1970s as raw data for researchers and administrators to perform their own calculations, was by this time reconstituted as a digital, commercial product. Citation indexes became packaged platforms that offered pre-computed indicators – impact factors, citation counts, journal rankings – integrated into the infrastructures of major publishers.

This development paralleled the digitization of scholarly communication more broadly. Throughout the course of the Science of Science period, scholarly journals became integrated into and offered as part of larger packages sold by publishers via increasingly multifunctional

²⁵² Julia Lane, “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific,” *Nature* 464, no. 7288 (2010): 7288, <https://doi.org/10.1038/464488a>.

²⁵³ Oxford Academic, “Research Evaluation,” OUP Academic, Oxford University Press, accessed February 27, 2026, <https://academic.oup.com/rev/rev>; “All Journal Issues,” *Journal of Informetrics*, Elsevier, accessed February 27, 2026, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-informetrics/issues>.

platforms. Large commercial publishing houses consolidated titles into networked, searchable portals, layering persistent identifiers, reference linking, and full-text services with dashboards for institutional management.²⁵⁴ Citation data and other bibliometrics became embedded in these platforms, sold as proprietary, pre-computed indicators, bundled with content licenses or sold as add-on products, and marketed to libraries, administrators, and research managers as tools for research assessment.²⁵⁵ Amid this evolution, researchers gained new interactive capabilities – to comment on articles online, to propose reforms to peer review, and to experiment with alternative forms of publication and recognition, but also increasingly found themselves subject to assessment through black-boxed indicators produced by publishers and sold to universities as easily-deployed and ostensibly objective performance indicators.

The most dominant of these metrics was the journal impact factor (JIF), a calculation originally generated by Eugene Garfield’s Institute for Scientific Information. JIF is now a figure generated by Clarivate (ISI’s successor), calculating the number of times the “average article” in a particular journal is cited over a given period of time (usually two years).²⁵⁶ Over the course of the 1990s and into the early 2000’s, the JIF became quite an influential number, becoming synonymous with journal prestige and perhaps inevitably also coming under considerable scrutiny by the research – and specifically, by the scientometrics – community.²⁵⁷ Throughout this period, multiple new approaches were explored, many of which sought to address the recognized

²⁵⁴ Christine L. Borgman, “Disciplines, Documents and Data,” in *Scholarship in the Digital Age: Information, Infrastructure, and the Internet* (2007), 181, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/7434.001.0001>.

²⁵⁵ Hans Radder, “The Commodification of Academic Research,” in *The Commodification of Academic Research: Science and the Modern University*, ed. Hans Radder (University of Pittsburgh Press, 2010), 7, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/j.ctt7zw87p>.

²⁵⁶ Clarivate, “The Clarivate Impact Factor,” Clarivate, accessed January 5, 2025, <https://clarivate.com/academia-government/essays/impact-factor/>.

²⁵⁷ Carl Bergstrom, *Eigenfactor: Measuring the Value and Prestige of Scholarly Journals* | Bergstrom | *College & Research Libraries News*, April 10, 2017, <https://doi-org.pitt.idm.oclc.org/10.5860/crln.68.5.7804>.

limitation of the JIF. Primary among these is the fact that the JIF treats all citations equally, whereas in reality, researchers regularly cite others' work critically, as well as in editorial and other pieces that might be indexed but are not peer reviewed.²⁵⁸

Another common criticism of the JIF pertains to its use – it has been used to assess the performance and contribution of individual researchers while it was designed as a means of evaluating journals. In 2005, Jorge Hirsch introduced the h-index as an alternative to the JIF. It was intentionally designed to measure the impact of the work of individual authors, offering a means of departing from the use of the JIF as a proxy indicator for the same. While offered as a response to the many criticisms levied against the JIF, the h-index suffered a similar fate as the JIF, coming under heavy criticism for its observed inconsistency and distorting effects on researcher behavior.²⁵⁹ Nevertheless, it quickly became a dominant measure of academic performance, incorporated into the by-then complex platforms sold by publishers to academic libraries.

Over subsequent decades, citation-based evaluation became increasingly technically sophisticated, incorporating field normalization, composite indicators such as the h-index, and prestige-weighted algorithms. These refinements sought to address known limitations of raw citation counts, though they retained the underlying assumption that citation behavior could serve as a proxy for scholarly influence.

²⁵⁸ Seglen, "Why the Impact Factor of Journals Should Not Be Used for Evaluating Research," 499.

²⁵⁹ Ludo Waltman and Nees Van Eck, "The Inconsistency of the H-index," *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 63, no. 2 (2012): Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, <https://doi-org.pitt.idm.oclc.org/10.1002/asi.21678>; Michael Fire and Carlos Guestrin, "Over-Optimization of Academic Publishing Metrics: Observing Goodhart's Law in Action," *GigaScience* 8, no. 6 (2019): giz053, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giz053>.

As a pair, the policy-level efforts to build a science of science policy and the academic debates over citation-based metrics reflect a shared engagement with the means by which research is measured and governed. A notable proliferation of quantitative indicators, coupled with a concurrent and growing concern over their consequences, is also clear. This therefore emerges as a moment defined by interaction between mechanisms of research assessment and the people who use, develop, and are affected by them. The remainder of this chapter examines these dynamics through the three intersecting themes of control, quality, and value.

5.2 Control

Control remains a guiding concern throughout the Science of Science period, however rather than being exercised through definition and categorization, here it is constructed through infrastructure and contested through direct intervention. The former is the work of federal policymakers, who during the early 2000s sought to construct a cohesive scaffolding – technical, methodological, and social – that would support the strategic capture and analysis of data curated to inform science policy decision-making. The latter occurred across the research ecosystem via a series of initially grassroots efforts to engineer alternatives to the increasingly commodified indicators – now called “metrics” – that were used to assess their performance and, often, determine the course of their careers.

The policy angle here is overt, clearly articulated throughout John Marburger’s AAAS keynote address, in which he delivers an explicit call for a “science of science policy” supported by an infrastructure of indicators, methodologies, and experts all cultivated to produce actionable

policy-ready data describing the status of the scientific enterprise in the U.S. In this call, Marburger offers praise for what had become the successor to the *Science Indicators* reports of the 1970s – rebranded by then as NSF’s *Science and Engineering Indicators* series – but identifies its infrastructural limitations as a serious barrier to effective policymaking. While commending the narrative volume as “an objective, high quality document full of excellent insights,” he also notes that “the indicators are based on a data taxonomy that is nearly three decades old” and that the “methods for defining data in both public and private sectors are not well adapted to how R&D is actually conducted today.”²⁶⁰ He cites the lack of an interpretive framework, inadequate classifications, and outdated data structures as key impediments to using the indicators for policy insight. Asserting that the growing importance of R&D specifically demanded more than incremental improvements, he declares, “I am suggesting that the nascent field of the social science of science policy needs to grow up, and quickly, to provide a basis for understanding the enormously complex dynamic of today's global, technology-based society.”²⁶¹

In response to this challenge, a series of initiatives emerged that sought to build both the conceptual models and the infrastructure needed to better inform science policy decisions. An Interagency Task Group (ITG) convened by the NSTC – a science and technology body advising the President – was charged with developing a federal roadmap for this purpose, determining in 2008 that while disciplinary norms remained dominant and valuable across scientific and agency communities, “the collection and analysis of data about the science and scientific communities they support is heterogeneous and unsystematic.”²⁶² Their concluding recommendations mirrored

²⁶⁰ Marburger, III, “2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum Keynote Address,” 6.

²⁶¹ Marburger, III, “2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum Keynote Address,” 7.

²⁶² Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 1–2.

Marburger's, including guidance made directly to federal funding agencies to "work in concert to establish a theoretical and empirical framework to understand the science and engineering enterprise within the context of the science of science policy", to fund relevant methodological innovation, and to build tools for evaluating the structure, process, and returns of the research enterprise.²⁶³ These efforts reflected a growing consensus that the foundational concepts and infrastructures for research assessment needed to be reimagined and more intentionally engineered.

The STAR METRICS initiative proposes a solution to the ITG's call. Conceived as a joint effort by NIH, NSF, and OSTP in the wake of the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA), STAR METRICS was designed to improve accountability for stimulus funding by tracking the outcomes of the federally funded research it supported. The explicit goal of STAR METRICS was to connect grant investment to research outcomes – to demonstrate how public investment in research translated into scientific, social, and economic outcomes.²⁶⁴ Doing so, however, demanded the development of a new and interconnected technical infrastructure capable of supporting the kinds of connections policymakers hoped to make. At the heart of STAR METRICS was an attempt to trace funding through a series of discrete but connected entities – from grants to institutions, to individual researchers, to research outputs such as publications, patents, and datasets (see Figure 6). To accomplish this, the initiative had to address and contend with the absence of standardized, interoperable identifiers at each of these nodes. At the time,

²⁶³ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 2.

²⁶⁴ Julia Lane, "The Science of Science & Innovation Policy Program," Seminar on the Science of Science and Innovation Policy, February 13, 2011, 18, <https://web.archive.org/web/20120301112106/http://scienceofsciencepolicy.net:80/publication/scisip-program-science-science-policy-and-star-metrics-presentation-julia-lane>.

funding identifiers most often came in the form of ad hoc, alphanumeric strings that were unique to individual agencies or institutions, but lacked the interoperability, persistence, or actionability understood to define identifiers today.²⁶⁵ Identifiers for people were similarly underdeveloped – ORCID had not yet been launched, and existing systems for disambiguating researcher identities were either limited or proprietary. Even where relatively mature identifiers existed (such as DOIs for journal articles), their use was generally restricted to traditional scholarly publications, with uptake still quite limited across other research outputs such as datasets, software, and grey literature.

To address these limitations, STAR METRICS launched a pilot phase that engaged six universities in efforts to extract structured administrative data from existing reporting systems.²⁶⁶ The idea was to begin with what institutions already collected, such as payroll and grant records, and use that data as the foundation for building interoperable linkages between funding inputs and research outputs. The resulting system was intended to document research activity while also operationalizing the very terms of evaluation – terms such as productivity, impact, and return, for example – within a framework envisioned to scale across agencies and institutions. The project's ambition thus lay in producing better data while simultaneously constructing a system that would render research activity calculable and, by extension, accountable to federal goals.

The challenges that STAR METRICS set out to address were symptomatic of a larger problem identified by both the ITG and Marburger himself – the absence of a coherent empirical

²⁶⁵ Network of the National Library of Medicine, “Persistent Unique Identifier,” NNLM, accessed July 27, 2025, <https://www.nlm.gov/guides/data-glossary/persistent-unique-identifier>.

²⁶⁶ Federal Demonstration Partnership, “STAR METRICS Science and Technology in America’s Reinvestment Measuring the Effect of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science,” Federal Demonstration Partnership, April 5, 2010, https://web.archive.org/web/20100405073845/http://nrc59.nas.edu/star_info2.cfm.

foundation for science policy. This was the primary frustration raised by Marburger in his 2005 AAAS address. In that address, he also centered a need to create a community of practice dedicated to the resolution of such challenges – a call that was met by NSF in the creation of the Science of Science and Innovation Policy (SciSIP) program within the Directorate for the Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences (SBE). Julia Lane succeeded Kay Husbands-Fealing as the director of the program in 2008, thereby assuming the responsibility of engaging and cultivating this community.

Figure 6: A diagram illustrating the design of STAR METRICS data streams²⁶⁷

²⁶⁷ Lane et al., “STAR METRICS: Science and Technology for America’s Reinvestment: Measuring the Effects of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science,” 7.

For years prior to Marburger’s call and Lane’s subsequent enlistment as a foot soldier in the charge, the research community had been sounding the alarm about flaws in the research assessment regimes that were being used to evaluate their work. Among these concerns, particularly in the moment of the Science of Science period, was an increasing entrenchment of research assessment within the opaque, proprietary, and automated systems sold by publishers to academic libraries – systems that institutionalized citation-based metrics while ultimately distancing the research community from the ability to understand or contest how those metrics were created. As citation-based metrics like the journal impact factor and the h-index became institutionalized, they became products to be consumed rather than numbers that, through access to raw data such as those made available by ISI in the 1970s, could be calculated independently.

In a 2010 paper, Loet Leydesdorff and Tobias Opthof criticize one such metric – SNIP, or “Source Normalized Impact per Paper” – for its methodological opacity, pointing to its implementation within Scopus as a barrier to scrutiny and reproducibility. “[A] number of normalization decisions are involved,” they explain, “which makes it impossible to test for significance.”²⁶⁸ Four years prior, Eugene Garfield, in reflecting on the evolution of the JIF, similarly highlights its embedded assumptions as one of the measure’s primary weaknesses, noting that “[t]he heuristic methods used by Thomson Scientific (formerly Thomson ISI) for categorizing journals are by no means perfect”.²⁶⁹ An unremarkable aside at first glance, this passage suggests an acknowledgement of the implications of selling assumption-based products rather than allowing

²⁶⁸ Loet Leydesdorff and Tobias Opthof, “Scopus’s Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP) versus a Journal Impact Factor Based on Fractional Counting of Citations,” *Journal of the American Society for Information Science & Technology* 61, no. 11 (2010): 2365, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21371>.

²⁶⁹ Eugene Garfield, “The History and Meaning of the Journal Impact Factor,” *JAMA* 295, no. 1 (2006): 92, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.1.90>.

researchers to derive measures through interaction with raw data and, importantly, through human judgement. With it, Garfield perhaps unintentionally signals a distance between the decisions made by the Thomson Scientific team in honing their product, and the end user of the product itself, illustrating the “black boxing” of evaluative metrics that ultimately served to remove researchers from the metrics used to assess their work.²⁷⁰

Simultaneous to and sometimes in direct response to such critiques about metrics’ opacity and other recognized weaknesses, scientometricians and others made multiple efforts to adapt existing metrics and recommend new ones. These recommendations were generally made with researchers in mind, centering their norms and interests over the inertia of the entrenched nature of the JIF and h-index. Indeed, the h-index itself was developed in effort to center researchers rather than journals in the design of evaluative metrics. “For the few scientists who earn a Nobel prize, the impact and relevance of their research is unquestionable. Among the rest of us, how does one quantify the cumulative impact and relevance of an individual’s scientific research output?”²⁷¹ This is the question that Hirsch uses to introduce his h-index in 2005, centering the individual in his proposed metric from the very outset.

Likewise, Zitt and Small propose a reorientation of citation analysis that centers the audience rather than the venue in its calculation. By weighting citations according to practices in the citing journal rather than the cited journal, they argue that the perspectives of readers offer a more meaningful benchmark.²⁷² Similarly, Ludo Waltman and his colleagues at the Centre for

²⁷⁰ Garfield, “The History and Meaning of the Journal Impact Factor,” 92.

²⁷¹ J. E. Hirsch, “An Index to Quantify an Individual’s Scientific Research Output,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 102, no. 46 (2005): 16569.

²⁷² Michel Zitt and Henry Small, “Modifying the Journal Impact Factor by Fractional Citation Weighting: The Audience Factor,” *Journal of the American Society for Information Science & Technology* 59, no. 11 (2008): 1856–60, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20880>.

Science and Technology Studies at Leiden University refined the then well-known Crown Indicator by extending its normalization parameters, recommending adjustments that more accurately reflect citation behavior across disciplinary subcultures. In closing, they acknowledge that "like any bibliometric indicator of research performance, the... [Crown] indicator has its limitations and is in general not suitable to be used in isolation. Instead," they recommend, the "indicator should be used in a complementary fashion with other indicators, and the focus should be on the overall picture that emerges from the various indicators".²⁷³

This recognition of multiplicity shaped broader efforts to account for the many ways research impact can manifest. Wolfgang Glänzel advances this argument over the course of several years, first in a coauthored paper with Henk Moed in which the two authors conclude that "methodological improvements in combination with additional, multi-dimensional measures and appropriate methodological and technological documentation may help to overcome limitations of" measures such as the JIF.²⁷⁴ Years later, in an article titled "The Multi-Dimensionality of Journal Impact", he elaborates on this idea, noting that simply expanding to a two-factor consideration of impact more "appropriately reflects [the] main characteristics" of a journal's impact.²⁷⁵ The benefit of this, he argues, is that in addition to resulting in greater validity, it also renders results more "comprehensible and intelligible" to the end user.²⁷⁶ Such efforts reflect a

²⁷³ Ludo Waltman et al., "Towards a New Crown Indicator: Some Theoretical Considerations," *Journal of Informetrics* 5, no. 1 (2011): 13, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2010.08.001>.

²⁷⁴ Wolfgang Glänzel and Henk F. Moed, "Journal Impact Measures in Bibliometric Research," *Scientometrics* 53, no. 2 (2002): 191, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014848323806>.

²⁷⁵ Wolfgang Glänzel, "The Multi-Dimensionality of Journal Impact," *Scientometrics* 78, no. 2 (2009): 355, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-008-2166-9>.

²⁷⁶ Glänzel, "The Multi-Dimensionality of Journal Impact," 355.

clear throughline: the development of measures that describe research more faithfully while also granting users greater interpretive control.

A subtler shift evident throughout the period can be observed the pursuit of control throughout the Science of Science period. Rather than taking form as an active power struggle, here it is contested more as a struggle for rationalization and intellectual control. Policy- and lawmakers are concerned with corralling indicators into “rational” systems where they can be tracked, quantified, and compared. Meanwhile, researchers are increasingly – and more vociferously – concerned with gaining intellectual control over what indicators actually indicate, and regaining control over the metrics that are used to assess their work. It is in researchers’ critiques that discussions of quality similarly shift and take new form. The subsequent section details findings related to this second analytical theme framing this research.

5.3 Quality

Quality is a persistent undercurrent throughout the Science of Science Policy period, but does not emerge from the literature as an explicit target of policy intervention. Federal efforts during this period largely sought to develop quantitative tools for assessing the value and performance of research, with little direct attention paid to how such tools might advance the substantive quality of science itself. For the research community, however, quality is a central concern, expressed across a significant body of literature decrying the behavioral effects that researchers felt were arising from an overreliance on quantitative indicators – effects they believed to undermine the production of rigorous, original, and meaningful work.

This tension is illustrated in the 2008 NSTC Interagency Task Group’s *Science of Science Policy Roadmap*, a 50-page report that documents the findings of the ITG and details a series of ten guiding questions meant to focus the efforts of funding agencies as they sought to develop supports for the nascent SoSP community. The ITG was tasked with conducting a thorough review of the state of science policy in the U.S., and identifying the primary blockers and opportunities faced in cultivating a dedicated science of science policy approach. After conducting a literature review and survey of federal agencies, the ITG offer the primary conclusion that:

“Expert judgment” remains the best available decision support tool for science policy makers, but a nascent community of practice is emerging in the science policy arena that holds enormous potential to provide rigorous and quantitative decision support tools in the near future. Support and development of this emerging community of practice can provide the Federal government with these much-needed decision tools.²⁷⁷

The ITG offers four next steps recommended to federal agencies, one of which pertains specifically to measurement tools and methodologies: “Encourage investment in the development and use of emerging tools, methods, data, and data infrastructure to enable science policy decision makers to base investment decisions on more rigorous and quantitative analyses.”²⁷⁸ While acknowledging the indispensable and traditional role of judgement in the assessment of science, the ITG centers “quantitative decision support tools” as being of critical importance – a seeming paradox that can be understood through an examination of the ITG’s founding goal. The group was convened to advance the mission of the science of science policy effort – one that was itself characterized by an effort to hone the infrastructure through which innovation could be captured

²⁷⁷ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 1.

²⁷⁸ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 2.

and cultivated. The goal was not the advancement of science, but, more specifically, the advancement of its economic outcomes.

To the contrary, when considering the literature on research assessment that emerged from the research community during this time, one of the most consistent lines of argumentation regards the negative effects of metrics-based assessment on the quality of the research process, its outputs and supporting ecosystem. Here, commentators and critics point to a distortion of research behavior that is believed to be motivated by the “perverse” incentives generated by a system that relies on standardized, quantitative measures of complex characteristics that are most often qualitative in nature. These behavioral effects are noted in changes in journal selection as well as in observed gaming and metric manipulation – phenomena that, in sum, can undermine not only metric validity but also the quality and integrity of the research enterprise itself.

In an article bluntly titled “Why the Impact Factor of Journals Should Not Be Used for Evaluating Research,” Per O. Seglen notes that the effects that journal-based impact factors had on the incentive structures guiding researcher behavior were affecting journal choice, with authors regularly choosing to publish in high-impact journals “often at the expense of specialist journals that might actually be more appropriate vehicles for the research in question.”²⁷⁹ After detailing a related argument that article impact affects journal impact “and not vice versa,” he asks a pointed question: “If scientific authors are not detectably rewarded with a higher impact by publishing in high impact journals, why are we so adamant on doing it? The answer, of course, is that as long as

²⁷⁹ Seglen, “Why the Impact Factor of Journals Should Not Be Used for Evaluating Research,” 498.

there are people out there who judge our science by its wrapping rather than by its contents, we cannot afford to take any chances.”²⁸⁰

The concern raised by Seglen is reiterated throughout the SoS literature and illustrated in real-life terms by the lament of Jose I. Saiz-Salinas, published in a letter to the editor of *Nature* a year earlier:

I am a graduate zoologist, doctor and university professor who was failed by [the Spanish] National Committee which, it seems, takes account only of the SCI ratings. It is ironic never to have failed an examination as an undergraduate, to have been awarded a doctorate in zoology and to have obtained a professorship and then to have been failed by a National Committee. Despite a research track record judged by editorial boards, granting agencies and international colleagues to have been active and productive, I was graded 4 on a scale of 10. There is considerable room for improvement in the way the system operates.²⁸¹

Earlier in his letter, Saiz-Salinas observes that “[n]obody doing research in Spain at the beginning of the 1980s could foresee that a list of journals compiled by the SCI was going to determine whether one's research was 'valid' or not.”²⁸² His frustration captures a sentiment that echoed across the academic literature at the time – by the late 1990s, quantitative, metrics-driven research assessment had become standard, premising one’s professional advancement and the estimation of the quality of their research on the journals they published in and on the citations they accrued.

As early as 1990, researchers raised concerns about the extent and limitations of metrics-based research assessment as well as about the effects of this kind of assessment on research behavior. Such concerns motivated a study by Hargens and Schuman, inspiring the pair of

²⁸⁰ Seglen, “Why the Impact Factor of Journals Should Not Be Used for Evaluating Research,” 501.

²⁸¹ Jose I. Saiz-Salinas, “Failed Professor,” *Nature* 381, no. 6579 (1996): 186, <https://doi.org/10.1038/381186a0>.

²⁸² Saiz-Salinas, “Failed Professor,” 186.

sociologists to conduct an inquiry into the motivations behind researchers’ “use and evaluation of citation index data”.²⁸³ In an article sharing the results of the study, they open by noting that across academic circles, “the widespread use of publication counts as a basis for promotion decisions is sometimes blamed for a deluge of trivial publications.”²⁸⁴ Other concerns about impact factors’ potential affect on author behavior surround self-citation and other practices, such as Henk Moed’s observation that practices such as citing both the English and non-English versions of the same paper might result in artificially inflated citation counts.²⁸⁵ Here, Seglen is careful to not attribute intent in his observations about such practices. Eugene Garfield is not so delicate. “After all,” he notes, “some highly published authors are little more than bureaucrats who attach their names to every paper they can.”²⁸⁶

Beyond individual metric gaming, a more systemic concern raised by authors during the time is the strategic selection of research topics – a practice that many commentators regard as particularly problematic, in that it skews the focus and direction of the research enterprise itself. Richard Monastersky, writing for *The Chronicle of Higher Education* in a piece titled “The Number That’s Devouring Science,” reports a sense that in response to pressures placed on them by metrics-driven assessment, “[i]nvestigators are now more likely to chase after fashionable topics – the kind that get into high-impact journals – than to follow important avenues that may

²⁸³ Lowell L. Hargens and Howard Schuman, “Citation Counts and Social Comparisons: Scientists’ Use and Evaluation of Citation Index Data,” *Social Science Research* 19, no. 3 (1990): 205–21, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0049-089X\(90\)90006-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0049-089X(90)90006-5).

²⁸⁴ Hargens and Schuman, “Citation Counts and Social Comparisons,” 205.

²⁸⁵ H. F. Moed et al., “A Critical Analysis of the Journal Impact Factors of *Angewandte Chemie* and the *Journal of the American Chemical Society* Inaccuracies in Published Impact Factors Based on Overall Citations Only,” *Scientometrics* 37, no. 1 (1996): 106, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02093487>.

²⁸⁶ Eugene Garfield, *From Citation Indexes to Informetrics: Is the Tail Now Wagging the Dog?*, *Libri*, 48, no. 2 (1998): 73, <https://doi.org/10.1515/libr.1998.48.2.67>.

not be the flavor of the year”.²⁸⁷ In an article titled “Is the Impact of Journal Impact Factors Decreasing?” Jan Reedijk and Henk Moed set out to characterize the behavioral effects of metrics-driven research assessment on the research ecosystem, ultimately concluding that these effects were having an effect of their own, degrading the integrity of the research ecosystem and of the impact factors themselves. Their analysis suggests that behavioral adaptations on the part of authors and editors – adaptations that include mandatory journal self-citation (in which journal editors require that authors cite sources within the publishing journal), manipulations of what are considered “citable” and “non-citable” manuscripts, and publishing both research articles and “buzzworthy” editorials at strategic moments within the calendar year – reduced the substantive contribution of both articles and their publishing journals, simultaneously diminishing the impact of impact factors due to the fact that, as a result of gaming and manipulation, the measures had in effect come to indicate winners of a game rather than superior work.²⁸⁸

5.4 Value

It is value that emerges as the central preoccupation of the Science of Science period. At the federal level in particular, the entire enterprise advocated by John Marburger, recommended by the ITG, and marketed by Julia Lane rests on the presumption that the value of research can

²⁸⁷ Richard Monastersky, “The Number That’s Devouring Science,” *The Chronicle of Higher Education* 52, no. 8 (2005), [https://advance-lexis-com.pitt.idm.oclc.org/api/document?collection=news&id=urn%3acontentItem%3a4HCB-Y8K0-010P-J076-00000-00&context=1519360&identityprofileid=7B6RR551949](https://advance.lexis-com.pitt.idm.oclc.org/api/document?collection=news&id=urn%3acontentItem%3a4HCB-Y8K0-010P-J076-00000-00&context=1519360&identityprofileid=7B6RR551949).

²⁸⁸ Jan Reedijk and Henk F. Moed, “Is the Impact of Journal Impact Factors Decreasing?,” *Journal of Documentation* 64, no. 2 (2008): 183–92, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410810858001>.

and should be quantified. Specifically, Marburger’s call for a science of science policy is premised on the idea that demonstrating measurable returns on investment is both possible and necessary, and that new infrastructures are required to support this pursuit. American competitiveness serves as the operative shorthand for value in this context, invoked via innovation as the ultimate outcome of federal research funding and the return most desired from public expenditure. The research community is called upon to provide the data, methodologies, and supporting infrastructure needed to showcase American competitiveness in a “scientific” manner – one that can be framed as both rigorous and transparent. Meanwhile, across the scientometric community, quantifiable metrics are also a driving concern, however in this context value is discussed in terms of “impact”. The discussion centers less on what that term means than on how it too can – and should – be demonstrated.

In his 2005 keynote to the AAAS Science and Technology Policy Forum, Marburger made the explicit case that the value of science should be measured in economic terms. Bemoaning the “primitive framework” then available to policymakers seeking to link research spending to national performance indicators such as the gross domestic product, he states outright that he believes science policy to be “to a great extent a branch of economics,” requiring a foundation of dedicated tools, models, and academic research. A single quote neatly summarizes his position: “[m]uch of the available literature on science policy is being produced piecemeal by scientists who are experts in their fields, but not necessarily in the methods and literature of the relevant social science disciplines needed to define appropriate data elements and create econometric models that

can be useful to policy experts.”²⁸⁹ Science policy, then, should be informed by social scientists specifically trained to support the policy community.

Throughout the SoS period, federal discourse on the value of science revolves around competitiveness, rigor, and transparency, with competition providing one of the clearest through-lines between presidential and agency priorities. In perhaps his most public-facing arguments advancing the SoSP initiative, John Marburger writes in *Science* about the need for “better benchmarks” to measure the outcomes of federal research investment, centering at the core of his argument an anecdote illustrating his frustration at the inability of the policy community to produce something as seemingly straightforward as comparative data on graduate degree completions between PhD students in the United States, China, and India.²⁹⁰ A year later, in a 2006 memorandum to agency heads outlining FY 2008 research and development priorities, he highlights the administration’s commitment to double investment in NSF, DOE’s Office of Science, and NIST core activities over ten years, explicitly tying this doubling to “potentially high impact on economic competitiveness.”²⁹¹ The same memo makes clear that competitiveness is bound to the SoSP agenda itself, noting that

[d]etermining the effectiveness of Federal science policy requires an understanding of the complex linkages between R&D investments and economic and other variables that lead to innovation, competitiveness, and societal benefits. An interagency process has been established and is now encouraged to promote and coordinate individual agency and collaborative actions needed to develop [a] ‘new science of science policy’.²⁹²

²⁸⁹ Marburger, III, “2005 AAAS S&T Policy Forum Keynote Address,” 7.

²⁹⁰ John H. Marburger, “Wanted: Better Benchmarks,” *Science* 308, no. 5725 (2005): 1087, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3842062>.

²⁹¹ John H. Marburger, III and Rob Portman, “FY 2008 Administration Research and Development Budget Priorities,” June 23, 2006, 1, https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/legacy_drupal_files/omb/memoranda/2006/m06-17.pdf.

²⁹² Marburger, III and Portman, “FY 2008 Administration Research and Development Budget Priorities,” 3.

Across federal resources from the time, competitiveness and innovation are often discussed hand-in-hand. This linkage is evident across presidential and policy initiatives as well as in in flagship measurement projects such as STAR METRICS, which enshrines the idea that innovation is the bridge between science and competitiveness in its full title: *Science and Technology for America's Reinvestment: Measuring the Effect of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science*. Despite this nominal scoping, documentation of the program reviewed in this analysis did not provide a clear articulation of innovation or its causal relationship with competitiveness. The project's first phase focused on tracking jobs created under ARRA, while its second turned to patents, publications, workforce outcomes, and longer-term benefits such as health and environmental impacts.²⁹³

While presumably innovation could be tracked through patent metrics, no methodology explaining STAR METRICS' metrics was found – a notable finding given Marburger's priorities and expressed frustrations throughout the period. At the same moment that he calls for better models to understand the processes underlying innovation, federal policy – much of it written to advance his policy priorities – routinely frames it as an unquestioned gateway to competitive advantage. The Bush administration's *American Competitiveness Initiative* (ACI), for example, presents innovation as the critical enabler of U.S. economic leadership. The ACI report, issued by OSTP's Domestic Policy Council in 2006, emphasizes that “sustained scientific advancement and innovation are key to maintaining our competitive edge,” casting federal R&D investments,

²⁹³ Office of Science and Technology Policy, “STAR METRICS: New Way to Measure the Impact of Federally Funded Research,” 2.

education reforms, and tax incentives as the means of securing that position.²⁹⁴ The logic is straightforward but largely unexamined – competitiveness depends on innovation, and innovation depends on science and technology. No justification of this chain of reasoning was found – instead, innovation appears to be positioned as a catchall, simultaneously the presumed outcome of federal research investment and the ultimate goal that legitimizes it.

Alongside the emphasis on competitiveness and innovation is also a pronounced push for greater rigor in federal decision-making. Indeed, a guiding assumption that appears to motivate Marburger and other policymakers at the time is that science policy must itself become more “scientific.” Julia Lane, one of the most visible advocates of the initiative, pitches the effort to the research community in precisely these terms through an editorial in *Nature* titled “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific.”²⁹⁵ In doing so, she links the science of science policy to research assessment, drawing on the longstanding frustration among scientists with bibliometric measures such as journal impact factors. “The dangers of poor metrics are well known – and science should learn lessons from the experiences of other fields, such as business. The management literature is rich in sad examples of rewards tied to ill-conceived measures, resulting in perverse outcomes.... There is enormous potential to do better: to build a science of science measurement.”²⁹⁶ The Interagency Roadmap for the Science of Science Policy initiative makes a similar case, declaring at the outset that “[t]he science of science policy (SoSP) is an emerging field of interdisciplinary research, the goal of which is to provide a scientifically rigorous, quantitative basis from which

²⁹⁴ White House Office of Science and Technology Policy Domestic Policy Council, *American Competitiveness Initiative: Leading the World in Innovation* (2006), 1, <https://georgewebush-whitehouse.archives.gov/stateoftheunion/2006/aci/index.html>.

²⁹⁵ Lane, “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific.”

²⁹⁶ Lane, “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific,” 488.

policy makers and researchers can assess the impacts of the Nation’s scientific and engineering enterprise, improve their understanding of its dynamics, and assess the likely outcomes.”²⁹⁷ The

Roadmap is blunt about current deficiencies:

Although the importance of public investments in science, technology, and innovation is understood, the rationale for specific scientific investment decisions lacks a strong theoretical and empirical basis. Accordingly... science policy decision makers must have at their disposal the most rigorous tools, methods and data that will enable them to develop sound and cost-effective investment strategies.²⁹⁸

In such passages, rigor is framed as an intellectual and practical imperative assigned to the federal government as well as to the research community. It is notable that Julia Lane addresses her call to researchers leveraging their complaints as justification, for at the time she was also tasked, via her role as program manager of NSF’s SciSIP initiative, with cultivating the community of practice identified in the Roadmap as being critical to the advancement of SoSP aims.

If rigor is cast as a responsibility shared across the research community, transparency extends that responsibility outward, framing accountability an internal matter of scholarly standards as well as a public obligation to demonstrate how federal investments in science yield tangible returns. In federal discourse, this outward-facing responsibility takes shape through calls for transparency, driven by congressional oversight, executive budget pressures, and the fiscal and political climate of the late 2000s. NSF director Arden Bement, reflecting on the creation of STAR METRICS, explains: “[t]here has been a high demand for these types of data. Members of Congress are always asking the question [about returns on investment], and it’s important that we

²⁹⁷ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 1.

²⁹⁸ Subcommittee on Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Committee on Science, *The Science of Science Policy*, 1.

satisfy that question to the best of our ability.”²⁹⁹ Julia Lane adds that OMB “is pushing pretty hard” for agencies to provide better measures of their performance, emphasizing the pressure put on funders to generate demonstrable evidence of returns on the public’s investment. Such pressures intensified in the wake of the 2008 financial crisis and the subsequent passage of the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act, which channeled over \$300 billion into federally funded research.³⁰⁰

It was in this environment that Lane pitched the STAR METRICS initiative, embedding emphases on accountability and transparency in her calls for a more cohesive research assessment infrastructure. While her more policy-minded colleagues speak in terms of accountability and angle towards the goal of “evidence-driven decision making” to appease Congress, Lane is in the position of serving as a diplomat of sorts, translating policy goals into strategic language to motivate and garner buy-in across the research community. She does so by positioning both STAR METRICS and the transparency that it promised as a way of advancing openness, which here becomes a means through which the scientific community might access, reuse, and perhaps gain some control over the metrics used to assess their work. Her “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific” article demonstrates this clearly. In it, she first sets up the problem – that science metrics are plagued by known and serious limitations, including the fact that they are produced and distributed as the opaque, proprietary products of publishing conglomerates. She then proposes a solution premised on the principles of openness and agency. “Importantly,” she argues, “data

²⁹⁹ Arden Bement quoted in David Kramer, “Initiative Aims to Quantify the Paybacks from Basic Research,” *Physics Today* 63, no. 8 (2010): 20, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3480067>.

³⁰⁰ American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009, H.R.1, U.S. Congress 111th, Pub. L. 111-5 (2009), <https://www.congress.gov/bill/111th-congress/house-bill/1/text>.

collected for use in metrics must be open to the scientific community, so that metric calculations can be reproduced.”³⁰¹

This research highlights three intersecting characteristics within the federal discourse surrounding the value of research: competitiveness, rigor, and transparency. Competitiveness and innovation offer the justification for expanding investments in research, rigor issues a mandate to develop models and indicators that ground decisions scientifically, and transparency positions accountability as both a political necessity and a professional responsibility. Julia Lane’s *Nature* editorial epitomizes this convergence, presenting transparency as an administrative demand and a means of empowerment for the research community. This framing resonates beyond the immediate concerns of the SoSP initiative, nodding to the emerging open science movement through which calls to make data and research outputs openly accessible are tied to ideals of collaboration, reproducibility, and demands for greater control over the systems of evaluation. Lane’s call thus serves as a bridge between policy-driven imperatives to improve the accountability of federal research expenditures and the frustrations of a scientific community wary of being judged by opaque, externally imposed measures.

The scholarly literature of this period reflects a profound ambivalence toward citation-based indicators such as the JIF. Despite widespread concerns about the effects of impact factors on the quality of research and the integrity of the research ecosystem itself, some positive reflections on impact factors also emerge. Some of these include impact factors’ comprehensibility and “fast availability”, perhaps ultimately speaking more to their success as commercial products than as indicators. Many others note their observed accordance with long-standing assumptions

³⁰¹ Lane, “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific,” 488.

across scientific and scholarly communities, particularly pertaining to peer- and other expert judgement as reliable indicators of quality.³⁰² For instance, in 1997 an editorial was published in *Allergy* in which the author argued that the JIF should be retained because it had proven itself to be a reliable measure of the assumptions that are important to the scientific community.

Experience has shown that in each specialty the best journals are those in which it is most difficult to have an article accepted, and these are the journals that have a high impact factor. These journals existed long before the impact factor was devised. The use of the impact factor as a measure of quality is widespread because it fits well with the opinion we have in each field of the best journals in our specialty.³⁰³

The author also argues that the JIF is “a good technique for scientific evaluation” because “there is nothing better, and it has the advantage of already being in existence”.³⁰⁴

While impact factors remained among the most visible and contentious indicators of research value, they were by no means alone. Long before the Science of Science period, scholars had devised informal and often personal means of quantifying their research contributions, forming a kind of folk numeracy within academic life.³⁰⁵ The meaningful development during the SoS period was not so much an impulse to quantify outcomes as it was the formalization and commodification of metrics. The desire to quantify and compete was codified in new indicators, integrated into digital platforms, and marketed as ready-made tools for evaluating research performance.

³⁰² Wolfgang Glänzel and Henk F. Moed, “Journal Impact Measures in Bibliometric Research,” *Scientometrics* 53, no. 2 (2002): 171–93, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014848323806>.

³⁰³ C. Hoeffel, “Journal Impact Factors,” *Allergy* 53, no. 12 (1998): 1225, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1398-9995.1998.tb03848.x>.

³⁰⁴ Hoeffel, “Journal Impact Factors,” 1225.

³⁰⁵ De Bellis, “History and Evolution of (Biblio)Metrics,” 28.

It was in this context that the h-index rose to prominence. By design, it condensed a scholar's entire publication and citation record into a single, easily comparable number. In his 2005 paper introducing the measure, Hirsch presents the h-index as a more balanced measure of productivity and influence than other leading indicators at the time – one that addressed dependence on journal-level proxies by shifting the unit of analysis to the individual. In so doing, however, the fast uptake of the h-index also crystallized and intensified the academic culture of self-measurement, as was observed by Roger Burrows in 2012.

“If the h-index functions to instantiate academic ‘value’ in the individual researcher or research group, then the various metrics that claim to measure the impact that particular academic journals possess provides another mathematical basis for making ever more subtle distinctions within this hierarchy of supposed worth.... So the ability to identify what the ‘top journals’ are is no small matter, not just for academics and the institutions in which they labour, but also for the commercial publishing industry within which journal impact factors often function as a proxy for journal viability and, indeed, profitability.”³⁰⁶

In a chapter contributed to Blaise Cronin and Cassidy Sugimoto's *Beyond Bibliometrics*, Ronald Day extends this argument by framing citation analysis as a system of value exchange. In his view, citation metrics had evolved into “citation economies” – sociotechnical systems in which symbolic capital, in the form of citations, is continuously converted into the social and institutional capital of jobs, funding, prestige, and the like.³⁰⁷ In such an economy, metrics transcend describing the value of research, indeed serving to create it by transforming documents and their authors into exchangeable units within an informational marketplace. Per Day's perspective, citation indices “represent metrics of value – not just metrical values, but social and cultural values,” embodying

³⁰⁶ Roger Burrows, “Living with the H-Index? Metric Assemblages in the Contemporary Academy,” *Sociological Review* 60, no. 2 (2012): 362, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.2012.02077.x>.

³⁰⁷ Ronald E. Day, “‘The Data - It Is Me!’ (‘Les Données—c'est Moi!’),” in *Beyond Bibliometrics: Harnessing Multidimensional Indicators of Scholarly Impact*, ed. Blaise Cronin and Cassidy R. Sugimoto (The MIT Press, 2014), 71, <http://direct.mit.edu/books/book/4039/chapter/167946/Science-Metrics-and-Science-Policy>.

and reproducing the hierarchies of the academic world and encoding what counts as valuable before feeding those assumptions back into systems of recognition and reward.³⁰⁸ This recursive dynamic, Day suggests, constitutes a reorganization of selfhood within academia, wherein the scholar becomes the sum of their measurable traces – a “data-self” whose value is constantly recalculated through citation and visibility metrics. “Where the self was, so the commodity shall be,” he observes, highlighting the shift suggested in the title of his chapter (“The Data – It is Me!”) – an inversion through which data are transformed from serving as representations of scholarly identity to ultimately forming the very substance of it.³⁰⁹

Burrows complements Day’s argument by situating it within an institutional setting where the implications of quantification become more concrete. Whereas Day traces the production of the academic “data-self,” Burrows identifies the environment that sustains it – a regime in which the mechanisms used to measure research value also come to shape and define it.³¹⁰ Within this construct, metrics reflect and enact scholarly worth, translating intellectual contributions into comparable and, increasingly, monetized units.

Whereas once metrics were simply part of an auditing process and, as such, functioned to ensure accountability they have, in more recent times, taken on another role, and now function as part of a process of what has been called ‘quantified control’. In essence academic metric assemblages are at the cusp of being transformed from a set of measures able to mimic market processes to ones that are able to enact market processes. In the neoliberal university world of student fees and ever-greater competition for student numbers and research grant income, these metrics function as a form of measure able to translate different forms of value. Academic value is, essentially, becoming monetized, and as this happens academic values are becoming transformed. This is the source of our discomfort.... we are fully implicated in their enactment.³¹¹

³⁰⁸ Day, “‘The Data - It Is Me!’ (‘Les Données—c’est Moi!’),” 78.

³⁰⁹ Day, “‘The Data - It Is Me!’ (‘Les Données—c’est Moi!’),” 75.

³¹⁰ Burrows, “Living with the H-Index?,” 356.

³¹¹ Burrows, “Living with the H-Index?,” 368.

This observation – that academic value has been commodified and that value is represented through demonstration – offers a useful vantage from which one can understand the operationalization of scientific value across the Science of Science period more broadly. During this period, and across both policy and scholarly contexts, value is articulated through discussions of what science can demonstrate. From a federal perspective, value is expressed through competitiveness, which serves simultaneously as evidence of national supremacy and as justification for public investment. Rigor and transparency, meanwhile, are mobilized to demonstrate that science policy itself is objective, accountable, and trustworthy. Within scholarly discourse, value remains articulated through impact, a concept that is debated with respect to both its validity and its consequences. A central concern raised across the scholarly literature is that attention is displaced from impact itself to its representations, giving rise to citation economies in which metrics circulate as currency and stand in for worth or merit. The discomfort identified by Day, then, reflects a broader discomfort with a rising tendency for the value of science to be progressively repurposed, toward demonstrable returns, legibility, and utility, and away from more intrinsic or tangible benefit.

5.5 Conclusion

The Science of Science period marks another critical turning point in the history of research assessment, building on the technical foundations and policy ambitions of the Science Indicators period and transforming them into an agenda of active ecosystem building. Where the 1970s introduced the idea that science could be described through indicators, the 1990s and 2000s set out

to construct the infrastructures and theories that might make that description actionable, and the system more successfully governed. This period thus saw a shift from representing science to modeling it – from counting the visible outputs of the research enterprise to building tools that could predict and optimize its performance. On the policy side, control was sought in efforts to inform and influence funding and other science policy priorities. Across communities of scholars, the concern relevant to control remained trained on the tools through which their contributions were assessed. Specifically, as it pertained to control, the notable effort rising out of the scholarly community was to regain control of the apparatus of evaluation, fine-tuning metrics and sounding the alarm about unintended consequences.

By the start of the SoS period, the citation databases that had once served as shared raw materials for analysis were subsumed within larger proprietary platforms, embedding already calculated metrics into the architectures of publishing and academic administration. The journal impact factor and the h-index became emblematic of this shift – both having been originally designed as heuristic devices and ultimately evolving into commodified means of performance management that reshaped academic behavior. Amid this expansion of measurement, warnings arose from the scholarly community regarding the unintended and ill effects of this transformation on research integrity and quality.

At the policy level, a similar transformation was underway, crystallized in John Marburger’s call for a “science of science policy.” Frustrated by the absence of coherent data and models for linking research investment to economic and social outcomes, Marburger and his contemporaries advanced a vision of policymaking that was “scientifically” informed by evidence, quantification, and predictive capacity. Characteristics generally understood to be constitutive of “good science” – particularly rigor and transparency – were cultivated through the intentionally

simultaneous creation of technical and social supports that might serve as mutually reinforcing resources in developing the data, models, and expertise needed to “scientifically” inform science policy. Motivated by a need on Marburger’s part to demonstrate the value of science to those paying for it, his science of science policy initiative was marketed to researchers as a way to claim control over the evaluation of their work.

The Science of Science period therefore reveals an intricate entanglement between information, infrastructure, and impact. It institutionalized an argument that science could and should be studied “scientifically”, and it operationalized that argument through the creation of data systems, metrics, and models that continue to influence research assessment today. The primary actors of this period – federal policymakers, economists, scientometricians, and infrastructure providers – were united by a shared aspiration to render the dynamics of science intelligible and governable. However in doing so, they unearthed – and in some cases directly contributed to – the very asymmetries and inaccuracies that would soon provoke reform: the concentration of evaluative authority in proprietary platforms, the reduction of intellectual quality to quantifiable output, and the tenacious gap between what can be quantified and what is most valued.

6.0 Values-Driven Research Assessment

6.1 Introduction

Recent years have given rise to a new period in the evolution of research assessment – one defined by deliberate efforts to align scholarly values with the systems through which research is assessed. Characterized here as the Values-Driven Research Assessment (VDRA) period, and extending from roughly 2012 through 2025, this moment arises in response to the dissatisfaction developing throughout the prior Science Indicators and Science of Science periods. What distinguishes this moment from its immediate predecessor is an observable activist shift, with researchers, policymakers and infrastructure providers working together to intentionally redesign evaluative frameworks such that they are more aligned with asserted values.

This dissertation treats the announcement of the *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)* as the symbolic start of the VDRA period. Drafted by a group of editors and scholars convened at the annual meeting of the American Society for Cell Biology in 2012, DORA turns the critiques of prior periods into actionable terms, calling for institutions, funders, and publishers to eliminate the use of the *journal impact factor* in promotion, review, and tenure (PRT) decisions, calling instead upon constituent communities within the research ecosystem to base research assessment decisions and practices on more contextually responsive criteria.³¹² DORA was the first of many such declarations and manifestos to emerge from the VDRA period, being

³¹² DORA, *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment* (San Francisco, 2013), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25649073>.

quickly followed on by the Leiden Manifesto, and complemented by the more specific altmetrics manifesto, which called for the integration of web-based metrics into research assessment infrastructures and incentives systems, and the Paris Call on Research Assessment, which married demands for research assessment reform with the incentivization of open science practices.³¹³

These grassroots declarations were joined by a pair of groundbreaking memos issued by the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, each drafted to ensure public access to the results of federally funded research. The first, “Increasing Access to the Results of Federally Funded Scientific Research” was drafted during John Holdren’s term as OSTP director and was thus known colloquially as “the Holdren Memo.” Issued in 2013, the Memo requires every federal agency with more than \$100 million in annual research expenditures to make publications and “digital data” resulting from federally funded research publicly available through open access repositories or publishing mechanisms.³¹⁴ The Memo allowed for a 12-month embargo period, and attached a tertiary requirement mandating that publications and datasets falling under its purview be shared with supporting metadata. The second OSTP Memo, known formally as “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research” and informally as “the Nelson Memo” (nodding to then-OSTP director Alondra Nelson), was issued nine years later, eliminating the embargo period and adding to the metadata requirements a mandate to include identifiers for every component of the research process (including funders, awards, authors, and outputs).³¹⁵

³¹³ Jason Priem et al., “Altmetrics: A Manifesto,” *Altmetrics*, October 26, 2011, <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>; Paris Open Science European Conference, *Paris Call – OSEC 2022*.

³¹⁴ John P. Holdren, “Increasing Access to the Results of Federally Funded Scientific Research,” White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, February 22, 2013, https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/ostp_public_access_memo_2013.pdf.

³¹⁵ Alondra Nelson, “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research,” White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, August 25, 2022, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo.pdf>.

As a pair, these memos formalize the aspirations shared by John Marburger and Julia Lane during the Science of Science period in the years prior, mandating critical components of the technical architecture needed to create the data-driven connections called for by Marburger and extend the infrastructure piloted by STAR METRICS. They do so while also couching their respective mandates in the moralized language that has become typical of the open science movement. The open science movement grew out of prior efforts to “open” science to access by members of the general public. Founded in a frustration with the skyrocketing costs of academic journal subscriptions, and by the seeming inequity of locking often publicly funded research behind private paywalls, activists across the scholarly community – and often led by academic librarians – engaged in a sustained effort to change institutional and, ultimately, publisher policies to allow for free and open access to scholarly publications.³¹⁶ By the time of the values-driven research assessment period, the effort had evolved to become a larger “open science” movement promising an enticing array of benefits. Among them is a means of enabling greater reproducibility, in response to “the reproducibility crisis” observed by some to be affecting psychology and other fields.³¹⁷ More equitable science is also proffered by many open science proponents, as public access is, after all, access by and for everyone, extending the possibility of engaging in science to those who might otherwise find themselves at the foot of the ivory tower.³¹⁸ For these reasons and more, open science is also argued to simply be better science – the argument

³¹⁶ Budapest Open Access Initiative, “Budapest Open Access Declaration,” Budapest Open Access Initiative, February 14, 2002, <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/>; “Berlin Declaration,” Open Access Initiatives of the Max Planck Society, accessed February 19, 2026, <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>.

³¹⁷ Open Science Collaboration, “Estimating the Reproducibility of Psychological Science,” *Science* 349, no. 6251 (2015): aac4716, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac4716>; C. Glenn Begley and Lee M. Ellis, “Raise Standards for Preclinical Cancer Research,” *Nature* 483, no. 7391 (2012): 531–33, <https://doi.org/10.1038/483531a>.

³¹⁸ Chelle Gentemann et al., “Opening Up to Open Science,” *Issues in Science and Technology* 38, no. 3 (2022): 57, <https://issues.org/opening-up-open-science-gentemann-erdmann-kroeger/>.

is made that by enabling greater access throughout the research lifecycle, science might reach its highest aims.³¹⁹

Critics of the open science movement note the extensive amount of work required to meet its lofty goals, creating burdens so high as to pose a material threat to the equitability the movement claims to advance.³²⁰ Open science advocates, comprised of energized researchers, policymakers, academic librarians, and entrepreneurs acknowledge the labor and counter by advancing new infrastructural interventions that have been strategically and intentionally designed not only to support the new demands of open science, but to also synchronize the enactment of open science principles with reward systems such that researchers are incentivized to adapt their behavior to the ideals of the open science movement. Towards the former, technical advances are made such that it becomes possible to conceive of a global research ecosystem comprised of interconnected components, including publisher platforms, data warehouses, and institutional repositories, that had previously existed independently but – now linked by standards, protocol, and the use of unique identifiers – could be leveraged to more meaningfully assess and engineer the research system as a whole.³²¹

This sociotechnical engineering is perhaps the most defining feature of the values-driven research assessment period, evident across numerous resources illustrative of the time. In 2018, the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine published a report titled *Open*

³¹⁹ Editorial Board, “Open Science — Embrace It before It’s Too Late,” *Nature* 626, no. 7998 (2024): 233–233, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00322-2>; Gentemann et al., “Opening Up to Open Science”; Brian Tarran, “Why Open Science Is ‘Just Good Science in a Digital Era,’” *Real World Data Science*, February 3, 2023, <https://realworlddatascience.net/foundation-frontiers/interviews/posts/2023/02/03/heidi-seibold.html>.

³²⁰ Tony Ross-Hellauer, “Open Science, Done Wrong, Will Compound Inequities,” *Nature* 603, no. 7901 (2022): 363–363, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00724-0>.

³²¹ Jamaica Jones and Ted Habermann, “Leveraging the Global Research Infrastructure to Characterize the Impact of National Science Foundation Research,” *Information Services and Use* 45, nos. 1–2 (2025): 30–47, <https://doi.org/10.1177/18758789251336079>.

Science by Design that, as its title suggests, champions the intentional, ethically motivated engineering that typifies the period.³²² Likewise, a similar report offering a *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives*, authored by multiple well-known open science advocates including Michael Dougherty of the University of Maryland and Caitlin Carter of the Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship (HELIOS), is titularly and expressly committed to orchestrating academic incentive systems such that they reward open science efforts on the part of faculty and researchers.³²³ An additional report titled *Walking the Talk, published by the Humane Metrics in the Humanities and Social Sciences (HumetricsHSS) initiative (an effort to center locally relevant values in research assessment regimes)*, concretizes the notion that values alignment can be treated as a design problem, offering tools for evaluators to articulate and ultimately reward research practices, design, and outputs that reflect local values.³²⁴ A similar contribution is made by Robin Chin Roemer and Rachel Borchardt who, on behalf of the Association of College and Research Librarians, publish a report called *Meaningful Metrics: A 21st-Century Librarian's Guide to Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, and Research Impact*, intended to support academic librarians in advancing values-driven and locally relevant research assessment across their home institutions.³²⁵

If values alignment is a design problem, it follows that the VDRA period would also be home to a series of proposed design solutions. A number of critical contributors to the research

³²² National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research* (The National Academies of Science, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.17226/25116>.

³²³ Michael R. Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, February 21, 2024, <https://osf.io/na7dh/>.

³²⁴ Nicky Agate et al., *Walking the Talk: Toward a Values-Aligned Academy* (HuMetricsHSS, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.17613/06sf-ad45>.

³²⁵ Robin Chin Roemer and Rachel Borchardt, *Meaningful Metrics: A 21st-Century Librarian's Guide to Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, and Research Impact* (Association of College and Research Libraries, 2015), <https://alastore.ala.org/content/meaningful-metrics-21st-century-librarians-guide-bibliometrics-altmetrics-and-research>.

ecosystem have either introduced new initiatives or honed existing ones to adapt research infrastructure such that it is designed to recognize new types of research contributions, track citations to these newly recognized resources, and identify and quantify other instances of values-driven actions within the research lifecycle. An early harbinger of this work is the Make Data Count initiative which, as the title makes clear, has set forth to make data “count” in systems of research assessment and reward. There is a systemic approach, touching all points throughout the research lifecycle to recommend data citation styles, ensure the regular use of identifiers, reengineer related infrastructures, and affect promotion, retention, and tenure practices such that they also “count” and reward data sharing efforts. The Public Library of Science (PLOS), meanwhile, has similarly undertaken to engineer a pilot set of “open science indicators” it believes can be reliably captured and used to meaningfully account for instances of open science practice by publishing researchers.³²⁶

By standardizing metadata, tracking sharing and reuse, and connecting indicators across repositories and publishing platforms, these initiatives create the conditions under which open practices can be monitored, quantified, and incentivized, illustrating the through which reform of what is recognized as a broken and inequitable system might be engineered into the architecture of research infrastructure itself. Federal memoranda provide technical and normative scaffolding, manifestos and advocacy documents set forth a design vision, and infrastructural initiatives enact those recommendations through standards, identifiers, and platforms. The sections that follow trace this evolution across the three analytic themes – control, quality, and value – to reveal how

³²⁶ Hrynaszkiewicz, “PLOS Partners with DataSeer to Develop Open Science Indicators.”

values-driven research assessment has emerged as a coordinated effort to affect values-oriented results through strategic social engineering.

6.2 Control

Control reemerges as a primary concern during the VDRA period. Throughout, a certain activism is palpable, evident across simultaneous efforts by researchers, institutions, and advocacy groups to assume the role of agents of change. Their goal is to craft an ideal set of research behaviors by strategically engineering the systems that support, describe, and reward them. Control is therefore advanced as an explicitly normative effort, often expressed in the language of stewardship. Federal policy makers, researchers, and advocates alike frame control as a collective responsibility and obligation on the part of all involved to cultivate a research ecosystem that reflects and upholds the values (assumed or overtly stated) of the scholarly community.

At the federal level, the clearest engagement with control again comes out of the Office of Science and Technology Policy, in the form of the Holdren and Nelson Memos. The Holdren Memo marked a pivotal moment in the federal government's effort to govern the output of its own research funding. Specifically, it required affected agencies to identify, preserve, and make research outputs publicly available within twelve months of publication. It likewise required that these agencies implement the necessary solutions to ensure that these outputs were described by openly available metadata.³²⁷ Both of these were to be achieved via open access institutional

³²⁷ Holdren, "Increasing Access to the Results of Federally Funded Scientific Research."

repositories or publishing mechanisms, setting in place a cascade of collateral effects across agency and publisher infrastructures. While the Holdren Memo is most broadly recognized as a critical advance in ensuring public access to the results of federally funded research results, behind the scenes it represents an equally significant advance in enabling the tracing and analysis of federally-funded research outputs. Nine years after its release, the Nelson Memo pushed each of these mandates – and their collateral effects – further, abolishing the 12-month embargo period and requiring that associated open metadata include persistent identifiers (PIDs) for authors, institutions, awards, and outputs.³²⁸

While these mandates define the structural mechanisms of control, their language reveals an equally important moral dimension. The Holdren Memo frames stewardship of research outputs as a federal duty, premised on the understanding that openness enhances both accountability and efficiency. It further positions federally funded research as “the grist for new insights and... assets for progress”, casting public access as service to the public good.³²⁹ The obligatory tone of the Holdren Memo paves the way for the Nelson Memo’s amplification of similarly normative framing, tying civic ideals to scientific values into a heavily laden rhetoric of duty and integrity. “A federal public access policy consistent with our values of equal opportunity,” it argues,

...must allow for broad and expeditious sharing of federally funded research—and must allow all Americans to benefit from the returns on our research and development investments without delay. Upholding these core U.S. principles in our public access policy also strengthens our ability to be a critical leader and partner on issues of open science around the world. The U.S. is committed to the ideas that openness in science is fundamental, security is essential, and freedom and integrity are crucial. Improving public access policies across the U.S. government to promote the rapid sharing of federally funded research data with appropriate protections and accountability measures will allow for greater validity

³²⁸ Nelson, “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research.”

³²⁹ Holdren, “Increasing Access to the Results of Federally Funded Scientific Research,” 1.

of research results and more equitable access to data resources aligned with these ideals. To promote equity and advance the work of restoring the public's trust in Government science, and to advance American scientific leadership, now is the time to amend federal policy to deliver immediate public access to federally funded research.³³⁰

This passage does quite a bit of work, pairing recognizably American values – including freedom, equality, and leadership – with a purported ethical structure of science, calling upon integrity, rigor and validity as the mechanisms through which scientific trustworthiness and national legitimacy might be simultaneously secured. Such a policy-level marriage of supposed American and scientific values raises the stakes in terms of control over the research enterprise. Framed as it is by the Nelson Memo, control is now afforded a dual opportunity in both infrastructure and ideology, extending the moral imperative of the Holdren Memo such that the domains of civic and scientific virtue are merged. The result is an expression of control that is new to the history of research assessment – one in which an intentionally engineered system might reproduce the values of good science and good governance simultaneously.

As federal policy committed to integrating values into its mandates, the research and advocacy communities have been simultaneously committed to adapting systems such that they are, likewise, intentionally designed to reward desired actions, outputs, and outcomes. No longer content to simply critique the limitations of existing systems, the critics of prior periods here have become agents of reform, advancing targeted proposals for how openness in particular can be structurally supported and normatively reinforced. The National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine's (NASEM) 2018 report *Open Science by Design* is perhaps the exemplar of this sort of effort. It resulted from a study commissioned by the Laura and John Arnold

³³⁰ Nelson, "Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research," 2.

Foundation with the explicit aim of identifying the steps necessary to “move toward open science as the default for scientific research”.³³¹ Offering five recommendations implicating actors at every level of the research ecosystem, the report’s authors center a restructuring of the academic reward system as their first. Recommending that “research institutions should work to create a culture that actively supports Open Science by Design by better rewarding and supporting researchers engaged in open science practices”, they start at the top, also calling in research funders with a mandate to “provide explicit and consistent support for practices and approaches that facilitate this shift in culture and incentives.”³³²

Throughout the report, its authors repeatedly frame the issue as a normative one, perpetuated by a system of rewards that is baked into the design of the scholarly communications ecosystem itself. “Researchers have the incentive to maximize the visibility of each scientific discovery,” they observe, while “universities seek to maximize the visibility and productivity of their faculty.”³³³ Meanwhile, “federal research funders are held accountable by Congress,” and “scientific societies promote the scholarship of their disciplines for their members.”³³⁴ Embedded within this larger structure of incentives are more nuanced, contextualized concerns that the authors repeatedly reference as being matters of culture. Speaking in some places of variations

³³¹ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 17.

³³² National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 7.

³³³ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 39–40.

³³⁴ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 40.

across disciplinary “publishing cultures” and in other places about “cultures of openness”, the authors make a case for “culture change” at the infrastructural level.³³⁵

This charge of culture change resonates strongly across VDRA documents, emerging first from the 2015 introduction of the Center for Open Science’s (COS) Transparency, Openness, and Promotion (TOP) Guidelines. Announced by way of a *Science* editorial, the TOP Guidelines were developed by Brian Nosek and his team at COS – an organization that is itself explicitly committed to advancing open science-related “culture change” across the research ecosystem – in effort to embed open standards across journal infrastructures and with the goal of “[translating] scientific norms and values into concrete actions and [changing] the current incentive structures to drive researchers' behavior toward more openness”.³³⁶ Framed as both a practical and a behavioral intervention, the TOP Guidelines strategically position incentives as a lever for shifting research culture, offering a tiered model that encourages journals to adopt increasingly stringent transparency standards and making it possible for publishers to gradually reshape the norms of scholarly communication. Implicit in this design is a theory of change that places journals at the heart of the culture in need of change.

The journal article is central to the research communication process. Guidelines for authors define what aspects of the research process should be made available to the community to evaluate, critique, reuse, and extend. Scientists recognize the value of transparency, openness, and reproducibility. Improvement of journal policies can help those values become more evident in daily practice and ultimately improve the public trust in science, and science itself.³³⁷

³³⁵ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 120; National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 96; National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 114.

³³⁶ Center for Open Science, “About,” accessed April 12, 2025, <https://www.cos.io/about>; B. A. Nosek et al., “Promoting an Open Research Culture: Author Guidelines for Journals Could Help to Promote Transparency, Openness, and Reproducibility,” *Science* 348, no. 6242 (2015): 1243, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aab2374>.

³³⁷ Nosek et al., “Promoting an Open Research Culture,” 1425.

Per this vision, culture change becomes a matter of infrastructural intervention, and control over the incentive system thus becomes a shared responsibility – one that both journals and the broader research community are called upon to steward.

This sense of stewardship is also central to the *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives*, which urges researchers to reenvision themselves as the active agents of reform, working to reshape research assessment rather than sit passively as the subjects of it. The *Toolkit* is, indeed, openly reform-oriented, highlighting the opportunity for individual actors to act as instigators of change within their home departments. “[T]he toolkit,” its authors explain, “is designed to provide a brief overview of several topics related to change, providing the change maker (you!) with resources and talking points to guide discussion (and change!) in your own units.”³³⁸ The *Toolkit* directly addresses researchers as potential leaders who are perfectly positioned to steward a more just and trustworthy research ecosystem (“we can and should do better!”), encouraging them to “realign” academic incentives with scholarly values.³³⁹ It offers a suite of fact sheets and a value-aligned assessment worksheet designed to support “culture change” from the ground up, outfitting researchers with tools to advance reforms that reflect their disciplinary norms, institutional missions, and personal commitments.³⁴⁰

While many reform documents in the VDRA corpus focus on realigning incentive structures to promote open science practices, others – such as HumetricsHSS’ *Walking the Talk* report – broaden the lens, emphasizing the importance of aligning research assessment with whatever values are dominant across individual institutions and their constitutive communities.

³³⁸ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 2.

³³⁹ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 4.

³⁴⁰ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 9.

The report emphasizes the importance of local, values-based governance, arguing that reform efforts must begin with an honest reckoning of what a given community seeks to reward and why. Like other reports from the period, *Walking the Talk* treats alignment as a design problem that can be addressed through intentional reflection, community engagement, and procedural transparency. They champion an approach recognizable as the “responsible use” of metrics, advanced by many others and inclusive of efforts to use “baskets of” or multiple metrics to ensure fulsome representation; to allow metrics to support but not supplant qualitative, expert judgement; and to ensure that any metrics used are selected for their alignment with local values.³⁴¹

Whereas the *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives* and the *Walking the Talk* report offer supports for reform-oriented action, the Public Library of Science’s Open Science Indicators (OSI) initiative advances an alternative suite of measures that were explicitly designed as infrastructural interventions meant to capture and quantify open science behaviors. Leveraging DOIs and other PIDs as their base unit, these indicators have been designed to track the sharing of research data, code, and protocol across the global research infrastructure. The OSI themselves are published with associated articles across PLOS journals, not as a means of monitoring compliance, it is argued, but rather “to understand how we can facilitate best practice and support research.”³⁴² Authors Iain Hrynaszkiewicz and Veronique Kiermer offer additional reassurances regarding the intent of these metrics clarifying that, “Open Science Indicators are just that – indications of Open Science practices.” However, they allow, “when combined with qualitative insights and other

³⁴¹ James Wilsdon et al., *The Metric Tide: Report of the Independent Review of the Role of Metrics in Research Assessment and Management* (Higher Education Funding Council for England, 2015), 134, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4929.1363>; Anna Clements et al., “Snowball Metrics – Providing a Robust Methodology to Inform Research Strategy – but Do They Help?,” *Procedia Computer Science* 106 (2017): 11–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.03.003>.

³⁴² Hrynaszkiewicz, “PLOS Partners with DataSeer to Develop Open Science Indicators,” 2.

responsibly-used metrics, Open Science Indicators could help provide a more complete understanding of the impact and credibility of research.... We see an opportunity for these Indicators to neutrally measure such activities wherever they are happening and reward the activity.”³⁴³

PLOS’ OSI are in some respects built on a foundation that was laid by the Make Data Count initiative of years prior. Launched in the early 2010s as a response to widespread recognition across the scholarly community that data sharing – prized as a hallmark effort of the open science movement – was both labor-intensive and inadequately rewarded. Frustrated by the perceived marginalization of data as a scholarly output, early organizers of the effort collaborated across the ecosystem to establish infrastructure to support the citation and data reuse tracking that are built into PLOS’ approach. As did PLOS in establishing OSIs, the early Make Data Count team intentionally incorporated feedback from the scholarly community into the design of their solutions, engaging both researchers and data managers in a survey designed to identify how data sharing should be incentivized.³⁴⁴ Their results revealed that researchers overwhelmingly valued formal citation as the most meaningful way to credit data contributions, however a tension arose from the survey data – while citation was prized, its actual practice was revealed to be compromised by a lack of standardized practice, a gap attributed to insufficient infrastructure.³⁴⁵ In response, the Make Data Count team worked collaborated with repository and other infrastructure providers on the development of a standardized, interoperable approach to capturing data citations. Now well established, Make Data Count exists as a collaboratively governed

³⁴³ Hrynaszkiewicz, “PLOS Partners with DataSeer to Develop Open Science Indicators,” 6.

³⁴⁴ John E. Kratz and Carly Strasser, “Making Data Count,” *Scientific Data* 2, no. 1 (2015): 150039, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.39>.

³⁴⁵ Kratz and Strasser, “Making Data Count,” 3.

initiative, fiscally sponsored by DataCite, perhaps the most significant infrastructure provider supporting research data and relevant persistent identifiers.³⁴⁶

Finally, the imperative to realign research incentives with observed values is also clearly articulated in the three foundational calls for reform that mark the VDRA period: 2013's Declaration on Research Assessment, the Leiden Manifesto, and the Paris Call on Research Assessment, each of which emerged from the collective input of researchers, librarians, publishers, and administrators, and each of which challenges the use of journal-based metrics and urges the academic community to adopt evaluative practices that reflect a more inclusive range of scholarly contributions. As the first, DORA focuses on journal impact factors, calling on institutions and funders to eliminate their use, advocating instead for a focus on the content and context of individual research outputs.³⁴⁷ The summary argument is that, as the validity of research assessment is understood to be critical, those assessments must be attuned to and reflective of the priorities and values of the communities being assessed. Two years after DORA, the Leiden Manifesto, named after the location of the 2014 conference from which it emerged, recommended ten actionable principles that foreground peer review, disciplinary variation, and transparency in assessment, emphasizing that metrics should support (rather than supplant) expert judgment, and – building on DORA's lead – that evaluation criteria should be tailored to local values.³⁴⁸ The Paris Call on Research Assessment builds on these foundations further by urging institutions to move toward qualitative, context-aware assessments that value societal relevance, collaboration,

³⁴⁶ Make Data Count, "Frequently Asked Questions," Make Data Count, October 7, 2024, <https://makedatacount.org/learn-about-us/frequently-asked-questions/>; Paul Vierkant, "What We Do," DataCite, accessed April 12, 2025, <https://datacite.org/what-we-do/>.

³⁴⁷ DORA, *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment*.

³⁴⁸ Hicks et al., "Leiden Manifesto."

and – above all – openness.³⁴⁹ Drafted by the French Open Science Committee and delivered to the Paris Open Science European Conference, the Paris Call centers openness as a primary means by which the research community might “align what we assess with what we value,” ultimately calling for “a research assessment system that:

- rewards quality and the various impacts of research;
- ensures that research meets the highest standards of ethics and integrity;
- values the diversity of research activities and outputs such as publications and preprints, data, methods, software, code and as well as their societal impacts...;
- uses assessment criteria and processes that respect the variety of research disciplines;
- rewards not only research outputs, but also the appropriate conduct of research, and values good practices...;
- values collaborative work, as well as cross-disciplinarity and citizen science, when appropriate; [and]
- supports a diversity of researcher profiles and career paths.³⁵⁰

Serving as a culmination of the three formal calls for assessment reform that mark the VDRA period, the Paris Call neatly ties together the mandates of its predecessors while also asserting an attempt at control – in a manner that is indicative of the time – that endeavors to shift structures in pursuit of an intentional incentivizing of ethically inflected behavior that is believed to support the production of “good science.”

Broadly, the developments of the VDRA period illustrate a moment in which the exercise of control reaches past the administrative oversight of prior periods, striving beyond management of research outputs and towards a more holistic engineering of research values themselves. The systems built to track, link, and account for research outputs also then become systems through which rigor, reproducibility, and responsibility are rendered visible. The exercise of control thus

³⁴⁹ Paris Open Science European Conference, *Paris Call – OSEC 2022*.

³⁵⁰ Paris Open Science European Conference, *Paris Call – OSEC 2022*.

begins to merge with the pursuit of quality. The following section examines this convergence across the VDRA period, tracing how the interlinked concepts of rigor, reproducibility, and responsibility come to define research quality.

6.3 Quality

Whereas in prior periods, research quality is understood as a feature of research outputs and identifiable through peer recognition, in the VDRA period quality is repositioned as being identifiable through behavior, evident in the ways science is conducted and, importantly, shared. In this period, quality is framed as a collective expression of two virtues – rigor and reproducibility – each of which functions as an ethical and methodological marker suggestive of the conditions under which science is pursued. Per the open science discourse that dominates this era, the prized characteristics of research quality are understood and discussed as design imperatives – features that can and should be embedded into the social and technical infrastructures that support the research enterprise.

Rigor stands out as the most procedural of the three, given that it can be enacted and thus evidenced at each stage of the research lifecycle. The National Academies' *Open Science by Design* positions open science as a means of operationalizing this opportunity, suggesting practices such as preregistration, data sharing, and replication as interventions that can demonstrate rigor. “From the very beginning of the research process,” the authors argue, “the researcher both contributes to open science and takes advantage of the open science practices of other members of the research community. Practicing open science by design means that researchers develop new

habits and customs to promote better science.”³⁵¹ They then make their case more tangible by offering examples of the ways in which open practices might advance research rigor at each stage in the research lifecycle (see Figure 7), highlighting opportunities to ensure that research questions are robustly informed during the “provocation” phase, that methodological intent is declared via preregistration in the ideation phase, and that analytic and interpretive decisions are thoroughly documented in the validation phase.³⁵²

Figure 7: The National Academies' Open Science by Design research lifecycle³⁵³

Such practices would take place during the conduct of research, demonstrating those values that Helen Longino characterized as those that are constitutive of science.³⁵⁴ Reproducibility, the second expression of quality idealized throughout the VDRA period, functions differently as rather than ensuring or demonstrating its object, it serves instead to create the conditions under which such ideals might be achieved.³⁵⁵ Despite its contingent nature, *Open Science by Design* describes reproducibility as “the heart of science and the scientific method,” emphasizing that the reliability of knowledge depends on the ability to replicate and verify results across time and context. Written

³⁵¹ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 108.

³⁵² National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 108–10.

³⁵³ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*, 109.

³⁵⁴ Longino, “Introduction: Good Science, Bad Science,” 4.

³⁵⁵ This insight is owed to Dr. Michael R. Dietrich and is included here with gratitude.

in the wake of the “reproducibility crisis,” the report directly links reproducibility to openness, observing that “open publication, open data, and open code support the ability of researchers to confirm and reproduce findings,” advancing “reproducibility enhancement principles” that articulate how a commitment to transparency might be enacted. It calls on researchers to share data, software, and workflows in open repositories, to use persistent identifiers to connect digital objects, and to ensure that journals “conduct a reproducibility check as part of the publication process, further extending the framework to institutions and funders, recommending that they “encourage and reward studies that focus on the replication and reproducibility of published research” and that the latter in particular embed training in open science and reproducibility across graduate curricula and professional societies.

The *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives* advances this design logic within the reward structures of research. It identifies “rigor, reproducibility, and quality” as core values associated with the production of knowledge and translates these ideals into observable actions such as preregistering analyses, conducting replication studies, sharing data and materials in trusted repositories, and adopting standardized identifiers.³⁵⁶ These actions are presented as behaviors that can be tracked and rewarded, enabling institutions to signal their commitment to quality while also providing researchers with clearer expectations. Through such a framework, reproducibility comes to function as both an indicator and as a practice, signaling a certain scientific virtue while also creating the conditions under which accountability can be advanced and, importantly, demonstrated.

³⁵⁶ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*.

Running alongside these advocacy-driven articulations of research quality is a substantial body of scholarship emerging from within the research community itself that approaches the question of quality from a different angle. The concern in this body of literature is focused on understanding how existing incentive structures shape research behavior and, relatedly, the conditions under which rigorous science can be reliably produced. A core problem emerges from this subset of the literature: the time, care, and labor required to produce rigorous research are insufficiently supported and unevenly rewarded within contemporary research assessment regimes. For instance, Higginson and Munafò, in reporting their findings from a study performed over a corpus of published biomedical research demonstrate how competitive publication incentives favor novelty, positive results, and quickly produced output, resulting in systematic pressures toward statistically underpowered and analytically malleable research design.³⁵⁷

Current incentive structures in science, combined with existing conventions such as a significance level of 5%, encourage rational scientists to adopt a research strategy that is to the detriment of the advancement of scientific knowledge. Given finite resources, the importance placed on novel findings, and the emphasis on a relatively small number of publications, scientists wishing to accelerate their career progression should conduct a large number of exploratory studies, each of which will have low statistical power. Since the conclusions of underpowered studies are highly likely to be erroneous, this means that most published findings are likely to be false. The results of our model support this conclusion. Indeed, given evidence that with sufficient analytical flexibility (known as p-hacking) almost any dataset can produce a statistically significant (and therefore publishable) finding....³⁵⁸

³⁵⁷ Andrew D. Higginson and Marcus R. Munafò, “Current Incentives for Scientists Lead to Underpowered Studies with Erroneous Conclusions,” *PLOS Biology* 14, no. 11 (2016): 2, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2000995>.

³⁵⁸ Higginson and Munafò, “Current Incentives for Scientists Lead to Underpowered Studies with Erroneous Conclusions,” 8.

It is notable that here, the authors' diagnosis trains attention on systems rather than on individual behaviors, centering institutional and systemic pressures as the source of these undesirable outcomes.

Similar dynamics are evident in studies of promotion and tenure criteria as well. Studies by McKiernan et al. and Pontika et al. suggest that while institutional policies may gesture towards quality and “responsible” research, formal evaluation criteria persist in relying on proxy indicators.³⁵⁹ Meanwhile, practices directly associated with rigor and reproducibility – including data sharing, replication, and transparent documentation – remain marginal or wholly absent within many assessment frameworks. The findings of Pontika et al.'s study are particularly suggestive: having analyzed the qualitative and quantitative standards by which research is assessed and framing their analysis in terms of the “traditional” – largely referencing quantitative impact metrics – and the “alternative” – such as those “relating to open and responsible research” – criteria, the research team determined that traditional measures remain dominant.³⁶⁰ “Assessing the prevalence of traditional and alternative (especially open/responsible research related) criteria across policies of 107 institutions,” they report, “we find substantial differences in their prevalence.... Overall, traditional indicators, related to the profession or to scientific publications, are much more common than indicators related to open and responsible research.”³⁶¹

³⁵⁹ Erin C. McKiernan et al., “Use of the Journal Impact Factor in Academic Review, Promotion, and Tenure Evaluations,” *eLife* 8 (July 2019): 5, <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.47338>; Nancy Pontika et al., “Indicators of Research Quality, Quantity, Openness, and Responsibility in Institutional Review, Promotion, and Tenure Policies across Seven Countries,” *Quantitative Science Studies* 3, no. 4 (2022): 890, https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00224.

³⁶⁰ Pontika et al., “Indicators of Research Quality, Quantity, Openness, and Responsibility in Institutional Review, Promotion, and Tenure Policies across Seven Countries,” 895.

³⁶¹ Pontika et al., “Indicators of Research Quality, Quantity, Openness, and Responsibility in Institutional Review, Promotion, and Tenure Policies across Seven Countries,” 897.

Both research and commentary from the VDRA period suggest that as demands for demonstrations of research quality sharpen, metrics used to assess for it remain, at best, dependent on proxy affiliation. As research continues to illustrate and substantiate a disconnect between the priorities of the research community and the measures by which their work is evaluated, proposed solutions continue to focus on the measurement rather than the measurability of quality itself. In the VDRA period, quality is most commonly expressed in terms of rigor and reproducibility, each of which is argued by open science advocates to constitute research quality while also demonstrating the value of scientific research to broader publics. It is to this theme that the following section turns.

6.4 Value

Given that this chapter details findings from what has been identified as a period of values-driven research assessment, and given that this particular section explores how research value is discussed and negotiated across this period, it is important to reiterate the framing of “research value” that is leveraged in this dissertation. In the context of this research, the term “research value” is understood to reference what research is “worth” – not how good it is, but what good it does. This definition distinguishes research value from research quality as well as from the epistemological and ethical priorities (“values”) that might inform judgement. Constrained by these defining bounds, research value is a concept that is negotiated throughout the VDRA period in much more inclusive terms than it had been considered in prior periods. In the Science Indicators period, value was considered in terms of its demonstrable value to the public. In the Science of

Science period, the primary concern relative to value had to do with quantification – its importance and accuracy. In the VDRA period, the discussion unfolds in more nuanced terms, expanding to include more subject material drawn from and identifiable in a more diverse array of sources, and locating the value of science in its public service and accessibility.

Towards the former, the VDRA period is home to a number of related efforts each designed to expand the bounds of outputs and contributions that are considered valuable across the conduct of research. Make Data Count is an exemplar of this, in its concerted effort to ensure that the creation, sharing, and reuse of research datasets are properly valued within and across the research ecosystem. The altmetrics movement provides another such example – one in which the media and mechanisms through which “impact” is recognized are opened to expansion. Jason Priem introduced altmetrics in the early 2010s, offering them as an alternative to traditional impact measures, which he and others argued no longer adequately reflected the range of outlets through which scholarly work is produced, shared, or engaged in the digital age. In his widely cited “altmetrics: a manifesto”, Priem observes that “[i]n growing numbers, scholars are moving their everyday work to the web,” and, further, that scholarly communication had evolved into a diverse ecosystem of networked technologies, actors, and what was then a newly interactive social media.³⁶² Altmetrics emerged as an effort to capture this broader ecosystem, tracking article views, downloads, social media mentions, policy citations, blog posts, and other forms of engagement that were understood by Priem and his collaborators to signal attention and relevance. The larger argument made by altmetrics evangelists is that peer recognition is context dependent. If it is to continue to serve as the coin of the realm, and if that realm transforms – as it had throughout the

³⁶² Priem et al., “Altmetrics.”

1990s and early 2000s – peer recognition must be sought and captured in terms that are commensurate with these changes. Despite criticism that altmetrics track mere “noise”, enable narcissism, and exacerbate the same historical inequities that their proponents criticized in more traditional metrics, they were soon – like those traditional metrics – incorporated into commodified products such as Elsevier’s PlumX Metrics.³⁶³

Simultaneous to discussions about what might demonstrate research value and where those demonstrations might be made is a critical interrogation of the ways in which value, and particularly impact, are understood of relevant terms. Academic librarians Robert Chin Roemer and Rachel Borchardt are direct in their unpacking, which prefaces their 2015 report *Meaningful Metrics: A 21st Century Librarian’s Guide to Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, and Research Impact*:

To understand what we get when we measure impact, we must jump back to what we actually mean when we talk about particular impact metrics. When we say, for instance, that a journal has an impact factor of three, what we mean is that in the last three years, this journal averaged three citations per published article. Does this mean if we publish in this journal we will have achieved impact? Not really, but it does tell us something about citations, which historically have been viewed as the best available approximations of academic impact. Indeed, the entire field of bibliometrics is based around the acceptability of this sort of substitution. But what we get when we count citations or perform analysis on book and article bibliographies is just that: information about citation patterns. It is only when we start to tell stories with these numbers (e.g., “my average is higher than your average”) that we get to a place where impact can thrive. It’s a small distinction but an essential one, particularly as we tackle our preconceptions and prejudices about the “legitimacy” of different impact metrics.³⁶⁴

³⁶³ Paul Wouters and Rodrigo Costas, “Users, Narcissism and Control: Tracking the Impact of Scholarly Publications in the 21st Century,” paper presented at 17th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, Quebec, *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, January 1, 2012, https://www.academia.edu/11617769/Users_Narcissism_and_Control_Tracking_the_Impact_of_Scholarly_Publications_in_the_21_st_Century; Cassidy R. Sugimoto and Vincent Larivière, “Altmetrics: Broadening Impact or Amplifying Voices?,” *ACS Central Science* 3, no. 7 (2017): 674–76, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.7b00249>; Elsevier, “PlumX Metrics,” Elsevier, accessed January 2, 2026, <https://www.elsevier.com/insights/metrics/plumx>.

³⁶⁴ Roemer and Borchardt, *Meaningful Metrics: A 21st Century Librarian’s Guide to Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, and Research Impact*, 5.

Michael Dougherty and his coauthors likewise premise the *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives* on the observation that “there is little or no evidence that” impact factor and other “journal-based metrics reflect the quality of the research,” noting that they “may cause more harm than good when included in faculty evaluation.”³⁶⁵ Centering by-then canonical research on the limitations of impact factor-based assessment factors, the *Toolkit’s* authors assert that “for far too long academic incentive systems have been misaligned with the foundational values upon which universities were founded. Rather than reward work based on the substance of their work, researchers are often rewarded based on superficial ‘metrics’ that promote quantity over quality and under-value research that addresses critical societal problems.”³⁶⁶ Following, they declare their motivation for developing the toolkit, noting that it “stems from the recognition that correcting this misalignment is necessary for promoting research integrity, restoring trust in science (and higher education), and building a more just society.”³⁶⁷ The opportunity for this correction, they argue, rests in community-engaged, open, rigorous, and reproducible science – all of which, in their view, is supported by “aligning” impact assessment with the “true” value of research.

Evident throughout language used in the *Toolkit* is an embedded presumption that is found in quite a bit of the literature of the period, regarding the duty of science to serve society. Indeed, as evidenced in the language above, the assertion appears to be that those involved in the research ecosystem bear an ethical responsibility to ensure that the system does not just endeavor but in fact achieves its highest potential so that it might further advance the highest aims of society. Open science is argued to be the mechanism through which these ideals might be achieved, evidenced

³⁶⁵ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 2.

³⁶⁶ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 1.

³⁶⁷ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 1.

across many of the advocacy documents of the period, including within the 2021 *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. This report packages service toward the public good in its very definition of open science, which presupposes that open science must engage and include broader publics in its practice, outputs, and collateral benefit:

...open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.³⁶⁸

UNESCO's *Recommendation* closes by offering formal guidance regarding evaluation, arguing for the creation of an incentivization structure that explicitly rewards open science practices and, simultaneously, acknowledges expanding notions of "value" across the research ecosystem. These recommendations include assigning "value to all relevant research activities and scientific outputs including... teaching, outreach and engagement of societal actors," and taking "into account evidence of research impact and knowledge exchange, such as widening participation in the research process, influence on policy and practice and engaging in open innovation with partners beyond academia".³⁶⁹

During this period, the concept of research value undergoes a marked transformation, expanding from traditional notions of academic prestige and influence to include a broader and

³⁶⁸ UNESCO, *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* (UNESCO, 2021), 7, <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>.

³⁶⁹ UNESCO, *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*, 27.

more socially engaged set of meanings. Ross-Hellauer et al. provide one of the clearest articulations of this transformation in their qualitative analysis of researcher perspectives on research value, identifying a widespread “value dissonance” between what researchers personally consider meaningful and what their institutions formally reward.³⁷⁰ Many researchers included in their study expressed strong commitments to contributions that reach beyond academic boundaries – such as societal and economic impact, public engagement, and community partnerships – but found these to be only rarely reflected in their institutions’ PRT policies (see Figure 8).³⁷¹

Figure 8: A figure drawn from Ross-Hellauer et al’s study on value dissonance, illustrating a “comparison between personal and... institutional view[s] on promotion criteria”, as perceived by researchers.³⁷²

That science should benefit the public is neither a novel nor a recent expectation. As discussed in Chapter Four, it was a guiding priority for policymakers during the Science Indicators

³⁷⁰ Tony Ross-Hellauer et al., “Value Dissonance in Research(Er) Assessment: Individual and Perceived Institutional Priorities in Review, Promotion, and Tenure,” *Science and Public Policy*, November 17, 2023, scad073, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad073>.

³⁷¹ Ross-Hellauer et al., “Value Dissonance in Research(Er) Assessment,” 8.

³⁷² Ross-Hellauer et al., “Value Dissonance in Research(Er) Assessment,” 8.

period. What stands out as a nuanced shift during the VDRA period is both the emphasis and the inflection used in discussing public engagement. Rather than merely serving the public, it is argued throughout the literature reviewed in this analysis that actors across the research ecosystem should engage the public. This is well illustrated by the *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives*, in which various forms of engagement are discussed as means of evidencing efforts towards the public good. The *Toolkit* closes with a series of tables linking values to actions and associated markers that could serve as indicators of work in support of those values. Figure 9 reflects the authors' suggestions regarding work towards the public good, including "community-engaged research" as a supporting activity and, as a related indicator of such work, sharing results "with the public, communicating with understandable language that facilitates reuse of information."³⁷³

³⁷³ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 20.

Values	Considerations	Activities or outputs	Behaviors and Indicators	
		Open reporting of results	Academics share their research reports via public preprint servers, repositories, or open access journals.	
		Funding	Academics openly disclose (in publications, on their websites, etc.) which organizations fund their research, and where any potential conflicts of interest may exist.	
Public good	What population(s) does the academic institution serve? Which aspects of academic work should benefit the public?	Education	Academics share educational materials, like class notes, authored textbooks, and videos, via public platforms that can be freely accessed and materials used by local schools.	
		Outreach	Academics participate in outreach activities, especially to engage or inspire the populations they serve as Minority-Serving Institutions, Land-grant universities, or other goals aligned with their institutional mission.	
		Research	Applied research	Academics conduct research of significance to society, addressing problems of relevance to local, regional, or international communities.
			Community-engaged research	Academics ensure their research has relevance and engages or produces real solutions by involving community participants in co-design, data collection, translation of results, etc.
		Research sharing and communication with the public	Academics share their results with the public, communicating with understandable language that facilitates reuse of information.	

Figure 9: Table of values-driven indicator alignment from the Toolkit on Aligning Incentives 2.0³⁷⁴

The “open reporting of results” also stands as its own category in this table entry, paired with behaviors and indicators that include sharing “research reports via public preprint servers, repositories, or open access journals.”³⁷⁵ In similar fashion, open, or public, access to the results of research is regularly centered in the VDRA literature as a societal benefit unto its own. The clearest expression of its primacy as a purported contribution towards the public good can be found in the Nelson Memo, which makes the claim that as a result of the public access victories secured by its predecessor, the Holdren Memo “the American public has experienced great benefits: more

³⁷⁴ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 20–21.

³⁷⁵ Dougherty et al., *Toolkit for Aligning Incentives 2.0*, 21.

than 8 million scholarly publications have become accessible to the public.”³⁷⁶ In such a formulation, access itself is treated as a sufficient proxy for public value, with scale and reach standing in for more substantive accounts of engagement or use. Public access is thereby positioned not merely as a means of serving the public good, but rather as evidence that scientific knowledge itself constitutes a public good.

Across the VDRA period, research value is increasingly articulated as something that can be actively identified and rewarded through the deliberate design of research assessment systems. Value is framed in expansive terms, encompassing public accessibility, societal relevance, and forms of engagement that extend beyond traditional scholarly communications. These commitments are likewise translated into proposed indicators, standards, and infrastructural interventions. Initiatives such as Make Data Count, altmetrics, and open science indicators exemplify this move, advancing concrete mechanisms intended to render previously underrecognized contributions tractable across evaluation and incentive regimes. In parallel, policy documents and advocacy texts present value as a property that can be embedded within the architecture of research governance itself, aligning assessment practices with explicitly articulated ethical and social priorities. What distinguishes this period, then, is not simply an expanded vocabulary of research value, but instead the strategic effort to operationalize that vocabulary through systems designed to cultivate, quantify, and reward particular forms of research conduct. In such a context, research value becomes a governable attribute of the research enterprise, produced through intentional, individual choices.

³⁷⁶ Nelson, “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research,” 1.

6.5 Conclusion

This chapter has traced the emergence of values-driven research assessment from roughly 2012 through roughly 2025, examining how decades-old critiques of research evaluation evolved into coordinated efforts to redesign the systems through which research is assessed. Anchored symbolically by the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment and materially by many other interventions, the VDRA period reflects a moment in which dissatisfaction with proxy-based evaluation gives rise to deliberate intervention across the research ecosystem. Researchers, policymakers, and infrastructure providers participate directly in reshaping assessment regimes, collectively advancing the notion that research governance should align with purported values. What distinguishes this period historically is the extent to which reform is pursued through the strategic engineering of the sociotechnical systems that structure research across its lifecycle.

Viewed through the analytic themes of control, quality, and value, the VDRA period illustrates an expansion and reconfiguration control across the research enterprise. It reemerges here as a central concern, exercised through the design of infrastructures, standards, and incentives that shape research behavior upstream. Federal public access policy provides a clear expression of this shift. Through mandates concerning openness, metadata, and persistent identifiers, the Holdren and Nelson Memos extend federal oversight beyond the management of research outputs toward the construction of the conditions under which research can be linked, quantified, and governed. These policies formalize aspirations articulated during the Science of Science Policy

period, particularly those advanced by John Marburger and Julia Lane, by mandating the technical foundations necessary for “joined-up” research infrastructure.³⁷⁷

With respect to research quality, the VDRA period is marked by a shift away from output-centered proxies and toward a sustained emphasis on both research practice and the conditions of production. The leading priorities surfaced from the literature are rigor and reproducibility – qualities that are sought and described as arising in the conduct of science. This reframing is accompanied by a growing body of scholarship documenting the prevalence of irreproducible results and methodological opacity across disciplines, reinforcing the view that research quality cannot be deduced from outputs alone. Instead, the view that dominates the VDRA literature is that quality is evident through process and thus can be cultivated through personal choice and incentivized through strategic system design. Whereas in prior periods, notions of quality were premised on characteristics that were largely only relevant within the scholarly community, it is interesting to note that in the VDRA period, quality is considered in terms that can help demonstrate trustworthiness.

An observable trend across the VDRA period is a certain dismantling of tradition that takes place across each of the three themes. Control is negotiated away from the traditional halls of power, with the voices and advocacy of the research community appearing to influence consequential federal policy. Traditional markers of quality – particularly those argued to reflect peer esteem – are challenged by new notions of quality that champion characteristics that can help demonstrate trustworthiness and accessibility to new participants. Traditional notions of value are also challenged, as advocates urge their peers, administrators, and funders to think instead about

³⁷⁷ Lane, “Let’s Make Science Metrics More Scientific,” 488.

the value that science should serve to its beneficiaries. Traditional notions of valued contributions and contributors are similarly contested, as calls rise to broaden the scope of what is understood as a valuable output, to unseat gatekeepers, and to devise more inclusive reward structures. Federal policy provides leadership in this reorientation by centering public access to research outputs as a contribution toward the public good.

Broadly, the dominant take-away from the VDRA period regards the relationship between definition and control. The story of this period is one in which actors drawn from previously disparate and, in some cases, opposed domains created and new activist community dedicated to advancing change across what has, over time, evolved into a dynamic research ecosystem. They have begun to affect this change by transforming the terms of engagement, intentionally reengineering systems to reflect and reward redefined notions of good science and valuable returns.

7.0 Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

As I began to write this dissertation, a new chapter in research assessment asserted itself – that of “Gold Standard” Science. Dawning with an Executive Order (EO) by President Donald J. Trump on May 23, 2025, the era of “Gold Standard” Science is openly unconcerned with objectivity, claiming an unsubstantiated loss of faith in science on the part of the American people as its mandate.³⁷⁸ Within its first paragraph, the Executive Order on “Restoring Gold Standard Science” claims the language of the VDRA period, citing at first the “reproducibility crisis” and, in the next sentence, falsification of data as the reasons why Americans no longer trust scientists to act in their best interests.³⁷⁹ The solution proposed centers nine qualifiers that must be met to ensure this “Gold Standard” of federally funded science, including that it must be reproducible, transparent, “skeptical of its findings and assumptions”, and free from conflicts of interest.³⁸⁰ Measures to support agencies’ shift to “Gold Standard” Science are not addressed, however “enforcement” and the treatment of “violations” are.³⁸¹ Here, the EO prioritizes individual judgement over objectivity, mandating the deputization of a “senior appointee designated by the

³⁷⁸ Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science.”

³⁷⁹ Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science.”

³⁸⁰ Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science.”

³⁸¹ Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science.”

agency head [who] shall provide for taking appropriate measures to correct scientific information” and, at their discretion, elevate the matter to human resources.³⁸²

The advent of Gold Standard Science is a nascent development in the landscape of science policy and research assessment – time will tell whether it begins a new period or whether the effects of Trump's EO will be limited to his second term. Understood within the longer historical arc traced in this dissertation, however, this development can be read as an intensification of prior trends. While the Order does not speak directly to indicators, it does reflect familiar concerns, particularly those regarding the legitimacy and governance of science. This episode thus invites urgent consideration of the vehicles, strategies, and rhetoric that have been leveraged in the negotiation of control, quality, and value across the research enterprise. The discussion that follows returns to this longer history.

7.2 Discussion

This dissertation opened by asking how science indicators have evolved as tools of science policy and research assessment over the course of three distinct periods. It has asked, further, how control over the research enterprise has been understood in light of its exercise across research assessment regimes and, relatedly, how understandings of research quality and value have consequently evolved. The analysis spans three periods: the 1970s emergence of science indicators across policy and bibliometric contexts; the late 1990s through early 2000s crystallization of the

³⁸² Trump, “Restoring Gold Standard Science.”

Science of Science Policy agenda amid an intensification of rising scientometric debate; and the values-driven research assessment period, spanning roughly 2012 through 2025, in which reformers frustrated by indicator-focused research assessment and other limitations of the research ecosystem engineered coordinated interventions across social and technical infrastructures to direct researcher behavior towards morally inflected behaviors. Iterative thematic analysis was employed over a large and heterogeneous corpus of textual documents produced contemporaneously with each period analyzed, training focus on those areas in which expressed priorities, assumptions, and agendas might address the study's guiding research questions. These questions asked how science indicators evolved in their dual policy and evaluative roles over time and, further, how related debates across affected communities reflect changing priorities and assumptions in research assessment. The ensuing analysis highlighted three interrelated themes relevant to this inquiry – those of control, quality, and value.

This research has demonstrated that across the three periods examined, indicators have served in their most essential capacity as representational devices that have rendered scientific activity legible to decisionmakers, enabling comparison and informing resource allocation. This legibility focuses attention on definition, as it is definition that raises priorities and assumptions to level of visibility. From at least the 1970s through to the present moment, definition has served to specify what science is, how scientific activity can be recognized as “good”, and what it should do for and is worth to its beneficiaries. The role of indicators across this history has been to operationalize these definitions and make them both calculable and actionable within administrative contexts. In the Science Indicators period, definitional authority was readily, visibly and openly contested. Actors from across the research and policy ecosystems responded to NSB's *Science Indicators* series with a variety of critiques that are all rooted in definition: What is

science? What is its unit of analysis? How do we know if it is “healthy”? What is it worth, and to whom should its reward fall? During this period, policymakers sought aggregate representations of scientific capacity and performance to answer these questions, while members of the scientific community actively contested what such representations might legitimately claim. It was here that citation analysis – a product of the research community – entered the policy repertoire as well, asserted as a proxy for significance and premised on a recognition of value that was limited in appreciation to the research community itself.

This analysis shows that in the Science of Science period, definitional work shifted into data systems and analytic frameworks designed to improve governance, with definitions evolving into categories and thus gaining durability as they were embedded in administrative tools and platforms. On the policy side, indicators matured as decision-making devices and became compiled into technical infrastructure that had been intentionally designed to advance science policy agendas. Meanwhile, the similarly matured discipline of scientometrics also asserted its will, countering the mounting use of impact factors with metrics designed to reflect more specific components of, and activities across, the research ecosystem.

It is in the Values-Driven Research Assessment period that the definitions sought and negotiated throughout the prior two periods have become more deeply encoded. In response to concerns regarding the inaccuracy, constraints, and undesirable effects of indicator-driven research assessment – and in an effort to “incentivize” idealized behavior advancing open science and other ethically motivated change – researchers and policymakers have joined forces amid the growing ranks of reform advocates. Values-driven behavior, such as the open sharing of research results, protocol, and peer review outcomes, is now being strategically incentivized through the creation of indicators engineered to “capture” instances of open science activity. In such a scheme, control

is thus exercised through infrastructure design at both the social and technical levels, enhancing the portability and administrative reach of indicators.

The findings shared here suggest that the notion of quality in science or research remains persistently refractory to capture, ultimately dependent on a definition of terms. This research suggests that these definitions have regularly gone unstated, packaged into the proxy measures developed to “indicate” quality. In the Science Indicators period, citation analysis served as the primary measure, advanced by policy makers, information scientists, and others as a suitable indicator of quality. Arguments in favor of the use of citation measures were largely premised on the long history of citation as a marker of significance, influence and, to some extent, endorsement across research communities. Research supporting their use as quality indicators was structured around this correlation, however critics across multiple contexts questioned the preferential focus on research outputs, highlighting a challenging distinction between evaluating the process of science and evaluating its products.

This research demonstrates that by the turn of the Science of Science period, policymakers had become less interested in capturing research quality. Indeed, the leading finding of an NSTC Interagency Task Group convened to support OSTP director John Marburger in advancing a “science of science policy” determined that the traditional use of qualitative judgement across research communities to be, as best, insufficient to meet their needs. Per the science of science policy, it was those characteristics that indicate high quality science that were advanced in support of a policy apparatus that might be more empirically grounded and defensible – “more scientific”. While related appeals were made to recruit the scientific community into the effort, many researchers, some of whom were active contributors to a strengthening scientometric community,

expressed concern about the effect that quantitative measurement was having on the very scientific quality that was so lauded.

This research further demonstrates that as the Values-Driven Research Assessment period emerged, attention refocused on process over product, with actors across multiple contexts advocating for the intentional alignment of assessment with values. In such a context, quality has been repositioned as something that is evidenced through action – to the extent that indicators can be “attached” to instances of values-driven action such as sharing or reusing research data, quality can be captured through strategically designed systems of incentivization and reward. Quality is therefore decoupled from influence and attributed instead to choice, vesting researchers, administrators, and policymakers with the responsibility of acting in accordance with the purported values of the scientific community. Many of these are themselves attached to openness, which is positioned as a means of creating the conditions under which the highest ideals of science might be achieved.

This analysis shows that across the literature examined in this research, the quality of research has been regularly conflated with its value. An assertion of this dissertation is that the two are in fact distinct, the former evident in how “good” research is and the latter typified by the good that it does. Quality is of course denoted by qualitative concerns – the characteristics that are constitutive of research done well. Per the definitions guiding this analysis, value is by contrast evident in quantifiable measures of the effect of research – by its impact. Such a clear parsing of concepts is enabled by the contest over research quality and value that is evident throughout the history of research assessment detailed here. At the start of that history, during the Science Indicators period, citation analysis is argued by NSF to serve as a reasonable indicator of quality. Researchers themselves are not so sure, as some investigate the very nature of the claim while

others assert quite clearly that if citation is to be taken as a marker of value it must be well understood that that value is meaningful only within the research community itself.

Evidencing the value of research to the taxpaying public is a primary concern of policy makers during the Science Indicators period. Those researchers who are engaged in the conversation raise multiple and quite nuanced concerns of their own, each of which suggests that science and research, as heterogeneous social processes the outcomes of which vest variably over time are not ideal econometric subjects. Nevertheless, the ability to demonstrate – and maximize – returns on investment become a driving policy priority by the late 1990s. John Marburger and his collaborators are explicitly concerned with the quantifiability of research outputs, as it is through that quantifiability that research investments can be both justified and informed. Marburger calls upon the tools and methodologies of economics to serve as a guide in this work, arguing that such expertise – particularly drawn from social science fields – should be leveraged to advance a “scientific” science policy.

During this period, scientometric researchers are similarly concerned with quantifiability, however this research demonstrates that across the sources analyzed, the focus of this discourse fixes on the accuracy and effects of quantification. Towards the former, new metrics are introduced and negotiated, many advanced as an improvement in the measurement of research impact. Towards the latter, researchers appear increasingly sensitive to the effects that evaluative bibliometrics are having on research culture. Scholars such as Roger Burrows and Ronald Day suggest that the warnings of the prior period – foretelling of a focus on representation rather than on the characteristics being represented – are bearing out. Ronald Day in particular reflects on the emergence of “citation economies,” in which it is not research quality or value that are sought but

rather the purported indicators of them – a reality in which calculated metrics begin to stand in for the more nuanced contours of one’s scholarly career.

Throughout each of the historical periods analyzed, the beneficiaries of research are generally agreed to be the taxpaying public. Their concerns and interests are foregrounded during the Science Indicators period, shift to the background amid the methodological debates of the Science of Science Period, and are energetically returned to center stage during the period of Values-Driven Research Assessment, during which point it is argued by researchers, advocates, and policymakers alike that mere access to the results of scientific research can constitute a public benefit. With science positioned as, fundamentally, a public good, value is sought in new forms and via new media and expression. As such, the collective understanding of the value of scientific research is intentionally expanded to express and include diversity in format, discipline, platform, and contributor.

There is a central tension across each of the periods analyzed and themes surfaced in this research – a tension that concerns who gets to define what science is, whose values are encoded in prevailing notions about what “good” science is, and who, ultimately, science should serve. This research has demonstrated that upon the first introduction of formal science indicators in the early 1970s, scientists instantly recognized the implications of their debut – “a precarious task,” warned Gerald Holton.³⁸³ Decades after the reports’ launch, and well into the reign of bibliometric impact assessment, policymakers remained stymied by the inherent challenges of measuring the outcome of research investments. Meanwhile, researchers remained vociferously resistant to indicator

³⁸³ Holton, “Can Science Be Measured?,” 43.

driven research assessment, busily redesigning bibliometric methodologies to more precisely capture characteristics of interest and also diligently documenting the systemic effects IDRA was having on the research ecosystem more broadly. In response to these and other rising concerns, researchers, activists, policymakers and others came together during the Values-Driven Research Assessment period to reclaim control, not only redefining quality and value on their terms, but also engineering new indicators to incentivize and reward the precise kinds of behavior that they believed would advance their value-driven priorities.

This research thus helps to reframe the relationship between science indicators and science governance, suggesting that it is in the act of establishing the terms of evaluation that control is asserted. It therefore suggests potentially meaningful nuance to prior scholarship. In 2005, Benoît Godin concluded that at the moment of their introduction, science indicators were not conceived of as overt means of control over research behavior.³⁸⁴ This is borne out in the findings shared here as well. However, what also emerges in this research is that regardless of any initial intent, science indicators did evolve into and were eventually claimed as explicit means of engineering outcomes. The argument made here is not that this evolution was predetermined, nor that the relationship illustrated was causal. Much to the contrary, what is suggested here has very much to do with risks incurred by proxy measurement and exacerbated by politics. These risks are considered in the following section, which also offers recommendations for their mitigation.

³⁸⁴ Godin, *Measurement and Statistics on Science and Technology: 1920 to the Present*, 3.

7.3 Recommendations

This research was undertaken in effort to better understand the evolution of science indicators as means of science policy and research assessment, particularly as they have been developed and deployed at the interface of scientific practice and policymaking institutions. As discussed above, this dissertation centered what can be loosely characterized as three case studies illustrating this history across a fifty-year arc and at specific moments of unique intervention into research assessment practices and the governance of science in the U.S. In the negotiations documented by this research, actors across each period actively negotiated control over the terms by which and the power through which research was to be assessed and rewarded. The dialogues traced here illustrate long-running debates about and, increasingly, activism designed to mitigate the effects of indicator-driven research assessment on the ecosystem of research itself. These debates and related activism are as active today as they ever have been, imbued with perhaps a new sense of urgency in light of a new and, to many, shocking exercise of control at the Executive level. Inspired by this analysis of fifty years of discourse, research, and negotiation, several recommendations can be made to guide both indicator-driven research assessment initiatives specifically and systemic reform efforts more broadly.

Identify and define terms operationalized in research assessment.

This recommendation reflects a recurring theme across the discourse, particularly as it relates to impact factors. Across all three periods studied, it becomes evident that indicators frequently operationalize otherwise complex, contextual terms without isolating or explicitly defining the assumptions embedded in those terms. As indicators become routinized, these terms risk becoming black boxed, shifting attention from what is being represented to the numerical

output itself. The historical record examined here suggests that isolating and defining operationalized terms supports a clearer – indeed, an intentional – articulation of what an indicator is intended to capture, what it necessarily excludes, and the conditions under which it is captured. Such documentary effort would support greater interpretive clarity across the broader research ecosystem, particularly as indicators travel across institutional and policy contexts.

Be cognizant of the differences between quality and value.

This recommendation builds on the prior and highlights the specific imperative to intentionally distinguish between quality and value when implementing or interpreting evaluative science indicators. This research has illuminated the extent to which conflation of the two has confounded the discourse surrounding science indicators and research assessment for at least fifty years. It has also suggested that quality and value do not always hold audience, import, or beneficiaries in common. Before taking on any effort to evaluate “the goodness” or the value of a particular research output or effort, it is important that evaluators take the time to distinguish, first, which they wish to evaluate for, and only then begin the work of identifying which signals might suggest the achievement of their identified goal.

Acknowledge and protect the space between an indicator and its subject.

Throughout the many decades in which indicators have been used as instruments of policy and assessment, scholars have called attention to the fact that indicators are choices. Rather than reflecting any natural law or objective relationship, indicators are selected by people in response to contextual constraints and temporal influence; their relationship to the phenomenon or characteristic they are chosen to represent is therefore neither natural nor self-evident. To acknowledge and protect the space between indicator and indicated is to resist the tendency, demonstrated throughout their use, for indicators to become black-boxed, treated as though they

are synonymous with the phenomena they signify rather than as necessarily partial and innately purposive proxies.

By continually and intentionally rendering the indicator–subject relationship explicit, evaluators and those subject to evaluation are each reminded that alternative representations are always possible, and therefore that agreement on an indicator does not imply agreement on its meaning or adequacy. Practices that illuminate this interpretive gap can help mitigate the drift toward numerical substitution, wherein attention shifts from research activity to its proxy, and can retain space for individual and collective judgment. Such a dedicated practice would protect the ability to contest whether a given indicator meaningfully captures what it claims to measure, thereby serving to support not only greater clarity of interpretation, but also autonomy and agency across the research ecosystem.

Exercise humility when using leveraging indicators as evaluative tools.

Throughout the history of indicator-driven research assessment, researchers and commentators have repeatedly urged caution when using science indicators to effect change across what is, ultimately, a complex sociotechnical ecology. The call made here is for humility, and for due deference to the potential consequences of intervening in the self-correcting dynamics of science and research. This study suggests that the introduction of evaluative indicators into social environments can have enduring and system-wide effects that extend well beyond their initial intent, particularly when they become portable across organizational and policy environments. It is in this context that the historical record shows most clearly that, when paired with reward, indicators operate as instruments of governance. Humility in their use therefore entails intentional, sustained, and deferential attention to the broader ecological dynamics they enter.

7.4 Future Research

This dissertation examined fifty years of interaction between members of the science policy and research communities as they negotiated the terms and tools of the research assessment landscape. This research was designed specifically to explore this particular negotiation across three specific period in history, leveraging documents – largely peer reviewed publications, reports, and editorials – as the evidentiary base supporting thematic analysis. Throughout the course of this research, multiple other themes and potential frames emerged, each suggestive of related inquiries that could be quite valuable to a more comprehensive examination of the factors affecting the evolution of science indicators as tools of science policy and research assessment in the U.S.

Chapter Four details the launch of NSB’s *Science Indicators* series, establishing, from an explicitly policy perspective, the “birth” of indicator-driven research assessment in the U.S. As documented in that chapter, this research suggests that while input into the design of the series and its inaugural indicators was in many respects limited to NSB and NSF staff, select external experts were also engaged. Francis Narin and his firm Computer Horizons Ltd. were known to have been contracted to produce a report on the viability of evaluative bibliometrics as indicators of research quality, for example. There is also evidence to suggest that Eleanor Bernert Sheldon and the Social Science Research Council were also called upon to advise on the role of science indicators as, ultimately, social indicators. Dedicated exploration of the explicit contribution of the social sciences and, more specifically, the SSRC, into the original design and implementation of the first class of NSB’s science indicators would afford valuable insight into not only the conditions under

which those indicators were developed but also how and whether they were anticipated to function within the social system into which they were about to be introduced.

Throughout the course of this research I became very interested in the seemingly porous boundary between the research and science policy communities. Certainly, this arose as much out of my own experience working at the precise site of this boundary as it did from the research I was simultaneously conducting. During the time that I began this research, I also served as the Executive Secretary of the NSTC Subcommittee on the Year of Open Science and, later, of the NSTC Subcommittee on Open Science Engagement. In this capacity, I supported policy professionals from dozens of federal agencies in drafting, implementing, and socializing open science policy across the agencies and research communities they represented. Specifically, I served as a NASA contractor, representing the agency at the White House, at conferences, and at workshops, all in service of engaging decision makers at the policy, administrative, and research levels. Working in such a capacity provided unparalleled insight into the extent to which, at the federal level, it can become difficult to discern between research and policy interests, as policymakers are quite often drawn from the sciences and in many contexts simultaneously pursue research and policy initiatives.

Through the course of my research, I therefore became particularly interested in understanding more about the legacy of the NSF's Science of Science and Innovation Policy (SciSIP) program, particularly as it might pertain to the integrated policy, research, and advocacy efforts that emerged in the Values-Driven Research Assessment period. As described in its introductory prospectus, the SciSIP program was launched in pursuit of three primary goals – to:

“(1) develop usable knowledge and theories of creative processes and their transformation into social and economic outcomes; (2) improve and expand science metrics, datasets and

analytical tools...; and (3) develop a community of experts across the Federal government, industry and universities focused on SciSIP.”³⁸⁵ Investigating the success of the program as might be defined by these three goals could yield valuable insight into the social processes at work within the structure of science as well as across any boundary between the science and federal science policy communities that may exist. Further, it may also provide insight into the cross-functional coalition of researchers, policy makers, and advocates who joined forces to advance a shared agenda during the Values-Driven Research Assessment period.

The Values-Driven Research Assessment period may itself serve as valuable site of inquiry, particularly as response to values-driven research assessment efforts continues to emerge. There is already a body of scholarship dedicated to critiques and questions raised about the claims of the open science movement in particular. Tracing the development of these critiques could prove valuable in further understanding how control continues to be negotiated, and how explicit efforts to affect “culture change” either achieve these ends or result in other, perhaps unintended consequences across the ecosystem.

Finally, and as previously discussed, the findings of this dissertation suggest that determinations about research quality and value are dependent on audience. This relationship can therefore be reasonably extrapolated to a consideration of funding source, and what implications funding arrangements bear relative to the terms of research assessment. The *Science Indicators* reports originated partly out of a need to demonstrate returns on the country’s first several decades of research investment. In the years since, a difficult relationship between scientists, their

³⁸⁵ National Science Foundation, “Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences Science of Science and Innovation Policy: A Prospectus,” 1.

benefactors, and beneficiaries has emerged. This dissertation documents one manifestation of that relationship. It may prove illuminating to extend a similar analytic framework exploring how control, quality, and value are both expressed and negotiated in the context of private funding – particularly that which comes from institutions such as the Howard Hughes Medical Institute, which is known for affording its staff researchers considerable autonomy.³⁸⁶

7.5 Conclusion

Should the Gold Standard Science Executive Order prove to have long-term consequences for research governance in the U.S., future researchers might note that the first signs of this were evident in the language used in the Order. Beyond simply reiterating the language of the VDRA and research reform efforts that preceded it, the Order in fact repurposes them, in effect asserting new ownership over terms such as “rigor,” “responsibility,” and “integrity” by not only reasserting their policy primacy but, likely more consequentially, by definitively relocating the right to define evaluative terms from the scientific community to political appointees. This dissertation has traced a history in which the right to define – the authority to define – has been contested over many decades and many emergent political contexts. Throughout this period, members of the scientific community have issued multiple warnings about the danger inherent in indications – that there can be a tendency to focus on these indications rather than on the phenomena they have been selected to represent.

³⁸⁶ Howard Hughes Medical Institute, “Scientific Research at HHMI,” HHMI, accessed March 1, 2026, <https://www.hhmi.org/research>.

This dissertation suggests that this tendency may have also been at work in the very negotiations about science indicators – that in the long and energetically contested history of their development, focus was trained on them, as warnings about their effects went repeatedly unheeded. A contribution of this dissertation is that it has provided some documentation of this process again at work – one in which, over time, language has been leveraged with increasing – and increasingly normalized – distance between indicator and indicated. The portability engendered by this move may well create a vulnerability in meaning that can be exploited by actors of all backgrounds and agendas. Here it is helpful to recall one of the unique characteristics of infrastructure – that it is owned by no one. It may be that in their collective use and negotiation, sociotechnical infrastructures are particularly vulnerable, in that the social component of these systems is comprised of a series of relationships and agreements. For a sociotechnical infrastructure to “work”, these commitments must be treated with care.

Appendix A Documentary Corpora

Appendix A.1 Science Indicators Period Documentary Corpora

Policy & Governance Records

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Appendix B Codebook

APPENDIX B Table 1 Codebook

Category	Code	Definition
Control		Attempts to, desire to, or instances of influence over outcomes.
	Locality	Reflecting local values, priorities, and other interests in assessment interventions
	Incentives	Mechanisms through which particular research behaviors, outputs, or priorities are rewarded
Quality		Qualitative reference to or proxy measure of what makes research “good”
	Significance	Qualitative judgments about the perceived importance of a scholarly work within a field or discourse
	Effects of Indicators	Effects of IDRA on the observed quality of research
	Reproducibility	The extent to which a study or some component of a study could be replicated
	Responsibility	Normative claims about the obligations of researchers to act in ways that serve and protect others
	Rigor	The epistemic soundness of research practices
Value		Reference to or measure of what good research does, who it benefits
	Impact	The effect that research has had

	ROI	Returns on investments in research. "What do we get for our money?"
	Beneficiaries	Populations to whom the benefits of research accrue

Appendix C List of Acronyms

AAAS – American Association for the Advancement of Science

ACI – American Competitiveness Initiative

ARRA – American Recovery and Reinvestment Act

CAQDAS - Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software

COS – Center for Open Science

CUDOS – Communism, Universalism, Disinterestedness, and Organized Skepticism

DOE – Department of Energy

DORA – San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment

EO – Executive Order

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

FORCE11 – The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship

GAO – General Accounting Office

GPRA – Government Performance and Results Act

HumetricsHSS – Humane Metrics in the Humanities and Social Sciences

IDRA – Indicator-Driven Research Assessment

ISI – Institute for Scientific Information

ITG – Interagency Task Group

JIF – Journal Impact Factor

NASEM – National Academics of Science, Engineering, and Medicine

NDRC – National Defense Research Committee

NIH – National Institutes of Health

NIST – National Institute of Standards and Technology

NSB – National Science Board

NSF – National Science Foundation

NSTC – National Science and Technology Council

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OMB – Office of Management and Budget

ORCID – Open Researcher and Contributor ID

OSI – Open Science Indicators

OSRD – Office of Scientific Research and Development

OSTP – Office of Science and Technology Policy

PART – Program Assessment Rating Tool

PLACE – Proprietary, Local, Authoritarian, Commissioned, and Expert

PLOS – The Public Library of Science

PRT – Promotion, Review, and Tenure

ROI – Return on Investment

RSA – Research Support Activities

SBE – Behavioral and Economic Sciences

SCI – Science Citation Index

SI – Science Indicators

SOS – Science of Science

SOSP – Science of Science Policy

SSRC – Social Science Research Council

S&T – Science and Technology

STAR METRICS – Science and Technology for America's Reinvestment: Measuring the Effect of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science

STS – Science and Technology Studies

TOP – Transparency and Openness Promotion

UNESCO – United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization

VDRA – Values–Driven Research Assessment

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